

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

Department of Economics LM-56

Second Cycle Degree in Economics and Econometrics

Quantifying Innovation's Impact on CO₂

A Meta-Regression Analysis of Current Econometric
Evidence

Supervisor:
Prof.
Maria Elena Bontempi

Author:
Francesco Baraccani

Session March 2025

Academic Year 2024/2025

Quantifying Innovation's Impact on CO2:

A Meta-Regression Analysis of Current Econometric Evidence

Francesco Baraccani

March 2025

Abstract

This study employs Meta-Regression Analysis (MRA) to assess the impact of innovation on CO2 emissions, synthesizing findings from 49 econometric studies. The analysis addresses publication bias and investigates the role of research design in shaping reported estimates. Results confirm that while innovation generally reduces CO2 emissions, its effectiveness is highly heterogeneous. The findings ultimately produce extensive evidence on the theoretical aspects of eco-innovation. These insights clarify the conditions under which innovation serves as a driver of environmental sustainability.

Keywords:

Innovation · R&D · CO2 · Greenhouse Gases · Environment · Climate Change · Global Warming · Meta-Analysis · Meta-Regression · Selection Bias · Publication Bias

Contents

Contents	2
1 Introduction	3
2 The relation between R&D and CO2	5
2.1 The Global Climate Change Problem	5
2.1.1 The Rise of Global Climate Action	5
2.1.2 The Innovation Nexus	6
2.1.3 Policies Adoption and Transition Performance Index in OECD	8
2.2 Environmental and Sustainable Innovation: A Literature Review	14
2.2.1 Drivers of Eco-Innovation And of Its Efficacy	16
2.2.2 Theoretical Models	19
3 Theoretical Foundations of Meta-Regression on Innovation’s Environmental Impact	22
3.1 Research Question and Its Relevance	22
3.2 The Meta-Analysis Approach	23
3.2.1 The Meta-Regression Analysis	26
3.2.2 Empirical Research Process	39
3.2.3 Diagnostic Tests	43
4 The Empirical Research	47
4.1 Dataset	47
4.1.1 Primary Studies Sample	47
4.1.2 Dataset Description	50
4.1.3 Descriptives Statistics	55
4.2 Results	67
4.2.1 The Meta-Regression Probit Model	67
4.2.2 The Publication Bias Meta-Regression Model	72
4.2.3 The Multivariate Meta-Regression Model	80
5 Conclusions	88
References	91
List of Figures	104
List of Tables	106

1 Introduction

The already acting and evident abnormal climate changes seriously raised concerns and stimulated action all around the globe. Total emissions are still rising at the global level, eventually causing temperatures to surge together. The time left to the “point of no return” is running out and world-living species need a solution for their survival as soon as possible.

Political intervention for climate started at the end of the 1980s, and since 1990s governments implemented cooperative actions to mitigate pollution from human activities. The primary aim of this movement is to stabilize the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere at a not dangerous level, in a time frame that allows a natural adaptation of the ecosystem, without hindering economic development. Over the years, the level of commitment of countries has increased vigorously, both in participation and intensity of actions.

Nonetheless, the founding goal of the Paris Agreement of limiting the global average temperature at 1.5°C degrees above the mean preindustrial temperature, signed in 2015, is still far from reaching, if not implausible.

The goal of stabilizing toxic gases emissions, while allowing economic growth, requires the acceleration of their removal from the atmosphere and the reduction of the reliance on carbon-emitting sources. Low-carbon solutions are available, but still not economically convenient with respect to consolidated, more polluting sources of energy.

The creation of new technologies and the consequential technical change requires innovation: to provide cleaner or more environmentally sustainable alternatives, as well as to enhance their applicability and, eventually, their mitigating power. Innovation is therefore the underlying central aim of political action.

The necessity of political intervention steers from market failures, which distances private economic interests from collective priorities. Indeed, as innovation causes both positive and negative externalities, required investments from the private-sector are lower than optimal levels. Hence, the role of public institutions is to stimulate eco-innovations.

Nonetheless, the actual availability of such solutions is still residual and not adequate to meet the scheduled goals. Moreover, stimulating investments in the invention of eco-friendly products is challenging, due to their relatively low economic incentives, long horizons for the realization, and high uncertainty. This poses the need for climate action to be further strengthened, to seriously accelerate the necessary technical changes.

The need to clarify how to effectively accelerate innovation, led to a recent rapidly growing trend in related publications. The main topics of interest are indeed on its drivers.

However, given its novelty and the complexity of its nexus with environment, literature so far failed to provide clear extensive evidence in this field of research.

Anyway, given the urgency of slowing climate change, the world requires well-informed plans of action to pursue.

This analysis is, for what is known, the first attempt to fill the gap of a comprehensive quantitative review of the actual knowledge on the nexus between innovation and greenhouse emissions. The general aim is to assess the empirical evidence reported so far on this presumed causal relationship. To do this, the method used is that of Meta-Regression Analysis (MRA). This systematic, well-defined, and statistically based approach is superior to conventional narrative review, as it is reproducible and, thus, more objective. Moreover, it has higher statistical power than the primary research collected, with which at most shares same weaknesses and limitations.

Most of all, MRA has the power to filter out misspecification biases, naturally arising from research consuetudes and the process of publication: these agents' tendencies lead to the *selection bias*, which potentially distort evidence and ultimately taint public knowledge. Since understanding a social phenomenon requires unbiased evidence, the correction of this conceivable cause of misrepresentation of reality is imperative.

Moreover, additionally to provide an estimate of the true effect of innovation, MRA enables to investigate potentially any thinkable systematic source of deviation from the average reported effect size. This eventually produces statistical evidence on any of the theoretical aspects related to the underlying causal relation. In this sense, drivers of eco-innovation will be tested, and, finally, comprehensive evidence on the aspects discussed by literature produced.

The rest of this analysis is organized as follows. Section 2 provides the theoretical foundations of the empirical part. Section 2.1 starts by describing the political action for global climate change pursued so far, and the centrality of innovation. Then, Section 2.2 presents an extensive literature review on the causal relationship between innovation and environment.

Subsequently, Section 3 will describe the research questions of this empirical analysis (Section 3.1), followed by an in-depth theoretical presentation of the Meta-Regression Analysis approach in Section 3.2: in detail, this latter part will discuss why this method is appropriate for the aim of this research, its theoretical foundations, and describes the process followed in the empirical part. Section 4 describes the empirical research and its results. Section 4.1 describes how the primary studies were collected and the resulting dataset used. Then Section 4.2 presents the models estimated and their results: Section 4.2.1 discusses the Probit Model, used to investigate the characteristics linked to the effectiveness of innovation in reducing CO₂ emissions levels; next, Section 4.2.2 presents the estimations of the true elasticity of innovation and of the intensity of selection bias present in the underlying empirical literature, additionally to a brief investigation of the random heterogeneity of the collected estimates; finally, Section 4.2.3 shows evidences on some factors leading to systematic deviations of estimates.

The analysis ends with Section 5, which provides the conclusions based on the results of the empirical research.

2 The relation between R&D and CO₂

2.1 The Global Climate Change Problem

In recent years, the global climate change problem has become a primary theme of interest: both as a topic of research, as well as a national and international politics theme of discussion.

The importance of this issue has been raised by the attested knowledge of the negative changing effect that human activities have had on climate since the beginning of industrialization. The expansion of economies and, consequentially, also of populations are the original causes of the greenhouse gases induced climate change. The main sources of GHG emissions are: fuel combustion, industries, deforestation, and farming.

Despite of the increasing concern, global energy-related CO₂ emissions are projected to at least double by the mid-century in the absence of mitigation measures (Nakicenovic and Swart, 2000); total emissions are still rising at the global level; and the ultimate international stabilization objective formalized by the Paris Agreement will probably not be met even if all of the national pledges will be achieved (Mor et al., 2024).

2.1.1 The Rise of Global Climate Action

The contribution of politics to limit human-induced climate change has been increasing since its start, as can be deduced from the international climate change policies historical review of the Congressional Research Service of the 2020 (Leggett, 2020).

As described in the review, the former international political intervention can be historically placed around the end of the 1980s, with the institution of the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), to provide United Nations with assessment of climate change science and eventual solution strategies.

But it was only in the 1990s that the international cooperation of governments became formally multilateral, through the institution of the U.N. Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). It follows from the common acceptance that, to achieve the stabilization of GHG concentration on the atmosphere, the participation of all the countries together is needed. The 197 Parties have therefore assumed common obligations to act and to cooperate for the stated primary objective of the treaty: stabilizing the concentration of the toxic gases in the atmosphere at a not dangerous level, in a time frame that allows a natural adaptation of the ecosystem and that enables sustainable development.

The level of commitment increased further with the ratification of the two primary subsidiary agreements of the UNFCCC: the Kyoto Protocol, which entered into force in 2005, then substituted by the Paris Agreement in 2015.

Through the former, 37 high-income, industrialized countries and the European Union were legally bound to reduce GHG emissions by 5% below the 1990 level during 2009-2012. Most of these countries - practically, the European ones - subsequently committed to additional targets for a second

commission period lasting from 2013 to 2020.

Although most of the bound parties have individually met their targets, total global emissions continued to increase (Mor et al., 2024). The overall failure of the KP has therefore been attributed to the fact that developing countries were not committed to emissions reduction, in addition to the non-participation of the United States (Singh, 2006).

Moreover, the GDP of the committed parties has decreased, inconsistently with the goal of sustainable development included in the primary UNFCCC intent.

The first attempt to improve the effectiveness of the former climate treaty, was the Copenhagen Accord of 2009. With this accord also 47 non-high income parties committed to implement climate mitigation actions: among those, high emitters countries as Brazil, China, India, Indonesia, Mexico, Republic of Korea, and South Africa (Buhr et al., 2012).

Although they submitted non-binding pledges, the agreement on national economy-wide GHG quantified emissions reduction targets represented a turn toward a more effective climate action. Indeed, the non-participation of these countries has been a point of contention between UNFCCC and high-income nations, since they anticipated that the developing ones would have grown their economic activities together with their income. This motive has been claimed as the reason for the withdrawal of the USA from the Kyoto Protocol.

Finally, in order to properly offset the problems that led to the acknowledged failures of the first primary subsidiary agreement, the Paris Agreement was based on voluntary pledges, rather than legally binding commitments. The aim is to avoid distributional conflicts, in order to encourage a broader participation from countries: indeed, 196 parties signed this second treaty. As reported in the cited review of the two treaties by Mor et al. (2024), it has in fact promoted low-carbon solutions and moved markets towards carbon neutrality and zero-carbon solutions, with an involvement of areas emitting 70% of global emissions.

However, total global emissions have continued to increase, and the principal goal of the Paris Agreement of limiting the global average temperature at 1.5°C degrees above the mean preindustrial temperature is still implausible. Moreover, like Kyoto Protocol, even the Paris Agreement has been discarded by the USA, possibly affecting the potential to globally manage the climate in the long term (Mor et al., 2024).

2.1.2 The Innovation Nexus

Stabilizing greenhouse gases emissions requires that their removals from the atmosphere balance the quantity released. Removals can only occur through photosynthesis or through advanced technologies. Hence, increasing the ability to remove toxic gases could allow for some level of such emissions from human activities to continue. Moreover, technological change is capable of reducing the economy's reliance on carbon-based fuels, reducing in this way the consequential emissions of GHG (Goulder, 1997).

Moreover, considering the primary goal of economic development, innovation is the pivotal instru-

ment through which to fight human-induced climate change and, thus, the final aim around which all the environmental public strategies are set, in fact. The idea is that to meet this challenge without excessive costs, an extensive innovation is required (Grubb, 2004).

It is because of their higher innovative capacity that the Kyoto Protocol tried to influence the higher-income countries, and on the hope that the promoted environmentally friendly innovation would have finally been spread even in developing nations.

It became even more explicit in the Paris Agreement, where the technology framework aims to encourage the sharing of knowledge and cooperation for the eco-innovation at a broader level (Leggett, 2020). Moreover, 20 countries committed to double their public investment in low-carbon technology (Matos et al., 2022)

It can be said that the ultimate goal of climate policy is to influence the orientation of innovations and the rate at which they occur. There is a consensus that regulation drives sustainable innovation. In fact, policy debates concern the best strategies and measures to promote technological environmental innovation, its adoption, and its diffusion.

The theoretical foundation of an imperative public intervention arises from two market failures: negative externalities from economic activities, not reflected by market prices and, therefore, not accounted in the costs faced by the users; knowledge spillovers, that create benefits also for those not incurring the costs, preventing investors from appropriating all of the advantages stemming by the innovation process. The former lead profit-maximizer economic agents to emit an excessive amount of pollutants. The latter reduces the level of R&D investments below the optimal level.

Public intervention became necessary to internalize the environmental costs that economic activities charge on the society and to support investments on eco-innovation. Given this duality of goals, policies are conventionally classified in one of two types: as market-pulling, which consists of market regulations that aim at encouraging low-GHG technology; or as technology-pushing, which operates instead by directly supporting the research and development processes. Common market-pulling policy instruments are: carbon taxes and quotas; tradable CO₂ or other GHG emissions permits; and subsidies to CO₂ emission abatement. On the other hand, examples of technology-pushing instruments are: subsidies to innovation of low-carbon technologies; public-sector R&D expenditures; government-financed technology competitions; reinforcement of patent rules.

These two classes of intervention increase their effectiveness when operate together, since the assistance to R&D is only functional if the regulatory system provides both the economic incentives and the social infrastructure to accommodate such innovations. Indeed, although market-based policies are generally more effective in promoting innovation adoption, advanced environmental technologies are typically adopted only when required to meet strict emission limits. Simply making these technologies available is not enough to encourage their use (Newell, 2009).

The effects of the policy intervention on the induced technological change operate through two main channels: both the investments on research and development, and the resulting learning-by-doing. The latter consists of the increase in efficiency arising from the experience gained through the usage of innovation, both over time and as they become more widely adopted.

But politics also operates indirectly through initial debates. This can happen in two ways. Firstly, by raising the public concerns: unmet demand for cleaner commodities and services can create market opportunities that can finally encourage investments in innovations by providers. Secondly, prior policy announcements lead to a faster increase in R&D, with the effect growing as their credibility increases. Indeed, innovators foresee the advantage to spread the costs and of installing the required equipment over a wider length of time.

Although the importance of international cooperation for this topic has been highlighted, a full international technology cooperation is challenging.

The diffusion of inventions can be advantageous for all of the parts and practicable. And, because of that, it is a way through which UNFCCC aims to tackle the climate problem.

On the other hand, the innovation process, as it is intrinsically strategic, can unlikely be an object of cooperation: both because of the intellectual property mechanism, which discourages a broad cooperation by nature, and because of international rivalry (Grubb, 2004). That reduces the applicability of international technology-pushing international policies.

Finally, the timing of intervention is crucial.

First of all, the natural removal of CO₂ is extremely low and, even if the annual emissions would be halved, the global average temperature would still increase for about two or three decades (Lee et al., 2021b). And also accounting for GHG removals from technologies would not change this result, since those actually affordable and used only remove and store less than 1% of what will be needed to meet the goal of 1.5°C by 2030 (Olhoff et al., 2024).

Moreover, although technological advancement should decrease the cost of abatement in the future, possibly giving advantages to the increase of abatement efforts in the long term, learning-by-doing mechanism encourages to take action immediately: indeed, the experience and knowledge gained in the near term benefits efficiency and effectiveness in the future (Goulder, 1997).

2.1.3 Policies Adoption and Transition Performance Index in OECD

In order to evaluate the effects of the political mobilization on environmental transition, it can be useful to compare data on climate policies adoption and the environmental performance in the respective geographical areas.

In particular, here the focus is on the OECD. On the one hand, because this represents a group of high-income, developed countries, which are the ones where the political action for climate has started. Moreover, due to the abundance of readily accessible data, focusing on this area allows a complete and consistent comparison of the measures of interest.

Figure 1: Environmental policies adoption and stringency trends between 2011 and 2019

Bars represent the OECD countries' average number of adopted policies per type. The green line represents the average aggregate number of climate policies adopted. The red line depicts the average stringency level of all the policies adopted.

Source: OECD (2023)

The upper graph in figure 1 shows: the countries' average number of the different kinds of environmental policies and actions; the trends of the average aggregate number of measures adopted by each country (green continuous line), and their average stringency level (red dotted line). This framework of analysis recalls the Climate Actions and Policies Measurement Framework (CAPMF) adopted by the IPAC countries (OECD members and accession candidates, G20 countries and the European Union) to classify, evaluate, and support the climate action. In details,

CAPMF database is structured across three building blocks: sectoral policies (grey bars in the graph), which apply to a specific source or economic sector; cross-sectoral policies, which aims to mitigate or remove GHG emissions that cannot be addressed to a specific sector (blue bars); and international policies (yellow), that consist in international agreements.

Given that the focus of the main analysis is on innovation, the graph highlights also the trend of one specific example of cross-sectional policy: the average number of RD&D public expenditures plans adopted by countries (orange bars).

This classification differs from the one that distinguishes technology-pushing and market-pulling policies: here the classification is based on the extension of the policy with the general aim of reducing GHG emissions, rather than how to foster technological change.

CAPMF also classifies each of the policies by their stringency level, between zero and ten, according to how much the policy incentivises or enables GHG emissions mitigation (Nachtigall et al., 2022).

Data on climate policies adoption and on the respective average stringency level in OECD countries for the period considered are provided in Table A in the Appendix.

The bottom graph in figure 1 depicts the average annual growth rate of the number of policies adopted by countries (green bars) and that of their average stringency level (red bars).

Although countries increased both the number of policies and their stringency during the whole time period, the analysis of the trends can be sub-divided in two periods: one trend between 2011 and 2015, and a different tendency afterwards. This likely reflects the entry into force of the Paris Agreement in 2015.

In the first of the two phases, the adoption of sectoral policies (which is the category with the highest number of actions and policies and, because of that, the highest bar) and that of international policies had a relatively high average growth rate: respectively 2.8% and 17% between 2012 and 2015. In this phase, cross-sectoral policies had the lowest average annual growth speed (2.36%). Public RD&D plans average number remained stable until 2019 (the average annual variation between 2011 and 2018 was 0.6%), when it reached the peak of the period thanks to an annual 10.6% increase.

From 2016, the yearly rate of adoption slowed: while the adoption of cross-sectoral policies accelerated (annual average increased by 9% between 2016 and 2019), those of both sectoral and international decreased their growth pace (1.96% and 0.51% the annual adoption variation in this second period).

On the other hand, as it can be seen in the bottom graph of figure 1, the average level of stringency yearly growth surged after 2015: this value passed from 2.6 out of 10 in 2015, to 4.5 in 2019. This is mainly due to the growth of cross-sectoral policies stringency after 2016, when its average level increased by 90% in one year and reached an average annual growth rate of 35% between 2016 and 2019 (compared to an average annual growth of 1.5% between 2011 and 2015). Additionally, also the stringency of the other two types of policy continued to grow in the last four years considered: that of international policies at an average annual rate of 13.6% (compared to an almost 5% aver-

age during 2011-2015); that of sectoral policies at an average annual rate of 3.3% (compared to a 4.3% average between 2011 and 2015).

To evaluate the results of the increase in both adoption and stringency of climate policies in OECD, this analysis can be compared to that of the trends of the Transition Performance Index (TPI) of the European Commission. This index has been introduced to measure the transformational changes required to enhance the adaptability and to slow climate change. These changes aim at an environmental sustainable and inclusive growth of the European economy, in accordance with the European Green Deal targets for 2050. Consistently with that, TPI is the average of four sub-indexes: the economic transition index, which measures the progress towards a resilient and sustainable economic growth; the environmental transition index, which represents the efforts to reduce the environmental footprint of economic activities; the social transition index, which assess the level of fairness and inclusion of the country's society; and the governance transition index, which measures the level of democracy.

Each index is then furtherly subdivided in four specific indexes. Each of them has a scale of measurement between zero and 100, and the higher-level index is the average of them (European Commission et al., 2022).

Consistently with the scope of this comparison, the analysis is focused on the environmental and the economic indexes, to evaluate how OECD performed in reducing their impact on environment and their reliance on resources, and on some of their sub-indexes interesting for the primary analysis, which are: R&D intensity, energy productivity, and gross GHG emissions. The European Commission computes this measures for 72 countries of the world, so not only for the European ones: consequently, it can be used to measure OECD countries transition progress.

Data on economic and environmental transition index of OECD countries are provided in Table B in the Appendix.

Figure 2: Economic and Environmental Transition Indexes Trends

The left-hand side scale represents the unit of measure of the bars. The right-hand side scale represents the unit of measures of the lines.

Source: European Commission (2021)

The blue and the yellow bars in figure 2 represent the OECD’s average environmental and economic transition indexes, respectively. The former has always been higher during the considered period. However, it has lowered between 2011 and 2019, passing from an average of almost 36 out of 100 to almost 33 (-8%). Economic transition index was stable at the level of 22.

Among the sub-indexes of economic transition, R&D intensity also remained stable. Indeed, as it can be seen by its average yearly rate of variation (the black dashed line in figure 2) the peak of growth between 2015 and 2016 and in 2019 was compensated by the negative rates in all the other years. Hence, this trend is consistent with the one of the average public expenditure in innovation, represented in figure 1.

For what concerns the sub-indexes of environmental transition, energy productivity similarly had a negative trend, having it been reduced by 6% from 2011. On the other hand, GHG emissions, which negatively affects the environmental transition index, had an almost 11% reduction from the starting year, and its annual growth rate has been positive only in 2017.

Hence, we can conclude that the steady increase of climate policy adoption and their stringency in OECD countries did not implied more sustainable and eco-friendly economies between 2011 and 2019 in OECD. Moreover, environmental policies failed in encouraging innovation and energy productivity. Nonetheless, OECD accomplished in GHG emissions reduction, with an average yearly

rate of reduction of 1.41%.

However, conclusions on the effectiveness of policies can hardly be done by this summary comparison, nor a failure of the climate approach adopted can be claimed. Moreover, a simultaneous comparison might not reflect the real effectiveness of environmental measures, since their effects might need years to get significant results. Rather, it can only be assessed the need for the climate action to continue and to be strengthened to accelerate the environmental transition of OECD economies.

2.2 Environmental and Sustainable Innovation: A Literature Review

Innovation refers to the practical implementation of inventions that take root from modern needs and requirements, through the provision of more effective products, services, technologies, or processes (Mensah et al., 2018). When it aims at balancing the present needs with the ones of the future generations, taking into account the natural capacity to remove and store emissions, it is called sustainable innovation. When the original need is to reduce the overall human impact on the environment, it is defined environmental innovation (García et al., 2014).

Finally, technological change takes place when the results of innovation are employed to produce in a more efficient way. In the context of environmental or sustainable innovation, it allows to reduce the economy's reliance on carbon-based fuels, finally reducing carbon dioxide emissions (Goulder, 1997).

The interest in the topic of innovation for climate change is still increasing, as testified by the increase in the related publications from 1990, and by its surge from 2005 onward (Figure 3). Matos et al. (2022) point out that it may reflect a response to the international mobilization described in section 2.1.1: the main discussed research subjects are the climate change mitigation and the sustainable transition, together with empirical analysis.

Moreover, it may also represent the increasing concerns from private businesses, as firms are becoming more aware of their consequences on the ecosystem and are increasing their investments in environmental and sustainable innovation. At the same time, it is a relatively young and highly interdisciplinary field, with much yet to be discovered. (García et al., 2014).

Figure 3: Number of papers related to innovation for climate change in the top ten innovation journals (1990-2021).

Source: Matos et al. (2022)

The urge of innovating the energy and the transport sectors comes from the projected scarce availability of conventional resources, together with issues in both the delivery and usage of renewable alternatives.

In fact, total energy resources are not limited. And the same is true for low-carbon solutions. The problem is that the conventional, high-carbon oil is still the main fuel used, and its demand is expected to outpace supply.

On the other hand, despite their potential, wide availability, and falling costs, less-polluting substitutes remain neither practical nor economical for the current system. Hence, climate problem can be solved in fact, but it requires an enormous increase of innovative technologies (Grubb, 2004).

Although feasibility of eco-friendly technologies has increased, low-carbon technological progress has been too slow to achieve the temperature goals of the Paris Agreement, and investments are still scarce (Matos et al., 2022). This is due to the high level of complexity and riskiness of the new energy sectors.

The yet cited work from Grubb (2004) describes in details the issues of innovation in the power sector.

First of all, the power generating sector is low-innovative. The innovative process is capital-intensive and takes long time, which raise the risk of investments; diffusion of innovations is slow, which also lowers profitability; and strategic competition is around price-efficiency of an identical product (electronics), rather than on product-differentiation, as it is in other highly-innovative sectors instead. Political risks also discourage investments: they concern the installation of usually large physical facilities, and the lobbies' pressure against carbon pricing, which in fact slows its implementation.

What furthermore deters environmental innovation is that, being oil the source that has dominated the power industry for decades, knowledge and huge rents encourage investments in high-carbon directions.

Weak private incentives cannot be solely addressed by public R&D. Indeed, as highlighted in the recalled publication, it has historically failed to conceive market products because of the differences between the needs of public and private sectors (Grubb, 2004).

Public institution must act both by financing investments and by setting the full framework to accommodate innovations: that is what respectively technology-pushing and market-pulling climate policies aims to do, as described in section 2.1.2.

As a final note on the goal of efficiency, it is befitting to mention a possible drawback of efficiency for GHG emissions: the rebound effect. Indeed, providing users with technologies which lower energy demand per unit of production, can stimulate their usage. And this can potentially increase emissions. Therefore, in order for the technological change to result in a net reduction of emissions, the rebound effect must be controlled.

Rebound effect is a crucial factor for why environmental and sustainable innovation can fail in emissions reduction. When rebound effect is absent, a 1% increase in energy efficiency leads to a 1% decrease in energy demand. However, the literature suggests this effect to be 30%, on average

- that would reduce the previous marginal energy demand decrease to 0.7% -, with much higher estimates also reported. Despite of its salience, rebound effect is rarely considered in studies, possibly undermining the reported effect of innovation on climate (Vélez-Henao et al., 2019).

2.2.1 Drivers of Eco-Innovation And of Its Efficacy

When technological change is endogenously driven by economic forces, it is called Induced Technical Change. Hicks defined it the result of the change in the relative prices of the factors. And it is the opposite of the Autonomous Technical Change, which is exogenous to economic factors (Hicks, 1932).

The environmental or sustainable technological change fostered by policies is induced.

In addition to investigating which policies effectively induce technical change, researchers focused on the drivers that accelerate it. In their review of the literature on Eco-innovation, Matos et al. (2022) found it to be the main topic of research in this field: the number of published research on this subject exceeds research on policies or on performance.

Income and Economic Development Levels

The principal factor that literature links to the efficacy of environmental innovation is the level of economic development of a country.

This hypothesis originally gathers from the Kuznet Curve, firstly proposed by Kuznet in 1955, and which hypothesizes an inverted U-shaped relation between income inequality and economic growth: income inequality at first rises as the income level of the country increases; once a given threshold of income is reached, this relation is inverted, leading income inequality to be inversely proportional to the economic growth (Kuznets, 1955).

Then, Grossman and Krueger in 1991 adapted this idea to the relation between economic development and CO₂ emissions: in a first stage, productivity growth leads to higher levels of CO₂; but once sufficient levels of income per capita and equality are reached, people can meet their basic needs and crave more for quality than quantity, and their concerns for the environment are raised together (Grossman and Krueger, 1991). Of course, technical change is implicitly assumed in the process that leads to the final described result.

Although pollutants concentrations have been found to decrease as the income level of countries increases, empirical findings generally reject the Environmental Kuznet Curve, providing a high level of heterogeneity in the estimates and suggesting more complex relations. This finally intimates the presence of other factors possibly essential for this connection (Özokcu and Özdemir, 2017; Stern, 2017; Mensah et al., 2018; Sarkodie and Strezov, 2019).

In his empirical work, Chen Lee found that, excluding countries with high levels of CO₂ emissions, high-income levels are a determinant of the efficacy of technical change in highly innovative countries, also for similar neighboring countries (Chen and Lee, 2020). Mensah et al. (2018) found that innovation plays a key role for the mitigation of CO₂ emissions in most of the OECD countries,

although its impact strictly depends on the course of the innovating process and on the characteristics of the countries. Consistently with these results, Fernández et al. (2018) estimated a positive impact of spending on research and development in developed countries.

Earlier empirical research that explored the role of the state of economic development focused on highly developed economies. This result can be addressed to the fact that these countries were the first to implement actions against human-induced climate change, as described in section 2.1.1. But as concerns were raised and also the mobilization by developing country was solicited, the academic interest on this latter class of countries rose together. In fact, ecological technical change in emerging countries is one of the major topics of interest. The aim is to allow their economic development while keeping the consequential emissions growth rate at a sustainable level: Asia, currently the continent with the highest average real GDP growth rate, accounted for 63% of the total global GHG emissions in 2023, with China and India respectively contributing to 30% and almost 8% alone (IMF, 2024; EDGAR, 2024).

As García et al. (2014) points out, the status of emerging country constitutes by itself an obstacle to adopt competitive environmental strategies. In fact, economic incentives for technological change are hindered by: the fact that competitive advantage is based on low labor costs; the labor productivity is not fully exploited; deficiency of environmental and industrial policies; less awareness in the business induced climate impact and in the benefit of technical change in resources productivity. Chen Lee estimated that, among 96 countries from all over the world, in both middle- and low-income nations technological innovation did not contributed to reduce CO2 emission over the period between 1996 and 2018 (Chen and Lee, 2020). On the other hand, Afrifa et al. (2020) observed that in 29 emerging countries between 1990 and 2018 investments in innovation contributed to the reduction of climate change problems, with better results as the level of innovation and quality of governments increased.

Indeed, governmental indicators are also claimed as a determining factor to face climate change, with an increased impact in developed and high-innovative countries (Afrifa et al., 2020). This confirms what the theory revised in section 2.1.2 suggests about the need of the political intervention.

Location

Location is more important for environmental than for other kind of innovations.

Urbanization is claimed as detrimental for the mitigation of CO₂, as it is connected to increase in pollutants emissions. However, some empirical findings also suggests a possible inverted U-shaped relation between urbanization and CO₂ emissions, similar to what EKC describes (Lin and Zhu, 2019).

Moreover, industrial districts foster innovation since knowledge spillovers and externalities are concentrated in a circumscribed territory.

But, in fact, eco-innovation can be more likely in high-poverty regions, which are less dependent on the advantages linked to urbanization. Similarly, rurality is also found to be a beneficial factor,

as the closeness to nature reflects greater environmental awareness.

Finally regional proximity to research centers and university, which are sources of external knowledge, are an important factor for innovation, particularly for the environmental one (García et al., 2014).

Energy Consumption Structure

A coal-dominated energy consumption structure, as that of China, may delay the adoption of less polluting innovation.

As described in section 2.2, new energy industry and its innovation are highly capital intensive and risky. This makes prices of new, cleaner energy products less competitive than that of coal, possibly neglecting their benefits in the short term.

However, higher climate damages increase the cost of economic growth due to higher expenses for their removal, and are detrimental for the sustainable development of the country. As a result, reliance in more pollutant energy structure may actually promote cleaner energy sources and environmental transition in the long-term (Xu and Lin, 2018; Lin and Zhu, 2019).

Globalization

As described by Newell, the effect of market openness on environment in developing countries can be decomposed into three effects: the scale effect, that is the increased pollution due to the induced economic growth and the energy intensity rise; the composition effect, which is the reduction of human-induced climate change as the country become richer, as hypothesized by the Environmental Kuznet Curve; the technique effects, meaning the emission reduction due to the gain in efficiency as international trades expand the access to cleaner technologies. For a given level of economic growth, the net effect will therefore depend on the interaction between the positive technique effect and the negative scale effect, possibly resulting from the rebound effect described in section 2.2.

The author includes in the globalization effects on environment also the political cooperation. Indeed, late adopters can learn from prior actions' results and the benefits of the lower costs of adaptation to these regulations thanks to technological improvements.

Finally, globalization can also increase emissions due to carbon-leakage: high-carbon industries can more easily migrate to countries with no or less restrictive climate laws (Newell, 2009).

Nonetheless, in the yet cited empirical work of Chen and Lee (2020), globalization, both at the economic and at the political level, is found to increase the efficiency of environmental technical change to reduce carbon dioxide emissions, regardless of: the level of income, level of technology, and level of CO₂ emissions of the country.

R&D and Patenting

The concept of induced technical change is strictly related to R&D, as it is an investment motivated by the profitability of potential innovations (Newell, 2009). Thus, it is a necessary tool to face climate change.

General innovation is a key factor to achieve eco-innovation. Technical improvements enhance the functionality of new technologies and investments can be aimed at this goal: this makes R&D an endogenous driver of accelerated innovation and diffusion (Matos et al., 2022). As reported in Jiao et al. (2018), inter-industry R&D intensity can effectively diminish CO2 emissions. However, as reported in García et al. (2014), general R&D is less related to eco-innovation adoption than to other kind of innovation: eco-innovation is characterized by a higher complexity and novelty, and this can be disadvantageous at least in the short term.

Patents and the related system of laws are necessary to guarantee profits to innovators, and, indeed, its number has been frequently used to proxy innovation. On the other hand, some authors claim that the induced protection can in fact prevent the diffusion of innovations and, consequently, be actually an obstacle to the success of environmental technical change (Mensah et al., 2018).

The Long-Term

Since most of the discussed measures gain effectiveness through time, long-term can be qualified as a crucial latent factor.

Technical change is intrinsically a process that takes time, and this makes all of its drivers to be only effective in the medium-long period. And also the related snow-ball effect of knowledge spillovers described in section 2.1.2 needs time.

However, the decrease of the quality of knowledge stocks over time results in declining levels of induced related discoveries. Hence, time does not increase monotonically the effectiveness.

Long-term also encourages innovation. Indeed, firms investments in innovation and rates of adoption of inventions increase as uncertainty over economic returns and practical application decreases. And this occurs as costs reduce, systems adapt, and inventions are corroborated (Newell, 2009).

2.2.2 Theoretical Models

To assess the role of drivers of the anthropogenic environmental change, economists have developed models that integrate the impact of economic growth and of technological change on the ecosystem.

One of such approaches relies on the Environmental Kuznet Curve, yet discussed in section 2.2.1. This kind of models formalize the impact measure as a quadratic function of economic growth, in accordance with the hypothesized inverted U-shaped linkage between the two measures. Of course, other relevant controls are generally included.

With the rise of interest in exploring the impact of technology, a modified version of the EKC have been formalized through the Innovation Claudia Curve Theory: the resulting equation allows the existence of an inverted U-shaped curve even between innovation and the environmental impact, integrating a quadratic technology variable.

An increasing number of recent empirical research have tested and confirmed the validity of the ICC (Mensah et al., 2018; Khan et al., 2022; Alnafisah et al., 2024).

Another environmental model originally used only to account for the anthropogenic environmental change is the IPAT model. Its name reflects the scientifically asserted knowledge that the impact ("I") on nature stems from: population ("P"); affluence ("A"), which represents the per capita economic activity and, therefore, typically represented by GDP per capita; and technology ("T"), which express the impact per unit of economic activity. The equation that represents this model is:

$$I = P \cdot A \cdot T$$

Since IPAT was initially only used as an accounting model of the impact of each factor on the quantified measure of I - usually CO2 emissions -, T was only deduced by solving for it:

$$T = \frac{I}{P \cdot A}$$

But in this way T captures everything that is not included in the model, not just technology. And it also possibly captures term changes that should be more properly allocated to P or A. Moreover, the underlying relationship is definitional, not providing an adequate basis for the statistical testing of hypothesis.

In order to address these two problems, Dietz and Rosa proposed that technology should be assessed directly and, moreover, proposed the reformulation as a stochastic model, in such a way it can be used to test hypothesis. With this latter aim, in 1994 they formalized the STIRPAT (Stochastic Impacts by Regression on Population, Affluence and Technology) model:

$$I = aP^b \cdot A^c \cdot T^d \cdot e,$$

where I, P, A, T remain the same accounting variables as in IPAT; a, b, c, and d are parameters to be estimated; and e is the residual term. a is the constant that scales the model, while b,c, and d determine the net effect of the respective factor on I.

The key advantages of this stochastic version of the model are: that it allows to estimate T independently of the other three factors; allows the application of a rich set of conceptual and statistical tools; allows to estimate the effect of the driving forces on each other through simultaneous equation models; allows for complex variations of the model (Dietz and Rosa, 1994, 1997).

A crucial aspect is the appropriate treatment of technological change.

Following the literature review of Newell, technological change has often been treated as exogenous. Alternatively, it is sometimes represented as the change of the unobserved knowledge stock that depends on time and prices. As both the theory and the empirical evidence suggest, this stock is the product of both innovation and knowledge spillovers.

On the other hand, there is not a single structural theory on how this accumulation occurs.

Going on with the analysis of Newell, some theoretical models have focused on the price-induced technological change. This approach supposes that energy efficiency is inversely proportional to

the change in energy prices. Consistently with this, technical innovation can be endogenized by the change in the level of prices. From the hypothesized ways in which this occurs, different models have been drawn.

But since empirical evidence suggests that change in energy prices only partly explain the speed of efficiency improvements, this approach have generally been dismissed in favor of the following two.

Learning-induced technological change models innovation as an increasing function of either the cumulative output - following the concept of learning-by-doing -, or of the decrease in costs, as it should indirectly represent the increase in the use of more efficient technologies - following the concept of learning-by-using -.

However, using this method generally leads to a lower estimated costs of environmental transition. Indeed, learning-induced innovation implies that any use of efficient energy technologies lowers the cost of its usage in the future, with no additional expenditure needed. This may lead to excessively optimistic estimates that in the end can dangerously weaken efforts.

Finally, the most common procedure to endogenize the induced technical change is to use R&D expenditures. Indeed, the wider set of models has been drawn on it.

Then again, this method has some key issues to be taken into account. The former is that, as discussed in section 2.1.2, it is associated with spillovers, which are harder to be quantified and that could possibly lead to overestimate the impact of innovation expenditure.

Another is that encouraging investments on environmental R&D can drain R&D in other sectors, potentially undermining the positive effect on climate by reducing innovations (Newell, 2009).

Therefore, each of the discussed methods to proxy the knowledge stock has its own drawbacks which prevent an indisputable prevail of one over the others and calls for ad hoc modeling assumptions.

3 Theoretical Foundations of Meta-Regression on Innovation's Environmental Impact

3.1 Research Question and Its Relevance

The nexus between innovation and environment and its key role to meet climate goals was deeply discussed and supported by the literature review in the previous sections.

However, despite the increasing academic focus on this topic, literature so far failed to provide unequivocal and general conclusions: neither on the factual impact that innovation has on the reduction of human footprint, nor about that of any of the determinants on this nexus. This can likely be addressed to the relative novelty of the topic as a field of research, because of which we can expect much more to be discovered and proven up to this point. Additionally, the multidisciplinary and the complexity of the connection between innovation and emissions complicate the investigation of its single aspects, along with the generalization of the respective outcomes.

Nonetheless, the urgency of reducing pollution creates the need to clarify how to accelerate the effects of climate innovation. As a matter of fact, recurring themes in publications on eco-innovation are its performance, its drivers, its different varieties, and the specific contexts (García et al., 2014). Moreover, the rapid increase of theoretical discussions quickly spilled over into empirical analysis, which is one of the major types of research in the field of climate innovation (Matos et al., 2022).

However, most of the published empirical analyses focus on recurrent specific contexts. Many of these research focused only on developed or developing countries or, at most, on the differences between them. Others were centered in specific geographical areas or countries: an example of a frequent individually studied sample is China. A very few studies referred to a generalized global sample, instead (e.g.: Li and Wang (2017); Chen and Lei (2018); Chen and Lee (2020); Mamkhezri and Khezri (2024)).

The fragmentation of the empirical evidence is fostered beyond by the fact that many studies focus only on some of the drivers discussed in 2.2.1, possibly neglecting the effect of their coexistence.

This research represents a first attempt to gather and generalize the empirical evidence published thus far. In detail, the aim is to quantify the impact that innovating efforts have had on GHG emissions, and to infer what drives the variability of related estimates.

The primary goal is to evaluate whether the implemented environmental measures effectively stimulated the ability of innovation to reduce emissions. Additionally, this research allows to assess which, among the ones suggested by theory, have been the significant factors that led this causal relation to diverge. Coincidentally, it involves assessments of the suitability of some frequent methodological features used.

Of course, also these review cannot be fully generalized, since it only relates to the existing litera-

ture analyzed. Moreover, given the dynamism of the climate action, it is rational to expect most of these results to evolve together.

Nonetheless, it constitutes a primordial, necessary attempt to provide an extensive empirical knowledge about what has been proven until now.

The final merit of this study is given by the fact that, among the consulted sources, there are not examples of such extensive empirical publications on the causal impact of innovation on emissions. Additionally, the methodology used in this work has not been used to comprehensively explore the general features of this relationships, beyond specific contexts. Hence, besides providing important insights, this study aims at promoting a more generalized approach in this essential field of research.

3.2 The Meta-Analysis Approach

In the last years, economics research publications increased their growth speed (Matos et al., 2022). However, rather than an organized flow of consistent information, this only produced a huge amount of facts. As Stanley and Doucouliagos (2012) opine, the consequential noise and misinformation make it harder to acquire knowledge of economic reality, and to implement informed policy actions. Moreover, the chaotic and confusing amount of data published often present unexplained heterogeneity, which possibly makes it impossible to understand reality.

The answer to the growth of this "Tower of Babel" of facts consisted in the contemporary rise of publications summaries: this kind of studies have the goal of organizing knowledge, possibly explaining and/or revising it. More than purely narrative reviews, in economics has gathered momentum quantitative syntheses based on the same statistical tools used by econometrics: Meta-Regression analyses. The suitability of this kind of empirical summary is that it allows to filter out common biases and explain systematic heterogeneity. It finally provides public knowledge with clarity.

Figure 4: Meta-Analysis in economics over time.

Source: Stanley and Doucouliagos (2012)

A Meta-Analysis is a systematic statistical combination of reported results from individual and independent studies that are related by starting hypotheses and objects of estimates. It is essential for evidence-based practices in medicine and social sciences: it has more statistical power than the reviewed studies in the estimation of average effects and the detection of sources of divergence; in addition, it can guide future empirical studies by identifying literature gaps and best procedures (Normand, 1999; Stanley and Doucouliagos, 2012; Cooper et al., 2019).

However, because economic evidence is usually not based on controlled experiments as in sciences, quantitative reviews in economics require specific methods: they rely on Meta-Regression analysis (MRA). What characterizes this latter procedure is that it can also estimate and filter out the misspecification biases that unavoidably originate from the selection of the model specification. Indeed, since econometrics is typically observational, restriction of this additional source of heterogeneity is crucial to estimate valid average effects and the influence of determinants of deviation. Conventional econometrics is incapable of correcting for this effect.

Qualifying Meta-Analysis as a systematic method of review distinguishes it from conventional literature reviews. Specifically, although a literature review similarly aims at integrating related publications, it does not require the implementation of a defined practical methodology. As a result, following Cooper et al. (2019), this latter kind of analysis has a high risk of being fundamentally influenced by reviewers' point of view .

Meta-Analysis elevates its level of reliance by aiming at being objective and reproducible. This goal can only be achieved by the definition of a replicable course of action. The first comprehensive framework of a MRA for economic studies has been illustrated in the yet cited book *Meta-Regression Analysis in Economics and Business* by Stanley and Doucouliagos (2012). Given its relevance, the following analysis is largely based on this work.

The practical goal of MRA is to find an explicit econometric model of statistical power and tests for true effects, corrected for selection bias contamination (Stanley, 2008).

The advantage of Meta-Regression in doing so is that it essentially relies on the same tools and statistical methods that econometricians employ to produce empirical estimates: thus, the same producers of the primary information analyzed have no reasons to object the comprehensive inspection of their results. MRA results can at most suffer the same limitations and weaknesses.

Moreover, reliance on reported estimates offers an additional advantage to their reviewers: since the necessarily assumed validity of the divulged outputs implies their compliance to stated statistical properties, their collection is implicitly assumed to have well known distributional properties, without the need of any additional assumption. Thanks to this, any source of deviations from the ideal distribution can be exploited to get statistically valid conclusions: tracking this drivers and estimate their effect correspond with the mentioned practical goal of MRA. The only responsibility left to meta-analysts is to identify and correct important issues of the data collection (Stanley and Doucouliagos, 2012).

Selection bias is central in this discussion because it significantly influences the empirical evidence in economics. This is due to the fact that, for a given economic phenomenon, results reported are selected from a large set of estimated models which, in turn, has been originally selected from a potentially unlimited set of ideal models of relation. Similarly, Journals have editorial policies that guide the selection of studies to be published based on their results: since this latter mechanism is known by the researchers themselves, this ultimately foster their tendency to select models that lead to favourite results.¹ What worsens this situation is that there is no impartial way to know which model specification is correct.

In empirical economics this problem is so severe that Stanley (2008) claims that published conclusions are often just the result of an impartial selection, rather than evidences of the existence of real underlying circumstances. On the other hand, an unbiased understanding of scientific evidence is essential to understand social phenomena: the relevance of MRA for economics is given by its ability to cleanse knowledge of artificial influences (and to estimate the weight and direction of this tendencies).

Researchers and authors affect evidence record when choose to report only significant results. This finally causes larger and significant effects to be overrepresented in literature. This kind of reporting bias is called publication bias. According to Card and Krueger (1995) any of the agents involved in this selection process has the predisposition to prefer statistically significant estimates. Additionally, the two cited authors address this bias also to the inclination of both reviewers and researchers, on their own, to favor results consistent with previous prominent findings. However, this behavior must not be conceived as a bad intention. Rather, it naturally stems from estab-

¹The journal selection mechanism potentially influences the reporting of scientific evidence across all fields of research, not just economics. These selection policies can be shaped by preferences for specific scientific paradigms, leading published findings to align with and reinforce particular systems of belief.

lished shared consuetudes perceived as correct methods: this is what makes it unavoidable and ubiquitous in some research fields.

The problem is its distortion effect on collective estimates. Indeed, in presence of publication bias non statistically significant and/or adverse findings will be probably missing in the respective literature. Vice versa, conventional conclusions and the proportion of significant effects will dominate the literature composition, independently of the existence and the true direction of the underlying phenomenon. The distorted accumulation of findings ultimately affects summary effect-size averages and their confidence intervals.²

Finally, once publication bias has been filtered out and an adjusted average effect size has been estimated, MRA helps to explain excess heterogeneity. Indeed, estimates also differ because of many other factor affecting the research. Since left-unexplained heterogeneity can bias the final output, modeling this variation in its presence is important too. Hence, another strength point of Meta-Regression is to allow the investigation of potentially any thought dimension leading estimates to differ, and to quantify their influence.

In the end, this also offers the possibility to statistically test for features of the phenomenon of interest suggested by the respective literature.

It is now clear the importance of using this framework to objectively collect knowledge about the environmental impact of innovation. First of all, because it is a modern field of research with an increasing growth of speed. MRA can therefore be functional to clarify evidence and purify it from the informational noise.

Additionally, a method that accurately estimates the true impact of innovation on environment is imperative. On the one hand, to know how the global mobilization has factually enabled its environmental role; and, together with this, possibly to determine which of the characteristics suggested by theory has been determinant up to now.

On the other hand, it is essential to purify results from the eventual distorting effect of publication selection: certainly, there's the risk that the accordance on the capacity of technical progress to prevent climate change might lead to an excessively optimistic perception. The possible disclosure of this enthusiasm would foster the relevance of this review by suggesting a redress of the judgment and design of climate policies.

3.2.1 The Meta-Regression Analysis

Fixed- and Random-Effects Meta-Analysis Models

²Also reporting only results that are conceived as more rational contributes to the distortion effect of this fallacy of composition. Indeed, as discussed in Stanley and Doucouliagos (2012), even when all the researchers suppress results due to a justified perceived irrationality of the sign of their estimate, the average reported effect-size will be inflated with respect to the real parameter. This paradox reinforces the idea that even best motives and defensive way of reporting estimates can finally affect the overall knowledge of a social phenomenon.

The dependent variable in a Meta-Regression Analysis is an effect size: a parameter quantifying the intensity and the direction of the relationship between two entities. The final aim is to estimate its value by means of the related reported estimates, which constitute the data.

As in conventional econometrics, MRA provides more than just the quantification of the sample average. It involves explaining the deviations from that value. This is done through the original definition of a meta-analysis model, practically represented by a mathematical formula that interprets the ideal data generating process.

Depending on which of two alternative assumptions about the parameter of interest better fits the observed estimates, the meta-analysis model can be of one of two types. The suitable model is the Fixed-Effects whenever it is likely that all the k predictors $\hat{\theta}_k$ share the same true effect, θ , by which they deviate only because of their sampling error, ϵ_k . Based on this model, observed estimates follow a

$$\hat{\theta}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\theta, \sigma_k^2),$$

leading to the consequential functional representation:

$$\hat{\theta}_k = \theta + \epsilon_k, \text{ where } \epsilon_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_k^2).$$

The natural estimator of ϵ_k is the standard error of its associated estimate.

The founding hypothesis is that the predictors differ only due to the group of units observed in the study, but that all of the groups are sampled from the same population. All of the other studies' characteristics are assumed to be *fixed*, instead. Therefore, the true effect size estimate is to be generalized to the population of the studies from which the data are collected.

Alternatively, the assumption that better fits the collected estimates is that they differ because they have been randomly drawn from a universe of different populations: predictors can deviate because they estimate different populations' parameters. The deviation of predictors is attributable to the *random* variation of the characteristics of the ensemble to which they are related, not only because of sample variance.

In the so called Random-Effects model, observed estimates are then hypothesized to follow a

$$\hat{\theta}_k | \theta_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\theta_k, \sigma_k^2), \text{ where } \theta_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\theta, \tau^2),$$

from which

$$\hat{\theta}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\theta, \sigma_k^2 + \tau^2),$$

which ultimately results in the mathematical formulation of the model:

$$\hat{\theta}_k = \theta + \zeta_k + \epsilon_k, \text{ where } \zeta_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \tau^2) \text{ and } \epsilon_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_k^2).$$

τ represents the average variation of all the random characteristics of the underlying populations. A crucial assumption of this model is that ζ_k parameter is independent of k and, since it is random,

it is not predictable a priori.

RE model does not assume the existence of a unique true effect size. Rather it aims at estimating the mean of the distribution of true effect sizes of the universe of related existing studies (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Random-Effects model distribution of effect sizes.

Source: Harrer et al. (2021)

An important note on the representativeness of the pooled effect is that it is only informative about the population (Fixed-Effects Model) or about the universe of populations (Random-Effects Model) of the collected studies: that is, it cannot be generalized to estimates not represented in the available data.

The generalization of conclusion is limited even assuming an extensive collection of data, since, as discussed in section 3.2, it is expected that some results are missing in literature and, still, that they will grow with new findings and change as the phenomenon itself evolves.

Hence, Meta-Analysis must be conceived only as representative of the existing knowledge of the topic of interest.

One summary measure of the true effect size is the weighted average of the estimates:

$$\bar{\theta} = \frac{\sum_k w_k \hat{\theta}_k}{\sum_k w_k},$$

where $\bar{\theta}$ is the average effect size, and w_k is the “weight” assigned to the estimate k . Standard error of $\bar{\theta}$ can be computed as $\sqrt{\sum_k \frac{1}{w_k}}$ (Stanley and Doucouliagos, 2012). Of course, effect sizes

$\hat{\theta}_k$ must be comparable: this requisite will be furtherly discussed in sections 3.2.3 and 4, describing the ways to address the dissimilarity of collected data.

The optimal weights to use are the inverse of the estimates' variances (Hedges and Olkin, 2014). Since the inverse of the variance is an indicator of the precision, this mechanism allows to give more importance to more accurate predictions, and vice versa. If the appropriate model is the Fixed-Effects, then $w_k = \frac{1}{SE_k^2}$, where SE_k is the standard error of $\hat{\theta}_k$ and, so, the natural estimator of its standard deviation. If, in contrast, a Random-Effects approach must be preferred, $w_k = \frac{1}{SE_k^2 + \hat{\tau}^2}$, where $\hat{\tau}$ is an estimator of the average random between-population variability, since this additional source of variation must be considered.

This summary measure is ideally a good estimator of the common parameter underlying the studies revised. Indeed, it is the most common approach used in Meta-Analyses. But in economics, where Meta-Regression is suitable, this measure is likely to be biased. This is because between-study variation is routinely found in economics research and, because of that, REE (Random-Effects Estimation) should always be preferred over FEE (Fixed-Effects Estimation). But, although in presence of selection bias any (weighted or unweighted) average estimate is distorted, REE weighted average will be even more biased than its alternative: its inferiority is due to the fact that it coincides with the average of the FEE and the simple mean, which has the largest publication bias (Stanley and Doucouliagos, 2012, 2014).

That essentially explains the cruciality of MRA in estimating the average true effect whenever selection bias can be suspected.

Publication Bias MRA

As previously described, selection bias arises when researchers and publisher choose estimates according to their statistical significance. Still, the resulting truncation of the pool of reported estimates is incidental, since effects are not directly selected: rather, agents choose among their corresponding z- or t-values, when these measures are above the preferred threshold. This framing makes Heckman's sample selection correction the ideal way to address the problem and estimate the corrected effect size. However, since it is not possible to know the probability that an estimate is not reported, this approach is not feasible (Stanley and Doucouliagos, 2014).

Nonetheless, the recognition of the truncated distribution of reported effects inspired methods to test for the presence of publication bias and, simultaneously, to estimate the corrected genuine effect. The underlying intuition is that: when the underlying phenomenon is small or non-existent, but the focus is on significance, the lower is the precision of estimates the more the researcher needs to experiment with more data subsets, specifications, and methods to achieve statistical significance. In fact, smaller studies are the most affected by publication bias: large studies, which inherently involve more resources and time, are likely to get published regardless of their level of significance; on the other hand, estimates in smaller samples, with correspondingly higher standard errors, will be more likely published when their estimates are highly significant: their researchers will be more inclined to select the methods that leads to estimates much higher than their standard errors (Harrer et al., 2021).

This finally leads publication selection to be positively correlated with the standard deviations of

estimates. Given this dependence and the conditional expectation of a truncated normal distribution, the expected observed effect is:³

$$E(\hat{\theta}_k | \frac{\hat{\theta}_k}{\sigma_k} > a) = \theta + \sigma_k \cdot \lambda(a - \frac{\theta}{\sigma_k}),$$

where: a is the standard normal distribution's critical value corresponding to the significance level desired by the publisher; $\sigma_k \cdot \lambda(a - \frac{\theta}{\sigma_k})$ represents the selection bias; and $\lambda()$ is the inverse Mills' ratio function. By replacing for sample estimates, under selection bias:

$$\hat{\theta}_k = \theta + SE_k \cdot \lambda(a - \frac{\theta}{\sigma_k}) + \epsilon_k,$$

with SE_k representing the standard error.

What is left for the estimation of the genuine effect θ , is a way to define the Mills' ratio. As said, Heckman two-step procedure is not feasible. Moreover, it is a complex function of σ_k (taking a and θ as given). Therefore, some simplifying assumptions has been proposed to tackle this issue. If the Mills' ratio is assumed to be fixed, the equation coincides with the PET (Precision-Effect Test)-FAT (Funnel-Asymmetry Test) meta regression model proposed by Egger et al. (1997):^{4,5}:

$$\hat{\theta}_k = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SE_k + \epsilon_k. \tag{1}$$

In this equation, β_1 estimates the relation between standard deviation and selection: the higher it is, the higher is the publication bias in the revised literature. And, more than just assessing the intensity and direction of this bias, it controls for its distorting effect: as a consequence, the intercept β_0 estimates the true underlying effect θ , that would be measured at the limit case of $SE_k = 0$.

Furthermore, controlling for the standard errors coincidentally corrects also for small sample biases: indeed, since smaller samples have higher variances, this bias' mechanism coincides with the dynamic of publication bias. In fact, the two biases cannot be distinguished one from the other (Stanley and Doucouliagos, 2012).

Eventually, as it will be accurately discussed in section 3.2.3, the implausible assumption that

³For simplicity, has been assumed a Fixed-Effects data-generating process. The formulas below can be easily extended to the Random-Effects case through the integration of the parameter ζ_k

⁴Egger et al. (1997) work actually focus only on the FAT, to provide a statistical measure and test for the asymmetry of the Funnel graph: this is a scatter plot of estimates against their precision. Under the implicitly assumed validity of the retrieved estimates and their comparability, Funnel graph should be normally distributed around the true value. Hence, its asymmetry can be addressed as an evidence of either a truncated distribution due to selection bias, and/or small sample bias.

⁵For the sake of clarity and coherence in the discussion, the properties of these two tests will be discussed in section 3.2.3

Mills' ratio is constant leads β_0 in equation 1 to be biased when there is publication selection. A feasible alternative is to assume Mills' ratio to be a quadratic function of σ_k . However, since the bottom of the parabola must occur when $SE_k = 0$ (that is, when the true effect is accurately estimated), the linear term coefficient is omitted: $\beta_1=0$. This finally leads to the *precision-effect estimate with standard error* (PEESE) MRA model proposed by Stanley et al. (2007):

$$\hat{\theta}_k = \beta_0 + \beta_2 SE_k^2 + \epsilon_k, \quad (2)$$

where the selection bias intensity is represented by β_2 . In fact, when an underlying effect truly exists, the β_0 in PEESE is a better estimator of the genuine effect. This is because the parabola better fits the degree of effort exerted by researchers to get significant results as precision lowers: as the standard error gets larger, the magnitude of the effect must be larger to get significant estimates (Figure 6).

Nonetheless, when there is no effect beyond selection bias equation 1 is correctly specified, because the expected reported estimate is a multiple of its standard deviation. Given that test for $\beta_0=0$ provides a valid statistic test for the absence of a genuine effect, whenever its absence is rejected PEESE provides better estimations of genuine effect.

Figure 6: Publication bias. The slope of the relation between estimates and their SE equals the inverse Mills' ratio at the critical value a .

In the image are depicted the two kinds of relation discussed. When there is no publication bias, $E(\text{effect}|\text{No PB})$ is constant and, consequently, it is well represented by a linear function of SE: the estimates will randomly vary around the true effect (as it is shown for low values of SE in the graph). On the other hand, when reported estimates are influenced by publication bias, $E(\text{effect}|\text{PB})$ is better represented by a quadratic function of SE: as the degree of precision of estimates decreases, estimates' magnitude must be many times higher than their standard error in order to achieve significance. Anyway, most precise estimates still randomly vary around the true effect, as they

are less influenced by selection bias

Source: Stanley and Doucouliagos (2012)

Multivariate MRA

It is common for economics research to contain excess of systematic heterogeneity above publication bias. Moreover, not addressing this variation can potentially bias estimations of the genuine effect. The additional strength of meta-regression models for publication bias is that they easily allow to address and explain excess of variability.

Primary studies' estimates ordinarily deviate due to: characteristics of the sample used, the choice of controls included by the researchers, econometric models, and estimation methods. In general, MRA allows to estimate and test the influence of the determinants of the relationship of interest, either suggested by theory and/or suspected by the reviewer herself.

In fact, both PET-FAT and PEESE models discussed try on their own to model the variation of estimates around the true effect. And, since publication bias term serves as an explanatory of the relative deviations, they are regression functions: Meta-Regression models try to predict

studies' effect sizes given their expected deviation from the average due to specific characteristics.

The estimates can deviate both because of the characteristics of the population to which they (*randomly*) belong, and due to specific (*fixed*) characteristics they possess. Each type (random or fixed) of deviating factors differently shapes the regression model design: if the predictor value is aleatory, unexplainably drawn from an unknown and potentially unlimited collection, it is modeled through a *Multi-Level* model (discussed below); if, on the other hand, a given quality is categorical (can only take one of a limited and fixed number of values) or simply deterministic, then it can be modeled through a *Multi-Variate* model.

The two kind of predictors address different statistical features of data, which often coexists in a MRA data sample: because of this, multivariate and multilevel models are generally merged in a *Mixed-Effects* model (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Mixed-Effects Model. Deviation effect of each of the two types of explanatory on the reported estimate.

Above, it is depicted the effect that fixed-effects have on $\hat{\theta}$. Assuming one sub-group distinction between A and B, each of the two groups of studies will have its own distinct average effect: $\hat{\theta}_A$ and $\hat{\theta}_B$, with their respective distribution. Below is represented the (unique) random level effect: inside each the two sub-groups A and B, any aleatory value of the random study's characteristic, embodied in the random level, leads to a own specific distribution from which relative reported estimate are drawn. Of course, several random levels and sub-groups generally affects estimate simultaneously.

Source: Harrer et al. (2021)

The multivariate version of PET-FAT-MRA is:⁶

$$\hat{\theta}_k = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_p Z_{pk} + \beta_1 SE_k + \sum \delta_j Q_{jk} SE_k + \epsilon_k. \quad (3)$$

This results from the addition of two terms to equation 1: \mathbf{Z}_k represents the vector of the P fixed-effects characteristics of the estimate k that are suspected to influence the genuine effect, while its respective vector of coefficients β_p quantify their deviating effect from β_0 ; similarly, \mathbf{Q}_k is the vector of the J fixed-effects characteristics (generally related to the “quality” of the respective study) that might affect the researchers’ tendency to report an estimate, while δ_j is the respective change on the Mills’ ratio slope (β_1). The two sets of variables Z and Q can overlap, whenever the respective features are suspected to influence both the true effect value and selection bias.

This model does not assume a unique true effect and publication bias. Rather, one effect for each mixture of fixed characteristics: there are several true effects represented by $\beta_0 + \sum \beta_p Z_{pk}$, and different tendencies toward significance level, represented by $\beta_1 SE_k + \sum \delta_j SE_k Q_{jk}$.

The multivariate version of PEESE can be obtained with the same transformation of equation 2:

$$\hat{\theta}_k = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_p Z_{pk} + \beta_2 SE_k^2 + \sum \delta_j Q_{jk} SE_k^2 + \epsilon_k. \quad (4)$$

Its interpretation follows the description of equation 3.

Moderators (fixed-effects variables) are frequently categorical variables, since they generally fit well the representation of finite groups of characteristics.

However, when a deterministic attribute is naturally represented by a continuous variable, and it is a suspected driver of a *fixed* proportional deviation on the true effect, it can also be used as a predictor of the deviation. Examples of this kind of variables are the year of observation, which may represents underlying structural changes; or journal quality measures, which can capture effects on the publication bias. In fact, this characteristics are not random, since they are the consequence of deterministic known processes (passing of time; appropriateness of the study and status of the respective journal).

Data Dependence And The Mixed-Effects Model

Another influencing factor of the pooled effect size’s predictor is the dependence of the sampled estimates. Statistical independence is one of the core assumptions of MRA, and not addressing it affects the efficiency of MRA estimates. In details, eventually unaccounted between-estimates dependence artificially reduces heterogeneity and, thus, finally inflates the significance of true effects estimates.

⁶To be coherent with the presentation of equation 1, this is the Fixed-Effects version of the multivariate model. Similarly as it as been noted above, the Random-Effects influence can be easily modeled by the integration of the random-variation parameter ζ_k . The simultaneous presence of this latter parameter, defines the Mixed-Effects version of the model.

Data dependence arises when several collected estimates are related by an identical or partially overlapping group of units used, and/or by same authors. As a consequence, dependence is unavoidable whenever multiple effects are reported from the same primary study.

However, since the abundance of estimates is essential for the statistical validity of their aggregates, multiple reporting from the same study can be helpful. Coding of such information requires (unbalanced) panel datasets to address for the potential unobservable within-study dependence steering from: data sources, the quality of the study, and the researchers' ideology.

When data are coded in a multidimensional structure, the previously discussed MRA models assume their unbalanced-panel version: PET-FAT selection model's equation 1 becomes

$$\hat{\theta}_{ik} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SE_{ik} + v_k + \epsilon_{ik}, \quad \text{for } i=1, \dots, m_k, \quad k=1, \dots, K, \quad (5)$$

where m_k is the number of estimates in study k , while K is the number of different studies coded, instead. The unbalanced-panel version of PEESE can be easily obtained by the coherent redefinition of equation 2.

The characterizing element of this equation is v_k , which represents the unobserved study effect. This term can be assumed to be either random or fixed, according to its relationship with the included covariates: if the study effects are assumed to be *random* and, consequently, independent of SE and other eventually included variables, the model is the *Random-Effects Multilevel MRA Model* (REML); if, on the opposite, v_k can be correlated with the included observed factors, the model is the *Fixed-Effects Multilevel MRA Model* (FEML). Hence, the only distinction between these two models concerns their assumption about the unobserved study effect.

FEML is the suited model for multivariate specifications whenever there is publication bias. Indeed, in this case, unobserved study effects necessarily include the respective latent level of effort exerted to find statistical significance and, therefore, v_k is *fixed*: estimates are partly the result of the unobservable process of model selection aimed at statistical significance which, in turn, depends on standard errors. This condition finally makes REML often inappropriate in economics MRA. However, the founding hypothesis of dependence can be tested through the typical tests used in econometrics, as it will be discussed in section 3.2.3.

It is not a coincidence that to distinguish the two latter models discussed are used almost the same name previously used to distinguish the data generating process models: both the Random- and Fixed-Effects Meta-Analysis models, formalized at start, coincide with two special cases of a 2-Levels Random-Effects model: the first level is where estimates deviates due to the sampling error ϵ ; the higher level is where the between-population random variability ζ lays. What distinguish the panel interpretation is that the populations are defined as the studies: v_k is the between-*study* variability, which is random, in fact (Figure 8). Nonetheless, explanation of the source of random-variability crucially addresses dependence by defining its structure, as explained.

Additionally assuming no between-study variability constrains $v_k = \zeta_k = 0$, and it collapses to the Fixed-Effects model.

Nota bene: the Fixed-Effects MRA model is not nested in the Fixed-Effects *Multilevel* MRA

model. In the latter model, *Fixed-Effects* refers to the allowed dependence of the study effect with observed predictors, and used to distinguish it from the case where it is independent (random), instead. In fact, the common suitable approach in economics is to model a Random-Effects data generating process (different populations, usually meaning studies) through a FEML, because of publication bias.

Figure 8: 2-Levels Random-Effects model structure

Source: Harrer et al. (2021)

These models are called multilevel since can separately address several random sources (levels) of data dependence. In particular, multiple levels are suitable when estimates have a *nested-clusters* structure: within each group, units can be additionally partitioned. Each cluster must represent an unobserved characteristics affecting effect-sizes. The ordering of the levels must respect the rational hierarchical structure, meaning that pooled effects at any level depend because they possess the same attribute at the higher level (Figure 9).

One factor is addressed as a level when its attributes are randomly assigned to units. This is the case whenever the set of its elements is not exhaustive and equally likely a priori. Vice versa, if the variable is fixed it should be modeled as a moderator (e.g.: if the data sample do not covers all of the geographical regions of the world, but only a *random* selection of them, such quality must be framed as a level rather than as a fixed effect (Harrer et al., 2021)).

Figure 9: 3-Levels Random-Effects model structure

Source: Harrer et al. (2021)

Finally, it is possible to simultaneously address the variability due to random unobserved sources and that due to fixed characteristics. As said, this must be done by estimating a Mixed-Effects model, in which between-population variance ζ_k is accounted together with the effect of observed non-random characteristics (recall Figure 7).

Moreover, if data have a nested-errors structure, the multilevel dependence must be accounted to consistently estimate deviations of the true effect due to moderators: this can be performed by setting a Multilevel Mixed-Effects Model. An example of a 3-level Mixed-Effects Model version of PET-FAT is:

$$\hat{\theta}_{ikp} = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_p Z_{piky} + \beta_1 SE_{iky} + \sum \delta_j Q_{jk_y} SE_{iky} + v_{ky} + v_y + \epsilon_{iky}, \quad (6)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, m_k, \quad k = 1, \dots, K_y, \quad y = 1, \dots, Y.$

where the subindex y has been added to represent the highest (third) level clustering of observations (e.g.: study k is nested into geographical region y). Similarly as before, v_{ky} is the unobserved random effect of being in the group ky ; v_y the one due to cluster y .

In equation 6 it is implicitly assumed that random-variation of estimates is imputable to random intercepts: cluster ky 's intercept is $\beta_0 + v_{ky} + v_y$; y 's intercept $\beta_0 + v_y$.

However, the model can ultimately be extended to include also random deviations of slopes. In this case, the added founding assumption is that, even within each study, it is possible to have different populations' effect sizes. To prevent overloading on the presentation, in this example the

additional random effect on slopes is assumed to depend only on level y :

$$\hat{\theta}_{ikp} = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_p Z_{piky} + \sum v_{py} Z_{piky} + \beta_1 SE_{iky} + v_{1y} SE_{iky} + \sum \delta_j Q_{jky} SE_{iky} + \sum v_{jy} Q_{jky} SE_{iky} + v_{0ky} + v_{0y} + \epsilon_{iky}, \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, m_k, \quad k = 1, \dots, K_y, \quad y = 1, \dots, Y. \quad (7)$$

For the sake of clarity, the number in the subindex of the random components v_s is assigned consistently with the slope that it affects.

Equation 7 presents the structure of the most complete MRA model.

3.2.2 Empirical Research Process

The statistical procedure of an MRA must be designed according to the nature of the literature reviewed.

The empirical research process of this analysis was fundamentally guided by the work of Feld and Heckemeyer (2011). Their analysis has the merit of mapping out how to sensibly choose the suitable methods according to the properties of the data collected.

The focus of this section is on how the appropriate final meta-analysis model is chosen from the set delineated in section 3.2.1. This involves a preliminary phase of sequential tests to determine which statistical properties need to be addressed. The ultimate purpose is to support the validity of the final results: only the results from the appropriate model will finally form the basis of conclusions.

A description of the tests used is provided in the following section 3.2.3. The central point of this part is the applicability of models.

Figure 10: Meta-analytical instruments set and the estimation strategy map

Source: Feld and Heckemeyer (2011)

Figure 10 outlines the step-by-step procedure followed in the MRA of Feld and Heckemeyer (2011). It starts with a meta-analysis of all the effect sizes collected. When the Fixed-Effects weighted average has been computed, it is possible to assess if there is an excess of heterogeneity. Heterogeneity is considered to be in excess when estimates deviate from their mean more than it can be imputed to their sampling errors' variation only; that practically means: when even the most precise predictors' value are significantly different one from another. The evidence of this kind of variability suggests that the estimates may belong to different populations and, therefore, that the suitable model is the Random-Effects.

Additionally, the eventual excess of variability must be explained. Given the centrality of MRA in doing this, a statistically proven high degree of deviation provides the foundation of its suitability. Otherwise, estimates' average provides a good predictor of the true effect and meta-regression analysis coincides with the *FEE* weighted average.

If the MRA approach is applicable, the multivariate meta-regression model of interest can be estimated.

For what concerns estimation, as said, any conventional estimation method used in econometrics can be potentially used. Anyway, Stanley and Doucouliagos (2012) strongly suggest least squares over more complex alternatives, as it results to be more resilient to unexpected issues: as a matter

of facts, it is the conventional estimation method used in MRA.

In economics the fundamental equation is the publication bias MRA equation, for the reasons discussed above. Thus, the empirical research starts with the estimation of equation 1 through POLS: neither adding other covariates, nor accounting for the eventual panel data structure of the dataset. The simplistic approach is justified by the prevailing of testing over empirical conclusions in this starting phase.

Nonetheless, the error dependence of estimates sampled from the same studies forces to use cluster-robust (by study) standard errors. This avoids potential overconfidence of estimates due to the artificial homogeneity of same study's estimates. Successive steps can then eventually determine if a multilevel approach is additionally required.

One crucial aspect concerning MRA estimation is that of heteroskedasticity. Indeed, the variance of each study effect estimate typically widely differs because of different sample sizes, data sets, and control variables used, causing this problem to be inherent and severe in MRA. Because of that, WLS is the regularly employed starting method. Furthermore, to ensure a conservative approach, heteroskedasticity-robust standard errors are employed.

Then again, the unchallenged validity of reported estimated poses one more advantage: the respective reported variance can be directly used to obtain consistent, asymptotically efficient, and asymptotically normal estimates through Feasible GLS, without the need of ulterior (consistent) estimations. This result is practically obtained by estimating through OLS equation 1 weighted by the observed variances SE_i^2 . Consequently, in practice, the (Fixed-Effects model) equation of interest becomes:

$$\frac{\hat{\theta}_i}{SE_i^2} = \beta_0 \frac{1}{SE_i^2} + \beta_1 \frac{1}{SE_i} + \frac{\epsilon_i}{SE_i^2}. \quad (8)$$

At this point, once again, it must be checked if the estimates' residuals still present excess heterogeneity. If this is the case, Random-Effects model is appropriate and, thus, FGLS must additionally account for the variance of the true effect sizes.

With the underlying feasible assumption that each study represents a unique population, several methods have been proposed to estimate the deviation of the parameter τ , and to ultimately enable its integration in the MRA model. Each of these methods suitability depends on: the number of studies collected, as well as the number of units included in each of them, and the magnitude of their true between-variance. The most popular estimator is the *Restricted Maximum Likelihood Estimator* (REML), plausibly for its superiority with continuous outcomes. Moreover, it is less biased in small samples than its precursor analogous *Maximum Likelihood* method (Veroniki et al., 2016). In addition to this, to accommodate for the uncertainty of $\hat{\tau}$, the Knapp-Hartung adjustment to the standard error of the estimated effect size is appropriate: using this variance estimator reduces the risk of anti-conservative confidence intervals (Knapp and Hartung, 2003).

Once $\hat{\tau}$ has been estimated, it can be inserted in the Random-Effects PET-FAT-WLS:

$$\frac{\hat{\theta}_i}{SE_i^2 + \hat{\tau}^2} = \beta_0 \frac{1}{SE_i^2 + \hat{\tau}^2} + \beta_1 \frac{1}{SE_i + \hat{\tau}^2} + \frac{\epsilon_i}{SE_i^2 + \hat{\tau}^2}. \quad (9)$$

Note that the weighting scheme of both equations 8 and 9 coincidentally implies that more precise estimates carry greater weight in the overall estimation, as seen for the weighted average. This property makes the use of this type of weights opportune, beyond that functional.

The following step is to check for the potential estimates' dependence due to study-specific effect: its evidence endorses the appropriateness of a Multilevel-Level approach.

Due to the preliminary nature of this phase, the focus is on a simple 2-Level model of the PET-FAT, addressing the unobserved primary research effect on estimates. The investigation of the potential influence of additional random sources of deviation is reserved to following steps.

The choice between a Random-Effects and a Fixed-Effects Multilevel design lies in the endogeneity of the cluster specific random component. With this aim, at first the estimation of the Random-Intercept model in equation 5 is compared with its expanded Random-Intercept-and-Slopes version, specified as:

$$\hat{\theta}_{ik} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SE_{ik} + \hat{v}_{1k} SE_{ik} + \hat{v}_k + \epsilon_{ik}, \quad (10)$$

where \hat{v}_{1k} is the estimated study k ' specific random variation of publication bias. The Random-Intercept estimation was preferred if it is nested within its alternative, since it evokes the irrelevance of slopes variation: stated differently, if the addition of \hat{v}_{1k} does not significantly improves the fit, it is not an essential explanatory.

Finally, a Fixed-Effects 2-Level Model is estimated through the Fixed-Effects cluster econometric method. Reliance on this latter approach depends on the endogeneity of the study-specific parameter.

The sequential scheme of estimations and tests described above is eventually performed in two following rounds.

The second round applies the same course of action to the PEESE model, starting from equation 2. However, as it will be explained in section 3.2.3, this becomes necessary only if the results of the appropriate specification of the PET-FAT evidences the significance of the genuine effect. Indeed, since in this circumstance the quadratic specification provides a more reliable estimator of β_0 , the output of the final PEESE model estimation corroborates its significance.

Finally, the sequence is repeated to address the left-unexplained heterogeneity of the simplistic version of PET-FAT. Indeed, the explanation of variability is crucial for the consistency of results. Then, in this ultimate phase, explanatories are added to the equation through multivariate and multilevel estimations, and the relative outputs tested following the scheme designed above.

However, the addition of covariates to the model implicates some additional, specific techniques in the designed procedure scheme. For what concerns eventual added levels, aiming at accounting the ulterior dependence steering from other random sources, their significance must be tested. It

implies that more complex specifications must be preferred only if they significantly improve the fit. Otherwise a nested equation model must be preferred, supported by the irrelevance of the additional explanatory parameter.

As regards of fixed-effects variables, instead, any explanatory is in principle allowed to be moderators of both the effect (that is: to be in the Z set of variables presented in equation 3) and the selection bias (in the Q set). However, in Meta-Analyses data sets are constructed by the analysts themselves and, thus, there is not any constraint on the number of variables included based on data availability, as it is in conventional econometrics. This freedom exposes estimation to overfitting and multi-collinearity, of which risk increases the more variables are included in the model.

In order to limit this threatening freedom in model specification, some guidelines and defined objective methods have been proposed: first of all, predictors to be included must be chosen at start, according to predefined inquiries lead by literature review; then, the number of included covariates (and interactions) must be objectively reduced to the minimal set that provides the best fit. To avoid an unfeasible experimentation of each possible combination, the most common practical method for the specification of the model is the *General-to-Specific* approach (Stanley and Doucouliagos, 2012, 2014). This implies the starting forced entry of all the predictors to be investigated, simultaneously: this constitutes the *General Model*. This full model is then tested following the usual preliminary investigation, and the resulting suitable type of model is chosen accordingly. At this point, variables are removed, one at a time, by backward induction based on which is the least significant predictor at that stage of removal: at start the model is estimated with all the variables together and, then, the covariate with the resulting highest p-value is removed from the following estimation; the iterative procedure stops when all the remaining predictors' marginal effects are significant.

3.2.3 Diagnostic Tests

As stated at the beginning of section 3.2.2, the determinants of the MRA research process and, thus, of the consistency of its results lay in the characteristics of the dataset. This section discusses the set of tests used to uncover such information and that consistently guided the direction followed at each node of the procedure outlined in the previous section. The discussion follows the sequence of steps, presenting the tests in the order in which they were performed in the empirical research.

One desirable feature of MRA is that it weights estimates proportionally to their precision. However, the usefulness is implied by the founding assumption that all the estimates included measure a comparable parameter, whose value is the central aim of the analysis. Therefore, data on phenomenon that differ from those of interest must be removed from the analysis. And it is in fact relevant their remotion, as they taint results by introducing heterogeneity that cannot be explained by control variables.

The less accurate an estimation is, the more its value can deviate from its true value and, conse-

quently, the harder it is to qualify its parameter. When *outlier* estimates have low precision, it is difficult to explain their respective large magnitude. Nonetheless, since its precision is low, its influence on the MRA pooled estimates is weak and, so, can be retained with limited damage.

On the other hand, *influentials* are estimates that greatly affect the pooled effect due to their high precision. The worst scenario occurs when their confidence interval does not overlap the average of the other estimates. But even when their magnitude is not particularly high or low, their predominant leverage power masks information carried by the remaining sample. Because of that, influential data must be removed from the research (Stanley and Doucouliagos, 2012).

After an initial check and correction of eventual coding errors, an objective technique of remotion of conflicting data is required. Among the several techniques to statistically assess the damaging influence of observations on the pooled estimate, this analysis used the DFBETA statistic to determine the degree with which the precision of a given estimate affects the computation of the genuine effect. This measure is appropriate because it allows to measure for each unit the leverage power of specific characteristics on the corresponding sample average coefficient. Since the representative variable of influence is the precision of the estimate, DFBETA served to quantify the distance between the average effect computed with and without an observation caused by its $\frac{1}{SE_i}$. It practically involved the computation of this statistic for the coefficient of precision in the OLS regression of t-statistics on $\frac{1}{SE_i}$: this coincides with the WLS estimation of the PET-FAT model's equation 1, weighted by observed standard errors:

$$\frac{\hat{\theta}_i}{SE_i} = (\beta_0 + \beta_1 SE_i + \epsilon_i) \frac{1}{SE_i} \iff t_i = \beta_0 \frac{1}{SE_i} + \beta_1 + \epsilon_i,$$

where β_0 remains the pooled estimated effect, while its respective regressor quantifies precision. Then, observations with a $|DFBETA|$ on precision greater than one have been removed from the following investigation: these data are inferred as influentials because their inclusion would cause a shift on the pooled estimate greater than one standard deviation from the genuine effect computed on the leftover estimates. The threshold value of 1 was preferred to lower cutoffs for the sake of conservativeness.

Despite of the assumed comparability of parameters, it still possible for them to diverge. The same phenomenon can exhibit varying parameters due to differences in measurement scales, treatment characteristics, and population attributes. This implicates heterogeneity of their predictors. Thus, evidence of excess of heterogeneity guides the choice between a Fixed- and a Random-Effects model, and, then, the eventual need to model left-unexplained systematic deviations by means of observable features.

Statistical heterogeneity is the measurable extent of the spread and precision of included data (Harrer et al., 2021). One measure of statistical between-study heterogeneity is the Cochran's Q statistic, which measure the extent of variation not attributable to sampling errors:

$$Q = \sum_{i=1}^I w_i (\hat{\theta}_i - \bar{\theta})^2, \text{ where } \bar{\theta} = \frac{\sum_i w_i \hat{\theta}_i}{\sum_i w_i},$$

and where weights w_i can be either $\frac{1}{SE_i^2}$ or $\frac{1}{SE_i^2 + \tau^2}$, according to the assumed data-generating process. This statistic is asymptotically distributed as χ_{I-1}^2 under the null hypothesis that the I included predictors share a common mean or, equivalently, that Q is 0. As a consequence, if the Cochran's Q is greater than the $100(1-\alpha)$ percentile of the χ_{I-1}^2 distribution, H_0 can be rejected since it is likely, at the $\alpha\%$ level, that at least one θ_i is different from the others and, thus, that it comes from a different population. In conclusion, rejecting Cochran's Q -test provides supports the suitability of Random-Effects model over its alternative and/or the presence of characteristic sub-groups: the latter circumstance is addressed through a multivariate approach. If the estimates are homogeneous, instead, there is less variation to be explained and, at the limit of complete homogeneity, any result would converge to the Fixed-Effects weighted average.

Although this test has low power, systematic excess of heterogeneity is almost always found in economics literature: Cooper et al. (2019) affirm that, in fact, Q -statistic is generally rejected when fitting univariate fixed-effects models and that it must be always assumed in economics MRA.

At this point, the primary interest lays in whether the remaining estimates evidence the existence of an underlying related genuine effect or not. Since, as explained, reported estimates depend on their selection, tests for the presence of an underlying phenomenon must take into account their publication bias. In fact, this aim coincides with the founding goal of PET-FAT and PEESE models that, simultaneously, allow the measurement of the true effect.

The "FAT" part of the former model relates to the coefficient β_1 of equation 1, which provides a statistic of the asymmetry of the distribution of collected estimates. Indeed, under the null hypothesis of data validity, estimates are asymptotically normally distributed. As said, MRA exploits causes of the deviation from their ideal distribution to draw conclusions about data. One required condition for estimations to be i.i.d. is the comparability of the scales of measurement of the dependent and the main independent variables. However, this condition is easily and necessarily addressed through the choice of which primary studies to include, eventual transformations of their data, and the codification of characteristics. Considering that MRA must use comparable predictors, the remaining causes of discrepancy of their distribution from a symmetric normal are differences in the model specifications and small sample bias. Given that both cause the dependence of reported magnitudes on deviations, the significance, the value, and the sign of the partial correlation between estimates and their standard errors respectively provides evidences for the existence, the extent, and the direction of the asymmetry of the distribution. Finally, the test for $\beta_1 = 0$ was named the *Funnel Asymmetry Test* (FAT) since its null hypothesis is that the distribution of the coded estimates outline the shape of an "inverted funnel": as the number of primary studies considered increases, its rejection points towards the presence of selection bias. Stanley (2008) shown through simulations that FAT is a valid test for the presence of publication selection, with nominal levels attending its significance; however, it has low power and, thus, it is always appropriate to address selection bias even when it is not detected.

The *Precision-Effect Test* (PET) coincides with the significance test of coefficient β_0 after the estimation of equation 1: its rejection suggests the existence of a true effect beyond publication

bias. Nonetheless, its magnitude is known to be downwardly biased when an underlying genuine effect exists, while it is upwardly biased in the contrary case. More than posing problems about the quantification of its true magnitude, this kind of bad measuring causes low power and inflation of actual the test's levels. In details: its power is inversely related to the extent of selection bias; while the incidence of type 1 errors is increasing in the degree of unexplained heterogeneity. Although the typical power level of PET makes it reliable for detecting the absence of an effect, the usual excess heterogeneity in the data raises concerns in rejecting H_0 (Stanley, 2008).

Of course, heterogeneity can potentially be explained through multivariate models, leading to better estimates of β_0 . Nonetheless, to provide an appropriate statistical test for the presence of the phenomenon of interest it is necessary to estimate it from the PEESE model. Thanks to its better capacity in controlling for publication bias, the estimated genuine effect in equation 2 provides a better measure of the genuine effect when FAT evidences selection bias. However, since selection bias must be suspected anyway, the significance test for β_0 retrieved from PEESE is more reliable in rejecting H_0 than PET.

On the other hand, since PET is good in detecting the absence of genuine effect and that, moreover, in the absence of genuine effect PET-FAT fits better the data than PEESE, the latter test should only be performed to test the null hypothesis once PET has already rejected it.

However, before of proceeding to PEESE estimation, also the appropriateness of PET-FAT models must be assessed. Indeed, as explained, any conclusion must be drawn from the suitable model. The decision between estimating models through WLS, lies on the result of a heteroskedasticity test: consistently with Feld and Heckemeyer (2011), in this analysis the decision has been based on the results of a White and a Breush-Pagan tests.

Then, if the Q-test evidenced the need for a Random-Effects MRA, a Breusch-Pagan LM test was run to check if the residuals' variance is zero: rejection of this null hypothesis evidence the presence of unobserved cluster (study) effects that must be addressed by a 2-level approach.

Finally, if the latter test suggested a cluster econometric approach, the Hausman test has been performed to test for the endogeneity of the unobserved study effects: rejection supported the use of the Fixed-Effects Cluster econometric estimation with respect to a Random-Effects Multilevel approach.

Only once the suitable model has been assessed, its results can support the decision on wether to use PEESE and/or a more complex version of PET-FAT. Similarly, the same sequence of tests was performed on these latter following approaches and conclusions made on the consistent models. For what concerns multivariate models, the test has been made on their General specification and, then, once the appropriate estimation method was chosen, proceeded with the remotion of variables to get their Specific version.

4 The Empirical Research

4.1 Dataset

4.1.1 Primary Studies Sample

The units of an MRA dataset are the estimates retrieved from the primary empirical studies. Of course, the literature consulted relates to the topic and research questions of interest; ultimately, the information coded must be functional to their empirical investigation.

Hence, since data are the product of the research process conducted, this initial procedure phase must be as comprehensive as possible of all the available knowledge on the relation inspected. This is essential for both the representativeness of the universe of empirical studies of interest, and to avoid worsening selection bias through an additional selection induced by the meta-analyst.

In accordance with the reproducibility that distinguishes meta-analysis from narrative review, the exploration and the codification of primary studies will be described in this section.

For what concerns representativeness, it is necessary to point out that it is likely that not all the aspects of interest have been explored by empirical researches, or at least with the same coverage. Therefore, the generalization must be intended as limited to the present evidence.

Within this universe, another limit is imposed by the fact that results included must be comparable. This requirement is achievable through transformations, as it will be explained afterwards, in section 4.1.2. Nonetheless, even this solution is constrained by the availability of information needed to carry out the conversions. In summary, the studies that can be included are those that directly involve the effect size measure of interest, or that contain all the statistics to convert a given kind of measure used in the chosen one.

The ideal population is defined by the set of basic characteristics that qualify the underlying causal relation. This is implicitly attained by researching specific keywords used in the study. This practically involves the research of econometric studies on the basic component of the relation: the main dependent (proxy) variables expressed as a function of the key controls.

The purpose of this analysis is to quantitatively describe the actual mitigation effect of innovation on human environmental impact. Since both innovation and environmental impact are not directly measurable, it is necessary to select one specific representative variable for each to allow comparison; nonetheless, the complexity of both the two concepts makes the selection of variables affecting the final results, since different measures can lead to different results.

For what concerns environmental impact, the most common measure is the level of GHG emissions. Furthermore, as carbon dioxide is the major contributor to overall GHG emissions, CO₂ emissions level is the most common proxy measure used.

On the other hand, innovation is usually represented by R&D investments or by the number of patents: the former likely represents the initial innovating efforts; the latter its results. Although both are valid measures used in empirical research on innovation, they are not comparable between

them. R&D expenditures has been chosen over patents because of two reasons, presented in section 2.2: first of all, because it is the most common measure used to endogenize innovation; secondly, patents have a possible inherent controversial effect on innovation, as some authors suggest they can in fact limit diffusion of inventions.

The collection of primary studies started in March of 2024 with the research of publications that used different combinations of these group of words as keywords, in their title, or in their text: "CO2", "Carbon Dioxide", "GHG", "Emissions"; "R&D", "Research and Development", "Innovation"; "Econometric", "Impact". The online libraries consulted are: Google Scholar, the online library of the University of Bologna AlmaStart, and Scopus.

After a primary collection of studies, the same research of keywords proceeded within the references of the documents retrieved. This process ended with 96 publications retrieved on July 24th. Among these papers only 77 are econometric studies; 65 use R&D in their explanatory variables set, rather than exclusively patents counts; 16 were removed because do not report some crucial data: the ultimate collection of the 49 suitable documents retrieved is listed in Table 1.

For what concerns studies that reported multiple estimates, whenever the author explicitly indicates some results as relevant, only these were coded in the dataset; otherwise, all the outputs disclosed have been included.

The end of this process results in a dataset of 180 estimates.

Reference	Journal	Citations	Sample Type
Afrifa et al. (2020)	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	90	Emerging
Ahmad et al. (2020)	Environmental and Ecological Statistics	185	OECD
Alam et al. (2021)	International Journal of Finance and Economics	103	OECD
Alam et al. (2019)	Energy Economics	344	G6
Ang (2009)	Ecological Economics	508	China
Apergis et al. (2013)	Ecological Economics	107	Europe
Balli et al. (2023)	Frontiers in Environmental Science	0	European Middle- Income and Emerging
Balsalobre-Lorente et al. (2018)	Energy policy	1289	EU5
Cai et al. (2021)	Frontiers in Environmental Science	73	China
Chen and Lee (2020)	Journal of Cleaner Production	455	World

Chen and Mkumbo (2020)	International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Policy	2	OECD
Churchill et al. (2019)	Energy Economics	393	G7
Cole et al. (2005)	Journal of environmental economics and management	598	UK
Fernández et al. (2018)	Journal of Cleaner Production	523	EU15
Ganda (2019)	Journal of Cleaner Production	408	OECD
Garrone and Grilli (2010)	Energy Policy	232	OECD
Herzer (2022)	Energy Policy	19	G7
Huang et al. (2018)	Energy Policy	159	China
Iancu et al. (2022)	SyNERGY MED 2022 - 2nd International Conference on Energy Transition in the Mediterranean Area, Proceedings	1	EU27
Jiang et al. (2024)	Journal of the Knowledge Economy	34	G7
Jiao et al. (2018)	Natural Hazards	70	China
Jin et al. (2017)	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	136	China
Kahouli (2018)	Energy	224	Mediterranean Countries
Kihombo et al. (2021)	Environmental Science and Pollution Research	71	WAME
Kocak and Alnour (2022)	Journal of Cleaner Production	45	USA
Koçak and Ulucak (2019)	Environmental Science and Pollution Research	238	OECD
Lee et al. (2021a)	Russian Journal of Economics	18	BRICS
Lee and Min (2015)	Journal of Cleaner Production	917	Japan
Mamkhezri and Khezri (2024)	Environment, Development and Sustainability	31	World
Mentel et al. (2022)	Energies	14	General
Mourshed and Quddus (2009)	International Journal of Energy Sector Management	16	EU15
Ni et al. (2022)	Resources Policy	40	Developed
Pata et al. (2023)	Journal of Cleaner Production	21	NATO
Petrović and Lobanov (2020)	Journal of Cleaner Production	162	OECD
Saeed and Iqbal (2024)	Environmental Science and Pollution Research	0	China

Shaari et al. (2016)	International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy	37	Developed
Shahbaz et al. (2018)	Energy economics	1017	France
Shahbaz et al. (2020)	Technological Forecasting and Social Change	235	UK
Shahzadi et al. (2022)	Renewable Energy	52	Developed
Shao et al. (2022)	Journal of Environmental Management	99	USA
Vitenu-Sackey and Acheampong (2022)	Environmental Science and Pollution Research	20	Developed
Wang et al. (2021)	Journal of Cleaner Production	24	Japan
Wang and Zhang (2020)	Journal of Cleaner Production	293	BRICS
Xu and Khan (2023)	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	11	G7
Yang et al. (2014)	Applied Energy	146	China
Yu and Du (2019)	Atmospheric Pollution Research	12	China
Yu and Xu (2019)	Atmospheric Pollution Research	84	China
Zhai and Song (2013)	International Conference on Geoinformatics	11	China
Zhang et al. (2017)	Energy Policy	724	China

Table 1: Primary Studies Included

4.1.2 Dataset Description

It is straightforward that to investigate sources of variations it is not enough to code only estimates values. For each unit, all of the relevant data must be included to allow their comparison and determine their influence. Of course, we expect that the characteristics of the defined reference universe of studies are so similar that can be described by the use of variables; moreover, it is necessary that the determining aspects suggested by theory can be represented by observable variables.

Therefore, the dataset must include each of the estimates traits that are suspected to be important for the research questions.

The dataset used for this analysis is made up of 67 variables imputed by the review of the relative estimate's primary studies. These variables can be grouped according to the kind of information they gather: the first group of variables listed in Table 2 identifies the estimate by the ID of its primary study, its own assigned ID, and the number of estimates retrieved from the same research; the second group of variables describe the unit's primary study; the third group qualify the period

and the sample to which the estimate refers to; the forth group contains relevant descriptives of the effect size; the fifth group lists a set of observable characteristics that potentially affect estimations.

Variable Code	Description	Variable Type
<i>Estimates Identifiers</i>		
ID	ID of the Primary Study	Nominal
ID_estimation	ID of the unit	Nominal
ID_est_num	Num of estimates for the same ID	Integer
<i>Primary Study Descriptives</i>		
title	Title of the primary study	String
author	Authors	String
journal	Journal	String
impact_factor	Scopus CiteScore 2023 (Elsevier, 2024)*	Ordinal
publ_year	Year of publication	Nominal
cit_num	Number of citations	Integer
<i>Period and Sample Observed</i>		
first_year	First year of observation	Integer
last_year	Last year of observation	Integer
years_num	Num of years observed	Integer
avg_year	Average of first_year and last_year	Numeric
unfccc	avg_year is after the year of institution of the UNFCCC (≥ 1994)	Binary
kyoto	avg_year is after the year of execution of the Kyoto Protocol (≥ 2005)	Binary
copenhagen	avg_year is after the year of ratification of the Copenhagen Accord (≥ 2009)	Binary
N	Number of units in the sample	Integer
n	Number of observations	Integer
national	If the unit of observation is the country = 1	Binary
sample	Sample type	String
oecd	sample strictly belongs to OECD	Binary
non_oecd	sample strictly differs from OECD	Binary
mix_oecd	sample contains OECD countries	Binary
eu	sample contains countries in Europe	Binary
africa	sample contains countries in Africa	Binary
n_america	sample contains countries in North America	Binary
s_america	sample contains countries in South America	Binary
mw	sample contains countries in Mid West	Binary

asia_oceania	sample contains countries in Asia and Oceania	Binary
eu_namer	sample contains countries in Europe and/or North America	Binary
afr_samer_mw	sample contains countries in Africa and/or South America and/or Mid West	Binary
only_eunam	If sample strictly belongs to eu_namer	Binary
only_asiaoc	If sample strictly belongs to asia_oceania	Binary
only_afrsamw	If sample strictly belongs to afr_samer_mw	Binary
mix_continent	If (only_eunam + only_asiaoc + only_afrsamw) = 0 then mix_continent = 1, otherwise mix_continent = 0	Binary

Estimate Descriptives

dep_var	dep_var classification type	Binary
dep_var_pc	dep_var is in per capita terms	Binary
indep_var	Independent variable of interest classification type	Binary
environmental_rd	indep_var represents environmental innovation	Binary
public	indep_var represents public expenditures	Binary
indep_var_pc	indep_var is in per capita terms	Binary
elasticity	Effect size is an elasticity	Binary
magnitude	Elasticity value	Numeric
negative	magnitude is negative	Binary
estimated	The reported effect size is converted as an elasticity, rather than being it as reported	Binary
st_err	Standard error of magnitude	Numeric
prec	Ratio of st_err	Numeric
t_stat	T-statistic of the effect size	Numeric
df	Degrees of freedom of estimation	Integer
pcc	Partial Correlation Value	Numeric
pcc_se	Standard error of pcc	Numeric
pcc_prec	Ratio of pcc_se	Numeric
significant	magnitude is significant at the 5% level	Binary

Potential Determinants of Interest

long_term	Effect size is a long-term coefficient, rather than contemporaneous	Binary
estimator	Estimator classification type	String
dynamic	estimator employed to estimate a dynamic model, rather than not	Binary
csd_control	estimator accounts for cross-sectional dependence	Binary
htg_control	estimator allows heterogeneity of slopes	Binary
endog_control	estimator corrects for the endogeneity of controls	Binary

rd_lag	Lag(s) of indep_var included as control(s)	Binary
rd_sq	Squared indep_var additionally included as a control	Binary
income	Variables related to income level included as controls	Binary
patents	Variables related to patents included as controls	Binary
governance	Variables related to governance quality level included as controls	Binary
carbon_str	Variables related to carbon energy structure included as controls	Binary
mkt_openn	Variables related to market openness included as controls	Binary
n_controls	How many types of controls of interest (income, patents, governance, carbon_str, mkt_openn, env_policy) included in the estimate's model	Integer

Table 2: Dataset Variables

*To avoid missings values, Journals not included in the Scopus CiteScore 2023 - i.e.: Iancu et al. (2022); Jiao et al. (2018); Zhang et al. (2017) - are assigned the minimum value of 2.6, which is the lowest score attained by the Journals included.

Clearly, the central variables for an MRA are those related to the effect size. Its codification must conform to the necessary comparability of effects.

The primary imperative task of the meta-analyst is to decide the comparable summary statistics that represent the extent and the direction of the effect size. In order for these measures to be eligible, they need to respect two requisites: the effect that they measure is a partial one, in accordance with the usual econometrics *ceteris paribus* assumption; it should be comparable both within and between included studies (Stanley and Doucouliagos, 2012). Additionally, its value should be interpretable, to allow meaningful conclusions about the results, and that its variability can be directly or indirectly quantified (Harrer et al., 2021).

Elasticity is the natural and most common way to represent an empirical economic effect. Additionally to being commonly used in primary studies, it attenuates the problem caused by the diversity of unit of measure of the main dependent variable: as introduced in section 3.2.3, incomparability of scales of measure prevents effect size to be i.i.d. (Becker and Wu, 2007). On the other hand, *level-level* coefficients and semi-elasticities are intrinsically more affected by the scale used. 26 different class identifiers have been assigned to indep_var during the codification, and no one is particularly more frequent than others: as each category possibly describes a different form of R&D expenditure, they can have different ranges of variation, which in some cases should not be compared in absolute value. Furthermore, this analysis focuses on innovating efforts, and the concept of "effort" is intrinsically valued in relation to a characteristic base level. Hence, by measuring causal impacts of percentage changes, elasticity better captures underlying efforts.

When primary studies do not involve elasticities, they can be retrieved from other reported statis-

tics: *level-level* coefficients and their standard errors were converted using the delta method as

$$\text{elasticity}_i = \text{level-level coefficient} \cdot \frac{\text{Average value of X}}{\text{Average value of Y}}$$

$$\text{st_err}_i = SE(\text{level-level coefficient}) \cdot \frac{\text{Average value of X}}{\text{Average value of Y}},$$

while, in the case of semi-elasticities, effect sizes were converted as

$$\text{elasticity}_i = \text{semi-elasticity} \cdot \text{Average value of X}$$

$$\text{st_err}_i = SE(\text{semi-elasticity}) \cdot \text{Average value of X}.$$

Of course both of the two types of conversion require both standard errors and descriptives statistics to be retrievable from the primary studies.

In fact, this conversion occurred for 56 estimates coded; on the other hand, it is not possible for the 9 estimates reported in Zhang et al. (2017), which have thus been left as semi-elasticities: therefore, these estimates cannot be compared with other elasticities (but only through partial correlations, as it will be discussed shortly).

However, also *dep_var* classifies CO2 emissions types in 8 groups: this additional variety furtherly increases the range of possible couples of Y and X scales of measure used in primary studies, potentially undermining comparability. This can practically result in a high level of left-unexplained heterogeneity.

Because of this usual kind of problem, many MRA use t-values to measure effect sizes: they have not dimensionality, which guarantees comparison, and they have a well-known distribution (Stanley and Jarrell, 2005). Moreover, since it is generally reported, it reduces the possibility of introducing errors through transformations of data by the meta-analyst herself.

It must be clarified that this is essentially different from what is done in equation 8 to address heteroskedasticity: the use of t-statistics as the effect size measure does not involve the transformation of the RHS of equation 1. However, although using t-statistics as the dependent variable in equation 1 equally deals with heteroskedastik errors, it changes the interpretation of regression coefficients. Indeed, as Becker and Wu (2007) point out, t-statistics information about effects is congenitally influenced by precision, which, in turn, can be equally influenced by both variability and sample dimension. Therefore, this statistic is not an uncontaminated estimator of the effect size, and regression on it is less meaningful.

One best alternative dimensionless statistical measure of association is given by partial correlations. Contrarily to *zero order correlation*, partial correlation represents the strength and direction of the linear relation between *dep_var* and *indep_var* keeping all the controls fixed - *ceteris paribus* -. Although this latter measure is rarely reported in primary economic studies, it can be computed

from conventionally reported regression coefficients:

$$pcc_i = \frac{t_stat_i}{\sqrt{t_stat_i^2 + df_i}}$$

$$pcc_se_i = \sqrt{\frac{1 - pcc_i^2}{df_i}}.$$

Moreover, since, unlike $elasticity_i$, all pcc_i are computed through homogeneous transformations for each unit in the dataset, they ensure greater comparability.

Nonetheless, it is not an economic measure of effect. Additionally, since in economics PCC_s are generally lower than their bounding values ± 1 , the practical significance of the effect must be assessed in relative terms. In this analysis, the interpretation follows the thresholds of economic significance presented by Doucouliagos (2011): in this work, the author proposes to interpret PCC as a small, moderate, or large effect if it is respectively larger than the first quartile (± 0.07), the median (± 0.17), or the third quartile (± 0.33) of the distribution of thousands partial correlations retrieved from 41 meta-analyses in economics.

An additional factor preventing reported effects to be i.i.d. is the set of additional controls in each study (Becker and Wu, 2007). This is the founding principle of multivariate and multi-level approaches, aiming at qualifying the deviations from the ideal distribution due to particular characteristics. And, since estimated models routinely vary across estimates, detecting sources of variation is crucial: both for the validity of results, and for the completeness of empirical knowledge on the relation.

Usual systematic causes of deviation can be grouped as referring to: dependent and independent variables' traits; characteristics of publication; sample type; model specification; estimation method. The list of variables practically used depends firstly on theory, and then on the type of data available. Related to this latter point, also their applicability depends on the number of observations possessing a given quality.

For what concerns the two main variables of interests, CO2 emissions and R&D expenditures levels, after having corrected for the variety of unit of measures, it is relevant to know if and how some qualifying covariates (public and `environmetal_rd`) affect the genuine effect estimation.

Observable data about the type of publication are in this dataset broadly represented by the characteristics of the journal. Nonetheless, as Stanley and Doucouliagos (2012) suggest, these information are usually ineffective in practice.

Finally, variables that in Table 2 are listed under the *Period and Sample Observed* category relates to primary studies' samples and period of observation characteristics; those in *Potential Determinants of Interest* qualify the estimation and modeling framework, instead.

4.1.3 Descriptives Statistics

Table 3 qualifies the overall sample observed through the aggregation of the 49 primary studies included. For space reasons, it is not possible to present the correlations' table: relevant data will

be highlighted in the text itself.

Each primary study provided on average almost 7 effect sizes. The oldest result included was reported in 2005, but the average year in which the covered estimates have been published is much closer to 2024: this is consistent with the recent increasing trend of publications mentioned in section 3.2.

Nonetheless, the mean value of `avg_year` is between 1999 and 2000: the overall period of observation is centered between the mean of `first_year`, 1985, and the mean of `last_year`, 2014, an interval's width consistent with the average number of years observed (that is: with the mean of `avg_years`). This vaguely defines the period to which the final genuine effect relates.

On the other hand, the variables related to global environmental policy coverage indicate that the main period of observation is later than what data on `avg_year` suggest: 86% of estimates' `avg_year` is after the creation of UNFCCC in 1994, and for the 56% it is also after the ratification of the Kyoto Protocol in 2005; only 25% are centered in a period after the Copenhagen Accord of 2009.

For what concerns primary samples, the main focus in this field of research is on countries, rather than on microeconomic data: almost 80% of the results included are based on national aggregate levels.

More than half (53%) of the effect sizes relates solely to OECD countries, while 11% to a mixed OECD and NON-OECD sample. Consistently with this, 60% units involve a sample that includes either Europeans and/or North American countries (`eu_namer`); these two continents have been grouped together because `eu` and `n_america` are highly correlated between them, meaning that they were often merged in studies' samples (see Table 4). Nonetheless, 4/5 of primary samples include Asian or Oceanian countries, with 33% of collected estimates not including other continents; furthermore, among these estimates, most focus on China only (see Table 1). Less estimates refer to the residual geographical areas, and none of them does not also focus on some of the more frequent continents: `only_afrsammw` is 0 for every estimate; moreover, correlation between `africa`, `s_america`, and `mw` is high.

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
ID_est_num	180	6,78	5,64	1	21
publ_year	180	2018,04	4,63	2005	2024
first_year	180	1985,61	26,83	1870	2006
last_year	180	2014,07	5,10	1998	2021
years_num	180	29,13	26,22	6	147
avg_year	180	1999,84	14,20	1942	2012,5
unfcc	180	0,81	0,39	0,00	1,00
kyoto	180	0,56	0,50	0,00	1,00
copenhagen	180	0,25	0,43	0,00	1,00
N	180	93,43	283,99	1	1350
n	180	1046,35	3478,14	20	29520
national	180	0,78	0,42	0	1
oecd	180	0,53	0,50	0,00	1,00
non_oecd	180	0,36	0,48	0,00	1,00
mix_oecd	180	0,11	0,32	0,00	1,00
eu	180	0,56	0,50	0,00	1,00
africa	180	0,14	0,35	0,00	1,00
n_america	180	0,49	0,50	0,00	1,00
s_america	176	0,15	0,36	0,00	1,00
mw	176	0,09	0,28	0,00	1,00
asia_oceania	180	0,81	0,40	0,00	1,00
eu_namer	180	0,60	0,49	0,00	1,00
afr_samer_mw	180	0,17	0,38	0,00	1,00
mix_continent	180	0,49	0,50	0,00	1,00
only_eunam	180	0,18	0,38	0,00	1,00
only_asiaoc	180	0,33	0,47	0,00	1,00
only_afrsammw	180	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00

Table 3: Cumulative Sample Observed Summary Statistics

Summary statistics about the number of estimates per primary study, the period of publication and observed, and the sample dimension.

	oecd	non_oecd	mix_oecd	eu	africa	n_america	s_america	mw	asia_oceania	eu_namer	afr_samer_mw	mix_continent	only_eunam	only_asiaoc
oecd	1,00	-0,79	-0,37	0,66	-0,30	0,66	-0,18	-0,20	-0,25	0,76	-0,25	0,37	0,30	-0,63
non_oecd	-0,79	1,00	-0,27	-0,78	0,00	-0,68	-0,02	-0,15	0,38	-0,86	-0,07	-0,51	-0,36	0,83
mix_oecd	-0,37	-0,27	1,00	0,15	0,47	-0,02	0,31	0,53	-0,18	0,12	0,49	0,20	0,06	-0,26
eu	0,66	-0,78	0,15	1,00	0,01	0,69	0,03	0,24	-0,23	0,91	0,06	0,60	0,19	-0,79
africa	-0,30	0,00	0,47	0,01	1,00	-0,03	0,84	0,58	0,08	-0,03	0,88	0,43	-0,19	-0,29
n_america	0,66	-0,68	-0,02	0,69	-0,03	1,00	0,08	0,16	0,05	0,80	0,04	0,66	-0,01	-0,69
s_america	-0,18	-0,02	0,31	0,03	0,84	0,08	1,00	0,45	0,21	-0,01	0,90	0,44	-0,20	-0,30
mw	-0,20	-0,15	0,53	0,24	0,58	0,16	0,45	1,00	0,00	0,21	0,66	0,32	-0,14	-0,22
asia_oceania	-0,25	0,38	-0,18	-0,23	0,08	0,05	0,21	0,00	1,00	-0,41	0,12	0,39	-0,95	0,36
eu_namer	0,76	-0,86	0,12	0,91	-0,03	0,80	-0,01	0,21	-0,41	1,00	0,02	0,52	0,39	-0,86
afr_samer_mw	-0,25	-0,07	0,49	0,06	0,88	0,04	0,90	0,66	0,12	0,02	1,00	0,48	-0,22	-0,33
mix_continent	0,37	-0,51	0,20	0,60	0,43	0,66	0,44	0,32	0,39	0,52	0,48	1,00	-0,45	-0,69
only_eunam	0,30	-0,36	0,06	0,19	-0,19	-0,01	-0,20	-0,14	-0,95	0,39	-0,22	-0,45	1,00	-0,34
only_asiaoc	-0,63	0,83	-0,26	-0,79	-0,29	-0,69	-0,30	-0,22	0,36	-0,86	-0,33	-0,69	-0,34	1,00

Table 4: Correlation Between Geographical Variables

In bold correlations higher than 0,5 in absolute value. Since only_afrsammw is 0 for each unit, its correlation is undefined.

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std.Dev.	Min	Max
magnitude	171	-0,053	0,29	-1,79	1,21
st_err	171	0,11	0,45	0,00	5,09
negative	180	0,69	0,46	0,00	1,00
estimated	180	0,31	0,46	0,00	1,00
prec	180	52,86	93,93	0,20	910,00
t_stat	180	-1,54	4,92	-22,00	21,84
df	180	1039,22	3477,76	15,00	29514,00
pcc	180	-0,02	0,09	-0,49	0,29
pcc_se	180	0,08	0,05	0,01	0,26
pcc_prec	180	20,69	24,80	3,89	171,80
significant	180	0,74	0,44	0,00	1,00
dep_var_pc	180	0,41	0,49	0,00	1,00
environmental_rd	180	0,19	0,40	0,00	1,00
indep_var_pc	180	0,05	0,22	0,00	1,00
public	180	0,16	0,36	0,00	1,00
long_term	180	0,37	0,48	0,00	1,00
dynamic	180	0,44	0,50	0,00	1,00
csd_control	180	0,28	0,45	0,00	1,00
htg_control	180	0,60	0,49	0,00	1,00
endog_control	180	0,38	0,49	0,00	1,00
rd_lag	180	0,23	0,42	0,00	1,00
rd_sq	180	0,05	0,22	0,00	1,00
income	180	0,81	0,40	0,00	1,00
patents	180	0,09	0,29	0,00	1,00
governance	180	0,10	0,30	0,00	1,00
carbon_str	180	0,37	0,48	0,00	1,00
mkt_openn	180	0,49	0,50	0,00	1,00
n_controls	180	1,89	1,05	0,00	5,00

Table 5: Summary Statistics of Effect Sizes and Controls

magnitude and st_err have fewer observation due to the inconvertibility of estimates in Zhang et al. (2017).

Table 5 describes the observed estimates' characteristics.

Although 70% of estimates report a negative value, 74% are significant at the 5% level, and the mean of magnitude is -0,053, published effect sizes widely range between negative and positive values: the standard deviation of magnitude is four times as large as its mean, and even the mean of the reported estimated deviation (`st_err`) is greater than 0,053.

Partial correlations confirm this conclusion: following the yet cited Doucouliagos (2011)'s guidelines, the mean `pcc` is negative but insignificant (see Figure 12b); however, retrieved values range between an almost large positive effect and a negative very large effect.

The described variation of reported effects is certainly in part caused by the timing of publication. Indeed, as results get published, knowledge accumulates and, moreover, stimulates, guides, and affects successive results.

Figure 11 shows the trend of the mean reported effect size as a function of time of publication: rather than a summary evidence of an actual decrease of the effect, it must be interpreted as the consequence of the accumulation of reported results on collective knowledge.

The increasing concentration of "dots" as `publ_year` increases, depicts the growing trend in the number of related publications. This consequently increased the rate of positive values, which, as a cumulative result, lessened the mean reported effect: this is likely because a higher frequency of estimates increases the probability of getting much different results. Moreover, it is the possible result of the attempt to corroborate or discredit previous conclusions.

(a) magnitude per publ_year

(b) pcc per publ_year

Figure 11: Magnitude per Publication Year

The y-axis represents the collected effect sizes, respectively as elasticities in figure 11a, and as partial correlations in figure 11b. The abscissa represents the year of publication of the primary study from which each estimate has been retrieved.

(a) magnitude Histogram

The range of magnitude plotted was reduced from -0.5 to 0.5, to allow a better visualization.

(b) pcc Histogram

Figure 12: Sample Distribution of magnitude and pcc

Bars represent the density of the respective interval of values. The blue continuous line is the average value.

In figure 12a dashed lines represent Cohen (2013)'s general thresholds of economic practical significance: the yellow, the orange, and the red ranges respectively represent the small, the medium, and the large practical effects areas.

In figure 12b dashed lines depicts the Doucouliagos (2011)'s pcc thresholds, instead: the yellow, the orange, and the red lines respectively represent the small, the moderate, and the large effects areas.

Figure 12 provides deeper insight into the distribution of reported effects.

In this primary inspection phase, the focus is on the practical extent of the effect: rather than its statistical significance, it is now interesting to inspect if published results testimony the efficacy of innovation for the environment. Indeed, the importance of this analysis is founded on examining the practical efficacy of innovation as a solution to the climate problem, rather than just evidencing their relationship.

In doing this, in addition to the Doucouliagos (2011)'s guidelines to interpret pcc, Cohen (2013)'s thresholds for elasticities help to evaluate concrete effectiveness: according to the author, an effect is practically small, medium, or large if its absolute value is larger than $0,2\sigma$, $0,5\sigma$, or $0,8\sigma$ respectively. σ represents the deviation of its distribution and, thus, can be estimated by the mean of `st_err` (0,11): thus, for the collected magnitudes the thresholds are 0,022, 0,055, and 0,088.

Figure 12a shows that the mean of magnitude (blue line) almost coincides with the threshold for a medium negative level of effectiveness (orange dashed line). In addition, the same graph shows a higher density for negative values than for positive ones. Nonetheless, the wide variation, ranging from large negative to large positive elasticity values, prevents any conjecture about the true underlying direction and degree of effectiveness.

Notwithstanding the last inference, the pcc histogram shows a less optimistic view: the partial relation between the two entities of interest is practically insignificant.

Anyway, it would be unwise to base conclusion on this basic analysis: first, because the distribution of the estimated effect sizes does not take into account of their precision, which is essential to evaluate reliability of results; secondly, because there is no data on the sources of deviation of values. These two elements basically entail the purpose of the following MRA.

(a) magnitude Funnel Plot.

$\theta_{REML} = -0,046$ with a 95% confidence interval defined between $-0,074$ and $-0,018$.

The two less precise observations have been removed by the plot since they complicate the visualization of other data while being very low informative.

(b) pcc Funnel Plot.

$\theta_{REML} = -0,002$ with a 95% confidence interval defined between $-0,006$ and $0,003$.

Figure 13: Funnel Plot and Random-Effect Estimated 95% Confidence Interval of The Effect Size

The red line is placed at the value of the computed Random-Effects weighted average θ_{REML} . The grey lines represent the associated confidence interval at the 95% level.

A clearer depiction of the composition of estimates is provided by the funnel plot in Figure 13. As yet discussed in section 3.2, the plot of estimates together with their precision should resemble a triangle below the weighted average: this is because most accurate estimates are weighted more in that average, while less accurate estimates intrinsically have a wider dispersion. Moreover, the asymmetry with respect to the mean value represents the eventual publication bias.

The graphs show a slightly higher frequency of values on the left of the red line, particularly for what concerns pcc: this may suggest a small tendency to report lower, negative values than higher ones. However, the placement of the dots does not resemble the typical asymmetric tailed distribution expected in the presence of a strong publication bias.

Figure 13a evidences a high degree of heterogeneity of elasticities. This is not true for partial correlations in figure 13b, which mostly appear under the 95% confidence interval area.

For what concerns the respective estimated effect size, the Random-Effects weighted average magnitude is $-0,046$, with a 95% confidence interval defined between $-0,074$ and $-0,018$; for pcc it is $-0,002$, with a 95% confidence interval defined between $-0,006$ and $0,003$, instead. These results reinforce what has been discussed before about the effectiveness of innovation: while collected elasticities suggest a small mitigating power of innovation on environmental impact, partial correlations evidence an almost insignificant relation.

Nonetheless, this analysis not only, and once again, lacks explanation of heterogeneity, but it may be strongly tinted by influentials at the top of the funnel graph.

The explanation of why the graphs above show so much variation on the reported results is not only important to get a statistically valid genuine effect; it also essentially provides an understanding of the factors connected with an effective reduction of pollution from innovation: since the latter outcome coincides with the goal of environmental technical change, results may suggest which archetypes to follow.

In doing this, it can be expected that the mentioned characteristics of primary samples in Table 3 represent underlying determining factors: from geographical variables, it can be assessed where innovation has been more effective up to now and, ultimately, if there are contexts to replicate; the impact of time and, especially, of environmental policies is useful to evaluate the progress made.

The controls in Table 5 are basically related to crucial methodological aspects, instead. Nonetheless, some of them can provide important theoretical insights. In particular, the variables representative of the covariates included in the original models are informative about which factors, among those discussed in section 2.2.1, have been found to be effectively determinants of the relation:

- rd_lag impact determine how the inclusion of lags of the dependent variable change the genuine effect estimated: since theory suggest the effect to take time, the simultaneous effect should be reduced;
- rd_sq corroborates the existence of the quadratic relation suggested by the Innovation Claudia Curve theory: a positive significant related coefficient would support an inverted U-shaped relation;

- income, patents, governance, carbon_str, mkt_openn coefficients inform about the importance of the related information for the estimation: their significance respectively suggest the risk and the direction of the omitted variable bias in models not including them. However, these results have the limit of being related only to the inclusion of those controls in the model equation, not about their levels: indeed, since primary data on their levels are not accessible, it is not possible to interpret the impact of their variations.
n_controls measures the marginal influence of their cumulative inclusion.

The remaining variables are related to the operational aspects of estimations. long_term informs about the difference between a short-term and a long-term type of estimated coefficient: thus, the expected effect and its meaning are consistent with those linked to rd_lag.

dep_var_pc, dep_var_ratio, environmental_rd, and public_rd are related to the effects of different mathematical or specific-class definitions of the dependent variable: the aim of the former two is to remove the artificially induced heterogeneity from practical transformations; the latter two to evaluate the effect of particular types of R&D.

Finally, dynamic, csd_control, htg_control, and endog_control determine the importance of addressing commonly expected statistical issues in the estimation of the relation of interest: informing about the bias of not using the correct method, and supporting the appropriateness of the respective solution, possibly guiding future estimations.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 The Meta-Regression Probit Model

As discussed in the theoretical review, the central postulate of this field of research is that innovation provides a solution to the climate change problem. The corresponding fundamental interest is how to enhance its mitigating power: clearly, the primary research question of this analysis is which are the factor that allow to accomplish that.

In line with this, the empirical part of this analysis starts with a Meta-Regression Probit Model, used evaluate the likelihood of measuring a negative effect in response to observed factors. Therefore, the final objective of this section is to indicate which of the characteristics of interest are more linked to the effectiveness of environmental innovation.

Then, successive MRA models for elasticities and PCC will be used to quantify the underlying true effect and detect its sources of deviation.

The dependent variable used in this section is “negative” (Table 5): a dichotomous variable equal to 1 if the respective unit’s estimated effect is negative, and 0 otherwise. Using this binary dependent variable has the advantages of being fully comparable and unaffected by the heteroskedasticity of primary studies’ reported standard errors.

Nonetheless, the *vote-count* outcome resulting from this kind of dichotomization is highly affected by publication bias, with the extent of its incidence increasing as more research is added. (Stanley, 2008). Therefore, given that this model is based on the proportion of negative values in the sample, it is worth stressing that the results of this method can only be representative of the population of the dataset used.

As shown by the summary statistics in Table 5, the sample base-rate of a negative effect is 69%. Assuming a multivariate data-generating process for negative, the estimated model is:

$$Pr(\text{negative}_i = 1 | \mathbf{Z}_i, SE_i) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \sum \beta_p Z_{pi} + \beta_1 SE_i + \epsilon_i),$$

where Φ represents the Standard Normal CDF, in accordance with the probit specification; SE_i is the standard error, included to capture the variation in the probability as precision lessens; \mathbf{Z}_i represents the unit’s observed set of characteristics included in the model.

A multilevel approach was not adopted because there is a high risk of endogeneity between the unobserved study’s effect and the fixed-effects variables: since there are not suitable estimation methods to condition out individuals’ unobserved fixed-effects, a pooled approach was preferred (StataCorp, 2023).

However, the fact that each primary study provided several estimates exposes to the risk of over-representation of their unvarying characteristics. To address this problem, each unit was weighted by the number of estimates included in its same primary study: this mechanism equalizes each of the primary studies’ contribute.

In this context, the focus is on the set of characteristics which can rationally affect the sign of the estimates. Thus, the classes of variables that were selected for the investigation are those related to: the type of sample used; the period of observation; the type of effect measured; the nature of the R&D expenditures; the set of controls used. Consistently, the variables included in \mathbf{Z}_i were selected among those in the correlation Table C, in the Appendix: `non_oecd`, `mix_oecd`, `only_eunam`, `only_asiaoc`; `avg_year`, `unfccc`, `kyoto`, `copenhagen`; `long_term`; `environmental_rd`, `public`; `rd_lag`, `rd_sq`, `income`, `patents`, `governance`, `carbon_str`, `mkt_openn`, `n_controls`. From the correlation table it is possible to see some of these variables to be highly correlated between them: `non_oecd` with `only_asiaoc`; `avg_year` with `unfccc` and `kyoto`, with the latter two being highly correlated even between them; `n_controls` with the categories of controls of interest. However, each group of correlated variables is easily recognized to convey similar information about the units: the former relates to the type of the sample used, and, since `only_asiaoc` mostly involves countries outside OECD, they describe similar geographical areas observed; environmental politics variables were designed with reference to `avg_year`, to describe a specific time period; the correlation between `environmental_rd` and `public` shows that in the majority of primary studies the two forms of expenditures (environmental and public) coincided; `n_controls` counts how many of the controls of interest were included in the primary model and, thus, is strictly related to their respective covariates.

Therefore, to avoid multicollinearity issues, the final model specification uses a set of uncorrelated variables that capture all relevant information while providing the best fit: five preliminary models were tested, and the final model was selected based on the specification with the highest Pseudo-R², AICc, and BIC values.

Furthermore, since `unfccc` and `kyoto` are also highly correlated, but `kyoto` has more variation in the dataset (the mean of `unfccc` is 0,81, compared to 0,56 for `kyoto`), the inclusion of the latter has been preferred over the alternative.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	OECD	Continents	Policies	Public	Control Number	Final Probit	Final Logit
non_oecd	-0.00238 (0.141)						
mix_oecd	-0.202 (0.149)						
only_eunam		0.252* (0.135)	0.261* (0.146)	0.249* (0.137)	0.189 (0.119)	0.189 (0.119)	0.184 (0.120)
only_asiaoc		0.310** (0.133)	0.301** (0.132)	0.308** (0.135)	0.338** (0.130)	0.338** (0.130)	0.333** (0.139)
avg_year	0.000363 (0.00398)	-0.000119 (0.00409)		-0.000231 (0.00413)	-0.00210 (0.00362)	-0.00210 (0.00362)	-0.00196 (0.00361)
kyoto			0.0489 (0.143)				
copenhagen			-0.0801 (0.159)				
long_term	0.193** (0.0983)	0.269** (0.0970)	0.259** (0.0932)	0.262** (0.0995)	0.269** (0.0874)	0.269** (0.0874)	0.269** (0.0914)
rd_lag	0.0893 (0.138)	0.120 (0.121)	0.139 (0.121)	0.110 (0.124)	0.0423 (0.108)	0.0423 (0.108)	0.0607 (0.112)
rd_sq	-0.169 (0.228)	-0.262 (0.205)	-0.270 (0.211)	-0.271 (0.205)	-0.349** (0.153)	-0.349** (0.153)	-0.330** (0.149)
environmental_rd	0.0687 (0.150)	0.151 (0.129)	0.127 (0.138)		0.155 (0.100)	0.155 (0.100)	0.149 (0.102)
public				0.164 (0.152)			
n_controls	-0.0390 (0.0607)	0.00342 (0.0584)	0.00178 (0.0562)	0.00290 (0.0587)			
income					-0.197* (0.116)	-0.197* (0.116)	-0.205 (0.129)
patents					-0.330** (0.126)	-0.330** (0.126)	-0.315** (0.135)
governance					-0.0143 (0.130)	-0.0143 (0.130)	-0.0224 (0.125)
carbon_str					0.279** (0.0957)	0.279** (0.0957)	0.269** (0.101)
mkt_openn					-0.0686 (0.0928)	-0.0686 (0.0928)	-0.0654 (0.0958)
st_err	-0.105** (0.0490)	-0.0861 (0.0567)	-0.0841 (0.0621)	-0.0890 (0.0599)	-0.0969* (0.0507)	-0.0969* (0.0507)	-0.0947* (0.0522)
N	180	180	180	180	180	180	180
Df	10	10	11	10	14	14	14
Pseudo R2	0.0722	0.1195	0.1262	0.1182	0.2241	0.2241	0.2208
AICc	221.3242	213.2172	212.1222	214.5911	77.4711	77.4711	77.6695
BIC	251.9520	243.8450	245.6733	245.2189	119.6271	119.6271	119.8254
OECD var _s joint p	0.3695						
Continents var _s joint p		0.0554					
Policies var _s joint p			0.8802				
public p				0.2780			
Controls var _s joint p					0.0419		
Correctly predicted %						72.22	67.78
Correctly negative = 1 %						72.00	89.60
Correctly negative = 0 %						72.73	18.18

* observations weighted by the inverse of the number of estimates from the same source

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 6: Average Partial Effects On The Probability Of Measuring A Negative Effect

Table 6 provides the average partial effects estimated from the different estimation models. The reference category for interpretation of `non_oecd` and `mix_oecd` is `oecd`; `only_eunam` and `only_asiaoc` are interpreted with respect to `mix_continent` (and, coincidentally, to `only_afrsamw`).

Estimation (1) refers to the model in which OECD related variables were included in place of those representing continents; the latter group is used for estimation of model (2), instead. As it can be seen from the comparison of the respective model's statistics, additionally to providing a better fit, the geographical variables specifically used in model (2) are jointly significant, whereas `non_oecd` and `mix_oecd` are not.

After having chosen `only_eunam` and `only_asiaoc` over their alternatives, model (3) evidenced that the inclusion of `avg_year` is superior to that of environmental politics variables: although model (2) have slightly lower Pseudo-R² and AICc, BIC is higher, and both `kyoto` and `copenhagen` are not significant, neither jointly nor individually. Hence, since the larger number of variables in model (3) gives almost the same fit as using `avg_year` solely, model (2) specification has been preferred once again.

Specification (4) shows that `public` is slightly less predictive than `environmental_rd`. However, the very slight difference in the fit confirms that the two variables coincidentally convey the same cumulative information for what concerns the sign, due to their strong relation in the sample.

Finally, model (5) evidences that, using the covariates linked to the five controls of interest in place of their aggregate number, `n_controls`, significantly improves the fit of model (2). Therefore it has been chosen as the final specification model.

The final Probit model was subsequently compared to a Logit specification. The superior fit and prediction accuracy of model (6) over model (7) ultimately validated the former as the preferred specification.

Figure 14: Margins Plot of the Average Partial Effects From The Final Probit Model Estimation
Plotted confidence intervals at the 10% level.

Figure 14 depicts the average partial effects from the final probit model.

The most important result is the APE of `st_err`: the negative, significant at the 10% level coefficient implies that, as the level of precision increases (`st_err` decreases), it is more likely for an included estimate to report a negative coefficient. This practically indicates that, in the used dataset, positive effects are more typical for less precise estimates; or, stated differently, that best estimates more likely find that innovation investments reduce pollution, rather than the opposite. It must be specified that this does not imply the direction of publication bias. Indeed, selection bias operates through magnitudes of the effects, which are implicitly inflated with respect to their standard errors. Since the magnitude is not accounted by the dependent variable, this tendency cannot be captured by this model. The coefficient on the standard error only represents its marginal impact on the probability of reporting a negative estimate.

The sign of the coefficients of the two geographical variables, `only_eunam` and `only_asiaoc`, means that primary samples that used European and/or North American, or Asian and/or Oceanian countries have better chances to have reported a negative effect size, with respect to mixed alternatives. Nonetheless, differently from `only_asiaoc`, the marginal effect of `only_eunam` is not significant. For what concerns the time needed for effectiveness, although the inclusion of lags of R&D are not found to be effective for the sign of estimates, long-term coefficients are more likely negative than short-term ones, *ceteris paribus*.

The estimation of a quadratic specification supports the Innovation Claudia Curve: when the

squared innovation term is added to the model, the coefficient of the main dependent tends to be positive, as it is implied by an inverted U-shaped relation with environment.

The fact that the type of R&D considered is specifically targeted at the environment does not significantly influence the direction of the relationship.

For the interpretation of the controls of interests, it is important to remember that their variables only relate to their inclusion in the model, and they cannot be interpreted as their levels increase. The only two significant coefficients are those linked to patents and carbon_str: respectively, taking other characteristics as given, estimates that controlled for the level of patented innovation more frequently measured a positive coefficient; the opposite is true for the ones that included measures of the carbon energy structure. The other controls' response probabilities are not significant instead.

4.2.2 The Publication Bias Meta-Regression Model

The second part of this empirical analysis goes deeper by estimating if the collected literature provides evidence of a persistent effect of innovation on pollution. As explained, the MRA on effect sizes allows to quantify it by partialling out the basic elements of the noise in public empirical knowledge: it estimates the direction and the extent of publication bias, and the impact of the sources of deviation.

The process followed in this section exactly resembles the methodology described in section 3.2.

The starting goal is to prove the existence of a genuine effect beyond publication bias. Then the analysis will investigate the sources of its heterogeneity.

The estimation of the true effect is based on elasticities, since it is the most natural measure used in economic empirical research. PCC will subsequently be used as an instrument for the statistical analysis.

Elasticities

Before starting with estimations and tests, it is important to investigate on the presence of influentials and, eventually, remove them. Therefore, two influential units, with a $dfbeta$ higher than 1, were removed from the following analysis (Table 7 and Figure 15).

Although the Random-Effects weighted average would be slightly influenced by their inclusion, the Fixed-Effects average is instead extremely inflated by the two influentials: the REE magnitude passes from a weighted average magnitude of -0,046 in the full sample to -0,047 (-2%) after their removal; on the other hand, their inclusion increases FEE magnitude by 82%, passing from an average of -0,004 in the full sample to -0,022 in the sample without influentials. Since these units can similarly affect even following results and obscure informative deviations in the sample, their removal is appropriate.

Reference	ID_est_num	sample	magnitude	st_err	prec	t_stat	dfbeta
Shao et al. (2022)	40.1	USA	-0,0246	0,00176	568.18	-13,98	-1,4692
Vitenu-Sackey and Acheampong (2022)	41.3	Developed	0,024	0,001099	910.00	21,84	5,7736

Table 7: Influentials Descriptives

dfbeta index represents the deviation in the pooled fixed-effects weighted average due to their inclusion in the sample, in terms of standard deviations. If an estimate has a *dfbeta* higher than 1 it was recognized as an influential and, thus, removed from the following analysis.

Figure 15: Influentials in The Funnel Plot of Elasticities

Due to their relatively extreme precision, the two influentials would exert too much influence on the weighted average effect size.

The Cochran's Q-test of the Meta-Analysis on the remaining 169 elasticities rejects the null hypothesis of between-population homogeneity of residuals, with a p-value of 0,000. This supports the suitability of an MRA approach for this analysis.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	POLS	WLS FE	WLS RE	RIML	RISML	FE Cluster
$\hat{\beta}_0$	-0.0421 (0.0372)	-0.0145*** (0.00134)	-0.0317 (0.0207)	-0.0399* (0.0243)	-0.0417** (0.0197)	-0.0391*** (0.00272)
$\hat{\beta}_1$	-0.107** (0.0341)	-0.887*** (0.0997)	-0.348 (0.306)	-0.348** (0.175)	-0.445** (0.173)	-0.134*** (0.0246)
$\ln \hat{\tau}_0$				-1.861*** (0.120)	-2.675** (1.033)	
$\ln \hat{\tau}_1$					-5.207*** (0.466)	
N	169	169	169	169	169	169
p(Wald statistic > χ_{df}^2)	0.0029	0.0000	0.2564	0.0469	0.0099	0.0000
$\hat{\tau}$			0.17	0.16	0.07	
I2			99.36	95.09	95.09	
Within R2						0.0628
Between R2						0.0029
Overall R2						0.0277

Standard errors in parentheses.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 8: PET-FAT Selection Bias Meta-Regression Analysis

POLS refers to Pooled OLS; *WLS FE* and *WLS RE* respectively to Fixed-Effects and Random-Effects WLS; *RIML* and *RISML* respectively to the Random-Intercept and Random-Intercept-and-Slopes Multilevel Models; *FE Cluster* to the estimation of the Fixed-Effects Multilevel Model through Fixed-Effects Cluster econometric estimator.

PET-FAT Statistical Properties	Test	Null Hypothesis	Result	Preferred Estimators
Heteroskedasticity	Breusch Pagan test	Normality of errors	$\chi_1^2 = 34,92; p < 0,0001$	FE WLS, RE WLS
	White test	No heteroskedasticity	$\chi_2^2 = 31,00; p < 0,0001$	
Unexplained Heterogeneity	Cochran's Q-test	No Heterogeneity	$\chi_{167}^2 = 3398,60; p < 0,0001$	RE WLS
Study-Specific Effects	Breusch Pagan LM test	No unobserved study-specific effects	$\bar{\chi}^2(0, 1) = 61,04; p < 0,0001$	Cluster-Econometrics: RIML, RISML, FE Cluster
Random Slopes	Likelihood-Ratio test	RIML is nested within RISML	$\chi_1^2 = 1,60; p = 0,2058$	RIML, FE Cluster
Endogeneity	Hausman test	No endogeneity	$\chi_1^2 = 0,46; p = 0,4968$	RIML

Table 9: Best PET-FAT Estimator Selection Tests

Table 8 shows the output of the rounds of estimates of the PET-FAT different specifications models for magnitude. Table 9 presents the results of the tests performed to assess the statistical characteristics of the dataset, and guides throughout the consistent choice of best specification. According to the properties of the dataset, the best estimated specification of the PET-FAT for magnitude is the Random-Intercept model in column (4). As in the different specifications, the genuine effect estimated by the reference model is negative, and it is moreover significant at the 10% level. Similarly, also the estimated selection bias linear coefficient $\hat{\beta}_1$ is negative in all the

specifications, and significant at the 5% level: this signals the increasing tendency to bias coefficients toward stronger negative values as precision of estimates reduces, rather than the opposite. However, as discussed in previous sections, as long as PET detects the existence of a genuine effect, it is not appropriate to base conclusions on its coefficient: in this situation, this is more accurately estimated through a PEESE specification.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	POLS	WLS FE	WLS RE	RIML	RISML	FE Cluster
$\hat{\beta}_0$	-0.0478 (0.0390)	-0.0221*** (0.00104)	-0.0465** (0.0161)	-0.0536** (0.0240)	-0.0536** (0.0240)	-0.0461*** (0.000142)
$\hat{\beta}_2$	-0.0289*** (0.00164)	-0.149 (0.167)	-0.0347 (0.187)	-0.0280 (0.168)	-0.0280 (0.168)	-0.0369*** (0.000667)
$\ln \hat{\tau}_0$				-1.830*** (0.120)	-1.830*** (0.120)	
$\ln \hat{\tau}_2$					-16.97 (.)	
N	169	169	169	169	169	169
Wald Chi2 test p	0.0000	0.3700	0.8533	0.8680	0.8680	0.0000
$\hat{\tau}$			0.17	0.16	0.16	
I2			99.38	95.20	95.20	
Within R2						0.1255
Between R2						0.0064
Overall R2						0.0431

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 10: PEESE Selection Bias Meta-Regression Analysis

PEESE Statistical Properties	Test	Null Hypothesis	Result	Preferred Estimators
Heteroskedasticity	Breusch Pagan test	Normality of errors	$\chi^2_1 = 0,55; p = 0,4566$	POLS, FE WLS, RE WLS
	White test	No heteroskedasticity	$\chi^2_2 = 2,84; p = 0,2412$	
Unexplained Heterogeneity	Cochran's Q-test	No Heterogeneity	$\chi^2_{167} = 3476.92; p < 0,0001$	RE WLS
Study-Specific Effects	Breusch Pagan LM test	No unobserved study-specific effects	$\chi^2(0,1) = 66.11; p < 0,0001$	Cluster-Econometrics: RIML, RISML, FE Cluster
Random Slopes	Likelihood-Ratio test	RIML is nested within RISML	$\chi^2_1 = 0,0; p = 1,000$	RIML, FE Cluster
Endogeneity	Hausman test	No endogeneity	$\chi^2_1 = 0,58; p = 0,4468$	RIML

Table 11: Best PEESE Estimator Selection Tests

Since no variation of slopes is detected in the RISML specification of PEESE (see Table 10), it coincides with the RIML specification.

Once again, the best model specification to estimate PEESE is the RIML in column (4). Results in Table 10 confirm the existence of a negative true effect, higher in magnitude than what PET coefficient estimates: included empirical research imply an average elasticity of CO2 levels to R&D expenditures equal to -0,0536; this value is very close to Cohen's threshold for a practically moderate negative effect, which is -0,055 for this dataset.

For what concerns publication selection, as discussed in section 3.2.3, the quadratic term in PEESE only allows to better partial out the bias from the average reported estimates; nonetheless, β_1 in PET-FAT better approximate its intensity.

Despite the encouraging implications provided by the results presented, the high degree of heterogeneity undermine generalizations. The *Higgins & Thompson's I2* statistic, which quantifies the percentage of between-study variability on the total variation, shows that almost the totality of the left-unexplained heterogeneity is caused by differences in reported estimates, rather than due to sampling errors. This is similarly reflected also in the fit of the FE Cluster models in Tables 9 and 10: although PEESE better captures variability than PET-FAT, both predict only a small portion of within-studies variability, and almost none of that between-studies.

Anyway, heterogeneity is normal in research syntheses (Cooper et al., 2019). And it does not necessarily invalidate quantitative summaries: in econometrics, much of heterogeneity artificially steers from researchers' choices, which is, to some extent, accounted for by the selection bias parameter (Stanley and Doucouliagos, 2012). Rather, it indicates underlying factors of deviation, which can be exploited to describe features of the underlying phenomena. Moreover, as discussed previously, MRA offers methods to statistically prove and estimate the practical role of the drivers suggested by theory on the relation of interest.

For these reasons, the following of this empirical research will focus on investigating the sources of the measured variation: this does not just finally provide better estimations of the genuine effect, but also theoretical and practical knowledge on several aspects of interest in this research field.

Heterogeneity Inspection

The multivariate specification, presented in section 4.2.3, will allow to inspect the role of the char-

acteristics that have been successfully operationalized into variables.

However, for some features which can cause heterogeneity it was not possible to unequivocally represent their partition of qualities, at least for all the units in the sample. One example of these attributes is the geographical area: indeed, each specific context may have unobservable factors which ultimately determines the level of efficiency of innovation; nonetheless, the fact that in primary studies geographical areas are generally merged together hinders the disentangling of their specific contributions.

A naive tentative to investigate this potential cause of left-unexplained heterogeneity, is represented by the outputs presented in column (1) and (2) of Table D, in the Appendix. These PET-FAT and PEESE Random-Effects 3-Levels estimations were performed on a restricted sample of only 76 estimates from 24 primary studies which focused solely on one of these listed areas: Europe, North America, Japan, or China. These are the only areas for which there exists an estimate which refers only to it. This allowed to assign an additional variable, "area" to the remaining units: this variable takes the value 1, 2, 3, or 4 if the unit corresponds to Europe, North America, Japan, or China. This variable constitutes the highest level of the 3-Levels model fitted.

For the sake of clarity, it must be noted that this variable represents a slightly different characteristic than the geographical variables presented in Table 2: `only_eunam` and `only_asia` allow to capture the specific underlying effects of being focused on the respective location, with respect to the use of a generalized sample; in this latter case, each value of "area" represents the distinctive characteristics of being localized in the respective area rather than in any of the other three. Differently said: while the former operationalization identifies units from the generality, this latter variable represents a subdivision in distinct (random) clusters. This finally implies its suitability as a level rather than as a moderator.

From the results presented, it can be firstly noted that the sample restriction did not significantly reduced heterogeneity in the sample: although this sample is classifiable in four groups, the same covariates can predict only a marginally higher fraction of deviations even within those clusters: I_2 , which in the multilevel specification refers to all the levels jointly, is still very high. Additionally, I_{2ID} shows that almost all of the unobserved drivers of heterogeneity are imputable to studies' specific characteristics; symmetrically, $I_{2\text{Geographical Area}}$ indicates that the variation in the random level "area" is not linked with deviations in the genuine effect.⁷ Therefore, the observable geographical areas in the sample do not explain variations in estimates.

Of course, the excessive necessary restriction caused would undermine the statistical power of the general MRA; moreover, it strictly reduces representativity: because of these two reasons, the results from these models cannot be used to draw generalized conclusions.

The remaining six columns of Table D instead investigate the role of outliers. Also in this case,

⁷ I_{2l} is the proportion of left unexplained heterogeneity quantified by $\hat{\tau}_l$ on the total residuals variability measured.

the sample used is a restriction of the total sample, based on the centiles of the units' t-statistics distribution (without the two influential units): the former two columns exclude the 1th and the 99th centiles; estimations in columns (5) and (6) refers to units between the 5th and the 95th centiles; while columns (7) and (8) to those between the 10th and the 90th centiles of the whole sample distribution.

As expected, the outliers removal is effective to reduce heterogeneity, as it can be seen by the progressive reduction of I2 statistics as the sample gets shrank. However, in the face of a reduction of 20% of the sample and, consequently, of a considerable loss of information, in the last two columns I2 is still at about the 80% level: this undermines the appropriateness of such a solution, and confirms the high level of heterogeneity of the collected elasticities.

Another already discussed factor which can likely cause general heterogeneity in the sample is the variability of the unit of measure. As said, although elasticities can somewhat address variations in the dependent variable scales of measure, PCC provides a better solution.

Partial Correlations

The transformation of magnitude in pcc completely removes heterogeneity. As Cochran's Q-Test p-value is 1,0000, the FEE and REE of the weighted averages coincide: the mean pcc is -0,002, with a 95% confidence interval between -0,006 and 0,003 (see Figure 13b).

As expected, the absence of heterogeneity ultimately also involves publication bias MRA models to confirm the results of the Meta-Analysis average: FE Cluster, which is the suitable estimator (see Table 13), corroborates the absence of a partial correlation between CO2 emissions and R&D expenditures (see Table 12); moreover, the left-unexplained heterogeneity is now 0%. The estimates involve the full sample as no influentials were detected.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	POLS	WLS FE	WLS RE	RIML	RISML	FE Cluster
$\hat{\beta}_0$	0.0376** (0.0136)	0.00261 (0.00301)	0.00261 (0.00168)	0.00261 (0.00301)	0.00261 (0.00301)	-0.0212 (0.0139)
$\hat{\beta}_1$	-0.720** (0.228)	-0.207** (0.0972)	-0.207*** (0.0540)	-0.207** (0.0972)	-0.207** (0.0972)	-0.0261 (0.164)
$\ln \hat{\tau}_0$				-11.88 (113.1)	-17.66 (90009.4)	
$\ln \hat{\tau}_1$					-13.25 (627.6)	
N	180	180	180	180	180	180
p(Wald statistic $> \chi^2_{df}$)	0.0028	0.0332	0.0002	0.0332	0.0332	0.8744
I2		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
$\hat{\tau}$			0.0002	0.0000	0.0000	
Within R2						0.0001
Between R2						0.3482
Overall R2						0.1910

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 12: PET-FAT Selection Bias MRA on PCC

PET-FAT Statistical Properties	Test	Null Hypotesis	Result	Preferred Estimators
Heteroskedasticity	Breusch Pagan test	H0=Normality of errors	$\chi^2_1 = 257,11; p < 0,0001$	FE WLS, RE WLS
	White test	H0=No heteroskedasticity	$\chi^2_2 = 47,72; p < 0,0001$	
Unexplained Heterogeneity	Cochran's Q-test	H0=No Heterogeneity	$\chi^2_{167} = 3398,60; p < 0,0001$	RE WLS
Study-Specific Effects	Breusch Pagan LM test	H0=No unobserved study-specific effects	$\chi^2(0,1) = 26,00; p < 0,0001$	Cluster-Econometrics: RIML, RISML, FE Cluster
Random Slopes	Likelihood-Ratio test	H0=RIML is nested within RISML	$\chi^2_1 = 0,00; p = 1,0000$	RIML, FE Cluster
Endogeneity	Hausman test	H0=No endogeneity	$\chi^2_1 = 5,27; p = 0,0217$	FE Cluster

Table 13: Best PET-FAT on PCC Estimator Selection Tests

As said, one of the sources of the magnitude heterogeneity addressed by this approach is the variability of the scales of measures: this is the primary aim of the use of pcc in the literature of MRAs. Nonetheless, as Ugur et al. (2018) point out, it is likely that other specific factors are tackled by using partial correlation in place of elasticities: according to the authors, spillovers of R&D likely bias and complicate the measurement of its causal impact; additionally, the way in which primary studies address common statistical issues, like endogeneity of controls, can cause differences; finally, due to the complexity of the relation between the two entities of interests, it

is likely that the measured elasticities are naturally heterogeneous. Ultimately, the higher degree of comparability, together with a shared insignificant linear relation evidenced, lead to no more heterogeneity left to be explained.

Although the implied conclusion about the relation of interest may appear conflicting with the previous ones, it must be considered that the two index used have different inherent purposes: elasticities represent the economic causal relation; partial correlations are a statistical measure of the intensity of the relation between two underlying quantities.

In fact, it is not rare for these two measures to evidence separate conclusions about the same relation; and, as Reed (2020) illustrates, this dissimilarity is more likely when the correlation between $\frac{1}{st_err_i}$ and $\frac{1}{pcc_se_i}$ is low (in this dataset their correlation is just -0,0296).

The MRA on partial correlation shows that the two entities are not directly related. However, as the primary interest lies in the economic impact of innovation as the - foundational, reasonably not direct - solution to the global climate problem, the focus can be kept on the analysis of elasticities.

4.2.3 The Multivariate Meta-Regression Model

The last part of the empirical process involves investigating the influence of the observed characteristics.

To statistically assess the impact of these units' attributes, the covariates were added to the PET-FAT model: this constitutes the General model. In this preliminary version of the model, all the covariates are added, since the ideal is to draw conclusions about all of the topics which inspired the creation of such variables.

Then, similarly to previous stages, the model has been tested to choose the best estimator.

Table 14 shows all of the estimations of the General model, while Table 15 the output of the tests and the relative best estimator choice.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	POLS	WLS FE	WLS RE	RI REML	RIS REML	FE Cluster
$\hat{\beta}_0$	14.60 (10.65)	6.141* (3.630)	15.77** (5.821)	10.03* (5.559)	10.03* (5.559)	-3.939 (4.410)
$\hat{\beta}_1$	-0.0343 (0.0623)	-0.214 (0.467)	-0.286 (0.308)	-0.0113 (0.209)	-0.0113 (0.209)	-0.116*** (0.0302)
avg_year	-0.00766 (0.00539)	-0.00314* (0.00183)	-0.00819** (0.00295)	-0.00516* (0.00282)	-0.00516* (0.00282)	0.00186 (0.00220)
national	0.230* (0.130)	0.0737** (0.0313)	0.216*** (0.0540)	0.123* (0.0688)	0.123* (0.0688)	
unfecc	0.257 (0.178)	0.0583 (0.0415)	0.329*** (0.0931)	0.160 (0.126)	0.160 (0.126)	
kyoto	0.191 (0.114)	0.00269 (0.0235)	0.0906* (0.0482)	-0.0890** (0.0308)	-0.0890** (0.0308)	
copenhagen	0.125 (0.116)	0.0417** (0.0209)	0.147** (0.0504)	0.202** (0.0655)	0.202** (0.0655)	
non_oecd	0.135* (0.0678)	0.0399** (0.0202)	0.140** (0.0423)	0.244*** (0.0262)	0.244*** (0.0262)	
mix_oecd	0.0299 (0.157)	0.00317 (0.0272)	0.00832 (0.0565)	0.0395 (0.0720)	0.0395 (0.0720)	
environmental_rd	-0.0154 (0.0987)	-0.0237 (0.0306)	-0.000494 (0.0684)	0.0877 (0.0753)	0.0877 (0.0753)	0.0921*** (0.00170)
public	-0.0102 (0.0753)	0.0329 (0.0282)	-0.0240 (0.0655)	-0.0544 (0.0756)	-0.0544 (0.0756)	-0.0448** (0.0130)
long_term	-0.116* (0.0605)	-0.0429** (0.0147)	-0.115** (0.0362)	-0.0157** (0.00531)	-0.0157** (0.00531)	-0.0122 (0.0471)
dynamic	0.131* (0.0718)	0.000353 (0.0146)	0.0547 (0.0374)	-0.00866 (0.0113)	-0.00866 (0.0113)	-0.00393 (0.0306)
csd_control	0.0674 (0.0599)	0.0209 (0.0264)	0.0455 (0.0455)	-0.0220 (0.0182)	-0.0220 (0.0182)	-0.105 (0.0713)
htg_control	0.00956 (0.0937)	0.00395 (0.0212)	-0.00909 (0.0432)	0.00706 (0.0145)	0.00706 (0.0145)	0.163 (0.114)
endog_control	0.0958 (0.0628)	0.0241* (0.0146)	0.0584* (0.0345)	-0.00458 (0.0116)	-0.00458 (0.0116)	0.0126 (0.0521)
rd_lag	0.00929 (0.0532)	-0.0724*** (0.0214)	-0.0401 (0.0433)	-0.00199 (0.0181)	-0.00199 (0.0181)	0.0100 (0.0626)
rd_sq	0.179** (0.0854)	0.0163 (0.0714)	0.101 (0.0771)	0.0153 (0.0281)	0.0153 (0.0281)	0.0944 (0.109)
indep_var_pc	-0.206 (0.130)	-0.141** (0.0643)	-0.204** (0.0905)	-0.390*** (0.116)	-0.390*** (0.116)	
income	0.0899 (0.0829)	-0.00419 (0.0205)	0.0122 (0.0438)	-0.0652*** (0.0168)	-0.0652*** (0.0168)	-0.0285 (0.0425)
patents	-0.0386 (0.0853)	0.00973 (0.0252)	-0.0243 (0.0717)	-0.0295** (0.00999)	-0.0295** (0.00999)	-0.0655*** (0.00000197)
governance	-0.0249 (0.0948)	0.0263 (0.0253)	0.0130 (0.0649)	0.0242 (0.0318)	0.0242 (0.0318)	0.788 (0.497)
carbon_str	-0.150 (0.0966)	0.00104 (0.0194)	-0.0873** (0.0422)	0.0206 (0.0284)	0.0206 (0.0284)	0.140*** (0.0109)
mkt_openn	0.0436 (0.0430)	-0.0171 (0.0152)	0.0497 (0.0341)	0.00910 (0.0133)	0.00910 (0.0133)	-0.0114 (0.0344)
$\ln \hat{\tau}_0$				-1.751*** (0.138)	-16.77 (.)	
$\ln \hat{\tau}_1$					-1.751*** (0.138)	
N	169	169	169	169	169	169
p(Wald statistic > χ^2_{df})	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000	.
I2		92.80	98.37	92.80	92.80	
$\hat{\tau}$				0.17	0.17	
Within R2						0.3629
Between R2						0.0382
Overall R2						0.0000

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 14: Multivariate MRA General Specifications

Multivariate Statistical Properties	Test	Null Hypotesis	Result	Preferred Estimators
Heteroskedasticity	Breusch Pagan test	H0=Normality of errors	$\chi^2_1 = 13,22; p = 0,0003$	FE WLS, RE WLS
	White test	H0=No heteroskedasticity	$\chi^2_{126} = 168,82; p = 0,0065$	
Unexplained Heterogeneity	Cochran's Q-test	H0=No Heterogeneity	$\chi^2_{145} = 1957,35; p < 0,0001$	RE WLS
Study-Specific Effects	Breusch Pagan LM test	H0=No unobserved study-specific effects	$\bar{\chi}^2(0,1) = 4,36; p = 0,0184$	Cluster-Econometrics: RIML, RISML, FE Cluster
Random Slopes	Likelihood-Ratio test	H0=RIML is nested within RISML	$\chi^2_1 = 0,00; p = 1,0000$	RIML, FE Cluster
Endogeneity	Hausman test	H0=No endogeneity	$\chi^2_{16} = 53,65; p < 0,0001$	FE Cluster

Table 15: Best Multivariate MRA Estimator Selection Tests

Due to endogeneity between the set of attributes of reported estimates and the unobserved study effects, the best estimator for the multivariate model is the Fixed-Effects Cluster econometric estimator. This prevents the estimation of the covariates which do not vary within each study, as their influence is inevitably filtered out together with the unobserved primary studies' fixed-effects. In detail, the variables for which it is not possible to properly quantify the potential distorting effect are: national, unfccc, kyoto, copenhagen, non_oecd, mix_oecd, and indep_var_pc.

Nonetheless, the transformation of units implied by this estimator is expected also to diminish the predictive power of some remaining variables. In fact, as can be seen from Table 16, although varying, many of the suitable variables have very low variation within each study. When endogenous fixed-effects are partialled out, variables that are almost constant in the sample coincidentally will have little variation left. This can ultimately prevent a proper analysis of the impact even of the variables still included in the final model.

This, of course, constitutes a weakness of this dataset, as its properties make an in-dept study of variables harder.

variable	Overall St.Dev	Between St.Dev	Within St.Dev
avg_year	14,53	12,81	2,47
environmental_rd	0,40	0,38	0,10
public	0,37	0,36	0,09
long_term	0,49	0,42	0,30
dynamic	0,49	0,47	0,21
csd_control	0,46	0,45	0,18
htg_control	0,50	0,48	0,22
endog_control	0,48	0,44	0,26
rd_lag	0,43	0,34	0,21
rd_sq	0,23	0,14	0,11
income	0,41	0,38	0,19
patents	0,24	0,25	0,08
governance	0,30	0,25	0,11
carbon_str	0,49	0,49	0,09
mkt_openn	0,50	0,49	0,12

Table 16: Standard Deviations of The Set of Variables Included In The FE Cluster Multivariate MRA's

The correlation table of the remaining (varying between studies) variables is provided in Table E in the Appendix. The inclusion of all the variables together poses the risk of multicollinearity in the model. Thus, as discussed in section 3.2.2, to avoid the relative potential bias, conclusions will be based on the final specification obtained through the General-to-Specific technique.

Moreover, in order to avoid worsening the threat of high correlation between explanatories, moderators of selection bias have not been included in the model. Indeed, as it can be seen from equation 4, these factors are included through the addition of interaction terms involving the standard errors: this inevitably increase the level of correlation. Anyway, their inclusion is expected to not be relevant, due to the relatively low intensity of selection bias detected by the univariate PET-FAT.⁸ Moreover, following Stanley and Doucouliagos (2012), $\hat{\beta}_1$ is a reliable estimator of the total publication bias steering from a variety of channels; thus, their inclusion is not necessary, except for specific interests in the selection mechanism.

Finally, as n_controls is not expected to convey more information than the inclusion of its con-

⁸Although not explicit guide on thresholds of selection bias has been found in the consulted references from Stanley and Doucouliagos, Ugur et al. (2018), based on previous analysis by these two authors, suggests interpreting publication bias as *substantial* if $|\hat{\beta}_1|$ is greater than 1, and as *severe* if it is greater than 2.

stituent determinants of interest, while being inevitably highly correlated with them, it has been omitted from the estimation.⁹

⁹In practice, its inclusion would cause a *VIF* higher than 20: the variance inflation caused can potentially mask the significance of other covariates, which ultimately can potentially can lead to improper exclusions from the General specification.

	(1)	(2)
	General FE Cluster	Specific FE Cluster
$\hat{\beta}_0$	-3.939 (4.410)	-0.178*** (0.0431)
$\hat{\beta}_1$	-0.116*** (0.0302)	-0.123*** (0.0207)
avg_year	0.00186 (0.00220)	
environmental_rd	0.0921*** (0.00170)	0.0917*** (0.00116)
public	-0.0448** (0.0130)	-0.0414*** (0.00122)
long_term	-0.0122 (0.0471)	
dynamic	-0.00393 (0.0306)	
csd_control	-0.105 (0.0713)	-0.124* (0.0677)
htg_control	0.163 (0.114)	0.194** (0.0950)
endog_control	0.0126 (0.0521)	
rd_lag	0.0100 (0.0626)	
rd_sq	0.0944 (0.109)	
income	-0.0285 (0.0425)	
patents	-0.0655*** (0.00000197)	-0.0655*** (0.00000135)
governance	0.788 (0.497)	
carbon_str	0.140*** (0.0109)	0.141*** (0.00987)
mkt_openn	-0.0114 (0.0344)	
N	169	169
Clusters	48	48
Within R2	0.3629	0.1184
Between R2	0.0382	0.0500
Overall R2	0.0000	0.0002
VIF	3.41	1.63

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 17: Multivariate MRA Specific Model

The mean *Variance Inflation Factor* (VIF) statistic of both the General and the Specific models in Table 17 confirms a low level of collinearity in the model: the average degree of inflation of the variance of estimated coefficients, due to correlation between regressors, is lower than 4, as econometrics literature suggests it should be. This guarantees some level of reliability even for the initial, complete specification.

The most important result of this last estimation is the confirmation of a negative genuine effect, significant at the 1% level in the final specification.

Also selection bias is confirmed to be negative and highly significant, in both specification. Additionally, its estimated intensity is lower than in the univariate PET-FAT.

The interpretation of the fixed-effects moderators needs to take into account the potential omission of relevant explanatories, caused by the convenient General-to-Specific method. Thus, in line with Ugur et al. (2018), consistency of results will be inferred by comparison of the Specific model with its General counterpart: an impact in the Specific model is inferred as strongly significant if its sign is consistent in the two specification and it is significant even in the General counterpart; it is instead interpreted only as moderately consistent if it is not significant in the complete specification. For what concerns other variables, results are interpreted as an absence of evidence of their influence on the relation.

Four variables have a strongly significant impact on the elasticity of CO₂ with respect to R&D expenditures. The negative coefficient of `environmental_rd` suggests that the measured CO₂ mitigating effect of expenditures on R&D directly aimed at reducing environmental impact is lower than that of general R&D. Although some underlying, unobserved specific aspects might be involved in this apparently controversial result, this is coherent with what the literature discussed in section 2.2.1 suggests: R&D is also essential to enhance the applicability and the diffusion of those innovations which originally stem from the willingness to address specific goals. In this sense, investment projects aimed at environmental innovations need subsequent technologies and related expenditures to be effective. Since general R&D expenditures involve both the two types of investments, it can ultimately result that the aggregate innovating effort is more effective than the specific one.

The strongly significant negative coefficient for public provides evidence of the higher efficacy of governmental expenditures in meeting collective interests than the private sector alone. This confirms the crucial role of the political intervention to address innovating investments and ultimately enhancing the efficacy of R&D in mitigating emissions. Given that in this dataset public investments mostly coincide with environmental innovation expenditures, the two opposite effects almost compensated and, eventually, the measured mitigating effect of environmental R&D was similar to the one of general innovations expenditures, on average, *ceteris paribus*.

Consistently with the estimation output of the probit model discussed in section 4.2.1, the only two detected drivers of eco-innovation are the level of inventions (patents) and the energy consumption structure (`carbon_str`). Since, as explained, these two variables are related to their inclusion in

the primary estimated models, rather than to their level, this provides evidence of omitted variable bias resulting from not accounting for them. In detail, estimations which do not account for the level of successful innovations, estimate a milder mitigation effect of innovating investments (in this dataset, on average -25% in magnitude, *ceteris paribus*); those that do not include controls related to the quantity of energy produced from carbon-dioxide-emitting sources tend to highly overestimate it: in fact, the coefficients evidence that the true impact of R&D can be nullified by the inclusion of such type of controls.

Curiously, the sign of their impact is opposed to that estimated in the probit model. However, due to its greater limitations compared to the multivariate specification, the latter model should be considered more reliable. Nonetheless, the fact that both of the two models evidence the significance of their inclusion, encourages this conclusion.

The only two controls on the side of moderate consistency are related to estimation methods. In particular, estimations that do not control for cross section dependence across units, tended to underestimate the elasticity of R&D. Given that most studies focused on countries, this may support the existence and significance of global interactions on the level of efficacy of innovation. On the other hand, estimates obtained through methods that do not allowed for the heterogeneity of effects tended to highly overestimate the underlying effect. This instead supports the high heterogeneity of the relation across units, which may equally be reflected by the collected results in the dataset used.

5 Conclusions

This analysis ultimately confirmed the appropriateness of a Meta-Analysis approach in addressing research questions: this method enabled extensive empirical knowledge about the key theoretical questions on the connection between innovation and environmental impact. In fact, the two main kinds of models (Probit and Publication Bias) employed collectively produced evidence about each of the aspects discussed in the theoretical review.

Despite the only recent, still growing trend of empirical publications on this theme, this analysis confirms the effectiveness of innovation in mitigating humans environmental impact: although not directly dependent one from the other, investments in R&D ultimately allow to reduce CO₂ emissions levels. Public empirical knowledge strongly supports this conclusion, with minimal influence from publication bias.

However, this nexus is complex and, thus, determined by several aspects: likely because of that, it is extremely varied and this complicates both its quantification and the explanation of its divergences.

First of all, mitigation of carbon dioxide emissions takes time. The long term effect of innovation is more likely measured as negative than its immediate causal impact. Moreover, as suggested by Innovation Claudia Curve Theory, there are evidence that R&D expenditures may actually increase emissions for low levels of efficiency, and that its mitigating effect may only overturn the relation with higher investments.

Despite not causing systematic differences between collected estimates, geographical location has been evidenced as a better predictor of the elasticity of CO₂ to R&D expenditures than the economic development level. However, studies observing European and/or North American countries are not found to measure a mitigating effect significantly more often than in mixed samples. Only studies focused in Asia and Oceania have an incidence of negative coefficients significantly (at the 5%) higher than that of positive ones; nevertheless, these primary studies generally focus only in few specific Asian countries (Japan and, mostly, China), and this result is likely affected by that. Belonging to OECD and, so, being located in the area in which public environmental action has started and at the highest level of economic development, is not found to be significant for the direction of the relationship. Moreover, the inclusion of covariates related to income levels in primary studies' estimated models is insignificant for both the sign and magnitude of the included effect sizes.

Elasticities of general innovation investments are on average higher than those in environmental R&D. This result can be interpreted as the importance of spillovers of innovations in other, private sectors. This may allow applicability and diffusion of cleaner products and, eventually, fully leverage the mitigation potential of environmental inventions.

Public intervention is another factor evidenced as important for the enhancement of the reduction power. The fact that in the dataset used this type of investments mostly coincides with environ-

mental innovation, finally almost compensated the lower elasticity of environmental R&D. But, most importantly, it provides support to political action in addressing collective concerns, particularly regarding climate issues.

Instead, this analysis failed to provide evidence about the effectiveness of the main intergovernmental global actions occurred. However, since the main period of observation in primary studies covers the start of the political mobilization for climate, with a predominant focus on following years, results of this analysis are coincidentally also influenced by this movement.

Among the determiners of eco-innovation efficacy suggested by theory, two were found to be crucial: the level of successful innovations patented, and the energy supply structure. In particular, not accounting for them causes the risk of biased estimations of the effect size of R&D expenditures: included estimates that did not control for patents generally report a lower mitigation effect of innovation investments; not accounting for the level of dependence on energy produced from carbon-dioxide-emitting sources extremely impacts both the magnitude and sign of reported effect sizes.

Similarly to income, also for proxies of governance quality and market openness evidence of omitted variable bias were not detected. Anyway, for what concerns governance, the importance of public intervention through investments support was previously discussed. In the same way, although omission of international trade levels do not lead to significant deviations of estimates, importance of international relations was indirectly evidenced: the fact that not allowing for cross-sectional dependence in estimations affects reported outputs, induce presence of connections between units; and given that in primary studies units of observation are mostly countries, this indirectly evidences the relevance of globalization for CO₂ reduction.

Lastly, another methodological aspect of estimation that was evidenced as moderately significant is the allowance for heterogeneity of slopes between units. This furtherly supports the inherent high degree of heterogeneity of the relation between CO₂ and innovation.

Despite the possibility to provide evidence on almost all the aspects discussed by literature, the dataset used still manifests an imbalance of results on important aspects.

Estimates are highly focused on recurrent geographical areas, which ultimately prevents extensive, general knowledge about residual areas: in particular, for South America, Africa, and Mid West it was not possible to summarize general empirical knowledge, because of the lack of studies exclusively focusing on one of these areas alone. Anyway, even for the areas for which this was possible (North America, Europe, Asia and Oceania), actual published results mostly refer to some frequent countries, likely leading to biased generalization about them.

As it can be seen from the dataset summary statistics, also some features suggested as relevant by theoretical literature still have a low empirical coverage. This surely undermines the statistical power to draw conclusions and discourages generalizable conclusions.

Therefore, the increasing trend in empirical research on eco-innovation must be exploited to address future publication in providing more knowledge on less covered features. This would provide

higher statistical power to explain the extreme level of heterogeneity of results and, finally, give a clearer knowledge about this vital solution to global climate problem.

References

- Afrifa, G. A., Tingbani, I., Yamoah, F., and Appiah, G. (2020). Innovation input, governance and climate change: Evidence from emerging countries. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 161:120256.
- Ahmad, M., Khattak, S. I., Khan, A., and Rahman, Z. U. (2020). Innovation, foreign direct investment (fdi), and the energy–pollution–growth nexus in oecd region: a simultaneous equation modeling approach. *Environmental and Ecological Statistics*, 27:203–232.
- Alam, M. S., Apergis, N., Paramati, S. R., and Fang, J. (2021). The impacts of r&d investment and stock markets on clean-energy consumption and co2 emissions in oecd economies. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(4):4979–4992.
- Alam, M. S., Atif, M., Chien-Chi, C., and Soytaş, U. (2019). Does corporate r&d investment affect firm environmental performance? evidence from g-6 countries. *Energy Economics*, 78:401–411.
- Alnafisah, N., Alsmari, E., Alshehri, A., and Binsuwadan, J. (2024). Assessing the impacts of technological innovation on carbon emissions in mena countries: Application of the innovation curve theory. *Energies*, 17(4):904.
- Ang, J. B. (2009). Co2 emissions, research and technology transfer in china. *Ecological Economics*, 68(10):2658–2665.
- Apergis, N., Eleftheriou, S., and Payne, J. E. (2013). The relationship between international financial reporting standards, carbon emissions, and r&d expenditures: Evidence from european manufacturing firms. *Ecological Economics*, 88:57–66.
- Balli, E., Cengiz, O., Koca Balli, A. I., and Akar, B. G. (2023). Analyzing the nexus between tourism and co2 emissions: the role of renewable energy and r&d. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 11:1257013.
- Balsalobre-Lorente, D., Shahbaz, M., Roubaud, D., and Farhani, S. (2018). How economic growth, renewable electricity and natural resources contribute to co2 emissions? *Energy policy*, 113:356–367.
- Becker, B. J. and Wu, M.-J. (2007). The synthesis of regression slopes in meta-analysis.
- Buhr, K., Roth, S., Stigson, P., and Karlsson, A. (2012). *Comparisons of the Copenhagen Pledges: Analyses For Climate Change Professionals*. Svenska Miljöinstitutet.
- Cai, A., Zheng, S., Cai, L., Yang, H., and Comite, U. (2021). How does green technology innovation affect carbon emissions? a spatial econometric analysis of china’s provincial panel data. *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 9:813811.

- Card, D. and Krueger, A. B. (1995). Time-series minimum-wage studies: a meta-analysis. *The American Economic Review*, 85(2):238–243.
- Chen, W. and Lei, Y. (2018). The impacts of renewable energy and technological innovation on environment-energy-growth nexus: New evidence from a panel quantile regression. *Renewable energy*, 123:1–14.
- Chen, Y. and Lee, C.-C. (2020). Does technological innovation reduce co2 emissions? cross-country evidence. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 263:121550.
- Chen, Y. and Mkumbo, R. N. (2020). Analysing the impact of eco-innovation on carbon emissions abatement: evidence from oecd countries. *Int J Sustain Dev World Policy*, 9(2):154–165.
- Churchill, S. A., Inekwe, J., Smyth, R., and Zhang, X. (2019). R&d intensity and carbon emissions in the g7: 1870–2014. *Energy Economics*, 80:30–37.
- Cohen, J. (2013). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences*. routledge.
- Cole, M. A., Elliott, R. J., and Shimamoto, K. (2005). Industrial characteristics, environmental regulations and air pollution: an analysis of the uk manufacturing sector. *Journal of environmental economics and management*, 50(1):121–143.
- Cooper, H., Hedges, L. V., and Valentine, J. C. (2019). *The handbook of research synthesis and meta-analysis*. Russell Sage Foundation.
- Dietz, T. and Rosa, E. A. (1994). Rethinking the environmental impacts of population, affluence and technology. *Human ecology review*, 1(2):277–300.
- Dietz, T. and Rosa, E. A. (1997). Effects of population and affluence on co2 emissions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 94(1):175–179.
- Doucouliafos, C. (2011). How large is large? preliminary and relative guidelines for interpreting partial correlations in economics.
- EDGAR (2024). EDGAR (Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research) Community GHG Database: A collaboration between the European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), the International Energy Agency (IEA), comprising IEA-EDGAR CO₂, EDGAR CH₄, EDGAR N₂O, EDGAR F-GASES version EDGAR_2024_GHG (2024). IEA-EDGAR CO₂ (v3), a component of the EDGAR Community GHG database version EDGAR_2024_GHG (2024), including or based on data from IEA (2023), Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Energy, available at www.iea.org/statistics, as modified by the Joint Research Centre. https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/report_2024?vis=ghgpop#data_download. [Accessed: 9-Jan-2025].
- Egger, M., Smith, G. D., Schneider, M., and Minder, C. (1997). Bias in meta-analysis detected by a simple, graphical test. *bmj*, 315(7109):629–634.

- Elsevier (2024). Scopus citescore 2023. <https://www.scopus.com/sources.uri?zone=TopNavBar&origin=>. [Accessed: July 2024].
- European Commission (2021). Transition Performance Index TPI. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/support-policy-making/support-national-research-and-innovation-policy-making/transitions-performance-index-tpi_en#documents. [Accessed: 17-Jan-2024].
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Research, Innovation, Prevost, S., Benavente, D., Stevenson, A., Caperna, G., and Panella, F. (2022). *Transitions performance index 2021 – Towards fair and prosperous sustainability*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Feld, L. P. and Heckemeyer, J. H. (2011). Fdi and taxation: A meta-study. *Journal of economic surveys*, 25(2):233–272.
- Fernández, Y. F., López, M. F., and Blanco, B. O. (2018). Innovation for sustainability: the impact of r&d spending on co2 emissions. *Journal of cleaner production*, 172:3459–3467.
- Ganda, F. (2019). The impact of innovation and technology investments on carbon emissions in selected organisation for economic co-operation and development countries. *Journal of cleaner production*, 217:469–483.
- García, C. D., Martínez, F. J. S., and Moreno, Á. G. (2014). Ecoinnovation: insights from a literature review. In *ICSB World Conference Proceedings*, page 1. International Council for Small Business (ICSB).
- Garrone, P. and Grilli, L. (2010). Is there a relationship between public expenditures in energy r&d and carbon emissions per gdp? an empirical investigation. *Energy policy*, 38(10):5600–5613.
- Goulder, L. H. (1997). Induced technological change. *Crowding Out, and the Attractiveness of CO2 Emissions Abatement (draft)*.
- Grossman, G. and Krueger, A. (1991). Environmental impacts of a north american free trade agreement. *natl bur econ res*.
- Grubb, M. (2004). Technology innovation and climate change policy: an overview of issues and options. *Keio economic studies*, 41(2):103–132.
- Harrer, M., Cuijpers, P., Furukawa, T., and Ebert, D. (2021). *Doing meta-analysis with R: A hands-on guide*. Chapman and Hall/CRC.
- Hedges, L. V. and Olkin, I. (2014). *Statistical methods for meta-analysis*. Academic press.
- Herzer, D. (2022). The impact on domestic co2 emissions of domestic government-funded clean energy r&d and of spillovers from foreign government-funded clean energy r&d. *Energy Policy*, 168:113126.

- Hicks, J. R. (1932). The theory of wages macmillan and co. *Ltd., London*.
- Huang, J., Liu, Q., Cai, X., Hao, Y., and Lei, H. (2018). The effect of technological factors on china's carbon intensity: new evidence from a panel threshold model. *Energy Policy*, 115:32–42.
- Iancu, I. A., Hendrick, P., Micu, D. D., Stet, D., Czumbil, L., and Cirstea, S. D. (2022). Decreasing co2 emissions from energy generation and consumption to achieve the green deal targets. In *2022 2nd International Conference on Energy Transition in the Mediterranean Area (SyNERGY MED)*, pages 1–7. IEEE.
- IMF (October 2024). Real GDP Growth: Annual Percentage Change. https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/NGDP_RPCH@WEO/OEMDC/ADVEC/WEOWORLD. [Accessed 12-01-2025].
- Jiang, Y., Hossain, M. R., Khan, Z., Chen, J., and Badeeb, R. A. (2024). Revisiting research and development expenditures and trade adjusted emissions: green innovation and renewable energy r&d role for developed countries. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 15(1):2156–2191.
- Jiao, J., Yang, Y., and Bai, Y. (2018). The impact of inter-industry r&d technology spillover on carbon emission in china. *Natural Hazards*, 91(3):913–929.
- Jin, L., Duan, K., Shi, C., and Ju, X. (2017). The impact of technological progress in the energy sector on carbon emissions: an empirical analysis from china. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 14(12):1505.
- Kahouli, B. (2018). The causality link between energy electricity consumption, co2 emissions, r&d stocks and economic growth in mediterranean countries (mcs). *Energy*, 145:388–399.
- Khan, H., Khan, I., and BiBi, R. (2022). The role of innovations and renewable energy consumption in reducing environmental degradation in oecd countries: an investigation for innovation claudia curve. *Environmental science and pollution research*, 29(29):43800–43813.
- Kihombo, S., Saud, S., Ahmed, Z., and Chen, S. (2021). The effects of research and development and financial development on co2 emissions: evidence from selected wame economies. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(37):51149–51159.
- Knapp, G. and Hartung, J. (2003). Improved tests for a random effects meta-regression with a single covariate. *Statistics in medicine*, 22(17):2693–2710.
- Kocak, E. and Alnour, M. (2022). Energy r&d expenditure, bioethanol consumption, and greenhouse gas emissions in the united states: Non-linear analysis and political implications. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 374:133887.
- Koçak, E. and Ulucak, Z. Ş. (2019). The effect of energy r&d expenditures on co 2 emission reduction: estimation of the stirpat model for oecd countries. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 26:14328–14338.

- Kuznets, S. (1955). Economic growth and income inequality. *The American Economic Review*, 45(1):1–28.
- Lee, H.-S., Moseykin, Y. N., and Chernikov, S. (2021a). Sustainable relationship between fdi, r&d, and co2 emissions in emerging markets: An empirical analysis of brics countries. *Russian Journal of Economics*, 7(4):297–312.
- Lee, J.-Y., Marotzke, J., Bala, G., Cao, L., Corti, S., Dunne, J. P., Engelbrecht, F., Fischer, E., Fyfe, J. C., Jones, C., et al. (2021b). Future global climate: scenario-based projections and near-term information. In *Climate change 2021: The physical science basis. Contribution of working group I to the sixth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change*, pages 553–672. Cambridge University Press.
- Lee, K.-H. and Min, B. (2015). Green r&d for eco-innovation and its impact on carbon emissions and firm performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 108:534–542.
- Leggett, J. A. (2020). The united nations framework convention on climate change, the kyoto protocol, and the paris agreement: a summary. *UNFCCC: New York, NY, USA*, 2.
- Li, M. and Wang, Q. (2017). Will technology advances alleviate climate change? dual effects of technology change on aggregate carbon dioxide emissions. *Energy for Sustainable Development*, 41:61–68.
- Lin, B. and Zhu, J. (2019). The role of renewable energy technological innovation on climate change: Empirical evidence from china. *Science of the Total Environment*, 659:1505–1512.
- Mamkhezri, J. and Khezri, M. (2024). Assessing the spillover effects of research and development and renewable energy on co2 emissions: international evidence. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 26(3):7657–7686.
- Matos, S., Viardot, E., Sovacool, B. K., Geels, F. W., and Xiong, Y. (2022). Innovation and climate change: A review and introduction to the special issue. *Technovation*, 117:102612.
- Mensah, C. N., Long, X., Boamah, K. B., Bediako, I. A., Dauda, L., and Salman, M. (2018). The effect of innovation on co2 emissions of oced countries from 1990 to 2014. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 25:29678–29698.
- Mentel, G., Tarczyński, W., Azadi, H., Abdurakmanov, K., Zakirova, E., and Salahodjaev, R. (2022). R&d human capital, renewable energy and co2 emissions: evidence from 26 countries. *Energies*, 15(23):9205.
- Mor, S., Aneja, R., Madan, S., and Ghimire, M. (2024). Kyoto protocol and paris agreement: transition from bindings to pledges—a review. *Millennial Asia*, 15(4):690–711.
- Mourshed, M. and Quddus, M. A. (2009). Renewable energy rd&d expenditure and co2 emissions in 15 european countries. *International Journal of Energy Sector Management*, 3(2):187–202.

- Nachtigall, D., Lutz, L., Rodríguez, M. C., Hašič, I., and Pizarro, R. (2022). The climate actions and policies measurement framework: A structured and harmonised climate policy database to monitor countries' mitigation action.
- Nakicenovic, N. and Swart, R. (2000). Intergovernmental panel on climate change special report on emissions scenarios.
- Newell, R. G. (2009). Literature review of recent trends and future prospects for innovation in climate change mitigation.
- Ni, X., Wang, Z., Akbar, A., and Ali, S. (2022). Natural resources volatility, renewable energy, r&d resources and environment: Evidence from selected developed countries. *Resources Policy*, 77:102655.
- Normand, S.-L. T. (1999). Meta-analysis: formulating, evaluating, combining, and reporting. *Statistics in medicine*, 18(3):321–359.
- OECD (10-11-2023). Climate actions and policies measurement framework. [https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?fs\[0\]=Topic%2C1%7CEnvironment%20and%20climate%20change%23ENV%23%7CEnvironmental%20policy%23ENV_POL%23&pg=0&fc=Topic&bp=true&snb=7&df\[ds\]=dsDisseminateFinalDMZ&df\[id\]=DSD_CAPMF%40DF_CAPMF&df\[ag\]=OECD.ENV.EPI&df\[vs\]=1.0](https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?fs[0]=Topic%2C1%7CEnvironment%20and%20climate%20change%23ENV%23%7CEnvironmental%20policy%23ENV_POL%23&pg=0&fc=Topic&bp=true&snb=7&df[ds]=dsDisseminateFinalDMZ&df[id]=DSD_CAPMF%40DF_CAPMF&df[ag]=OECD.ENV.EPI&df[vs]=1.0). [Accessed: 19-Jan-2024].
- Olhoff, A., Christensen, J., Lamb, W. F., Pathak, M., Kuramochi, T., Fransen, T., Rogelj, J., den Elzen, M., Portugal-Pereira, J., Grant, N., et al. (2024). Emissions gap report 2024: No more hot air... please! with a massive gap between rhetoric and reality, countries draft new climate commitments.
- Özokcu, S. and Özdemir, Ö. (2017). Economic growth, energy, and environmental kuznets curve. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 72:639–647.
- Pata, U. K., Destek, M. A., Manga, M., and Cengiz, O. (2023). Militarization of nato countries sparks climate change? investigating the moderating role of technological progress and financial development. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 409:137241.
- Petrović, P. and Lobanov, M. M. (2020). The impact of r&d expenditures on co2 emissions: evidence from sixteen oecd countries. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 248:119187.
- Reed, W. R. (2020). A note on the use of partial correlation coefficients in meta-analyses. Technical report.
- Saeed, A. and Iqbal, J. (2024). Exploring asymmetric influence of r&d expenditures on co2 emissions in china: evidence from nonlinear ardl model. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 31(9):13089–13099.

- Sarkodie, S. A. and Strezov, V. (2019). A review on environmental kuznets curve hypothesis using bibliometric and meta-analysis. *Science of the total environment*, 649:128–145.
- Shaari, M. S., Abdullah, D. N. C., Alias, N. S. B., and Adnan, N. S. M. (2016). Positive and negative effects of research and development. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 6(4):767–770.
- Shahbaz, M., Nasir, M. A., Hille, E., and Mahalik, M. K. (2020). Uk’s net-zero carbon emissions target: Investigating the potential role of economic growth, financial development, and r&d expenditures based on historical data (1870–2017). *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 161:120255.
- Shahbaz, M., Nasir, M. A., and Roubaud, D. (2018). Environmental degradation in france: the effects of fdi, financial development, and energy innovations. *Energy economics*, 74:843–857.
- Shahzadi, I., Yaseen, M. R., Khan, M. T. I., Makhdum, M. S. A., and Ali, Q. (2022). The nexus between research and development, renewable energy and environmental quality: Evidence from developed and developing countries. *Renewable Energy*, 190:1089–1099.
- Shao, X., Zhong, Y., Li, Y., and Altuntaş, M. (2022). Does environmental and renewable energy r&d help to achieve carbon neutrality target? a case of the us economy. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 29(58):87426–87445.
- Singh, S. (2006). Kyoto protocol: Toothless and obsolete. *Panjab University Research Journal (Arts)*, 38(2):33–42.
- Stanley, T., Doucouliagos, H., et al. (2007). Identifying and correcting publication selection bias in the efficiency-wage literature: Heckman meta-regression. *Economics Series*, 11(2007):629–634.
- Stanley, T. D. (2008). Meta-regression methods for detecting and estimating empirical effects in the presence of publication selection. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and statistics*, 70(1):103–127.
- Stanley, T. D. and Doucouliagos, H. (2012). *Meta-Regression Analysis in Economics and Business*. routledge.
- Stanley, T. D. and Doucouliagos, H. (2014). Meta-regression approximations to reduce publication selection bias. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 5(1):60–78.
- Stanley, T. D. and Jarrell, S. B. (2005). Meta-regression analysis: a quantitative method of literature surveys. *Journal of economic surveys*, 19(3):299–308.
- StataCorp (2023). *xtprobit — Random-effects and population-averaged probit models for panel data*. StataCorp LLC, College Station, TX. Stata Manual.
- Stern, D. I. (2017). The environmental kuznets curve after 25 years. *Journal of Bioeconomics*, 19:7–28.

- Ugur, M., Awaworyi Churchill, S., and Solomon, E. (2018). Technological innovation and employment in derived labour demand models: A hierarchical meta-regression analysis. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 32(1):50–82.
- Vélez-Henao, J.-A., Vivanco, D. F., and Hernández-Riveros, J.-A. (2019). Technological change and the rebound effect in the stirpat model: A critical view. *Energy Policy*, 129:1372–1381.
- Veroniki, A. A., Jackson, D., Viechtbauer, W., Bender, R., Bowden, J., Knapp, G., Kuss, O., Higgins, J. P., Langan, D., and Salanti, G. (2016). Methods to estimate the between-study variance and its uncertainty in meta-analysis. *Research synthesis methods*, 7(1):55–79.
- Vitenu-Sackey, P. A. and Acheampong, T. (2022). Impact of economic policy uncertainty, energy intensity, technological innovation and r&d on co2 emissions: evidence from a panel of 18 developed economies. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(58):87426–87445.
- Wang, J., Wang, L., and Qian, X. (2021). Revisiting firm innovation and environmental performance: New evidence from japanese firm-level data. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 281:124446.
- Wang, Q. and Zhang, F. (2020). Does increasing investment in research and development promote economic growth decoupling from carbon emission growth? an empirical analysis of brics countries. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 252:119853.
- Xu, B. and Lin, B. (2018). Assessing the development of china’s new energy industry. *Energy Economics*, 70:116–131.
- Xu, Q. and Khan, S. (2023). How do r&d and renewable energy consumption lead to carbon neutrality? evidence from g-7 economies. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(5):4604.
- Yang, Y., Cai, W., and Wang, C. (2014). Industrial co2 intensity, indigenous innovation and r&d spillovers in china’s provinces. *Applied energy*, 131:117–127.
- Yu, Y. and Du, Y. (2019). Impact of technological innovation on co2 emissions and emissions trend prediction on ‘new normal’ economy in china. *Atmospheric Pollution Research*, 10(1):152–161.
- Yu, Y. and Xu, W. (2019). Impact of fdi and r&d on china’s industrial co2 emissions reduction and trend prediction. *Atmospheric Pollution Research*, 10(5):1627–1635.
- Zhai, S. and Song, G. (2013). Exploring carbon emissions, economic growth, energy and r&d investment in china by ardl approach. In *2013 21st International Conference on Geoinformatics*, pages 1–6. IEEE.
- Zhang, Y.-J., Peng, Y.-L., Ma, C.-Q., and Shen, B. (2017). Can environmental innovation facilitate carbon emissions reduction? evidence from china. *Energy Policy*, 100:18–28.

Appendix

Country	Policies	2011		2012		2013		2014		2015		2016		2017		2018		2019		
		Stringency	Pol	Str																
Australia	37	13.27	40	14,16	40	15,31	39	14,92	39	14,92	39	14,91	41	21,50	41	20,86	42	22,35	41	22,87
Austria	39	14.69	39	15,18	40	15,20	41	16,41	42	15,59	45	23,30	45	23,30	45	23,88	45	24,68	48	28,82
Belgium	35	13.43	38	15,09	35	13,37	40	15,30	40	14,42	39	14,57	41	22,17	41	22,17	41	22,32	42	24,48
Canada	41	16.33	42	15,56	45	15,69	46	16,89	45	16,44	49	24,38	48	25,29	50	29,71	51	30,59		
Chile	15	3.53	16	3,89	18	3,76	28	5,73	30	6,31	31	6,93	33	15,48	37	20,10	40	20,90		
Colombia	11	2.74	13	2,75	13	2,78	16	3,44	17	3,75	20	5,01	26	7,52	27	14,42	28	14,86		
Costa Rica	13	3.79	14	3,93	13	3,84	14	3,93	16	4,16	19	11,73	23	16,45	23	16,82	25	17,86		
Czechia	36	13.84	36	13,78	37	13,59	38	13,84	38	13,86	39	14,10	41	21,63	39	23,18	41	24,96		
Denmark	40	15.23	42	15,89	44	16,37	46	18,04	46	17,98	49	25,36	49	25,86	49	28,96	50	30,49		
Estonia	27	13.06	28	8,94	31	13,76	33	12,88	33	12,67	38	20,47	38	18,93	39	20,59	43	25,28		
Finland	34	14.50	37	15,29	38	15,54	39	16,75	39	17,02	43	24,65	45	29,54	47	29,73	47	29,78		
France	38	17.27	38	17,49	40	18,02	44	18,70	44	18,21	46	25,33	51	29,56	52	31,28	53	33,74		
Germany	38	14.45	39	14,57	40	15,78	41	15,75	43	15,49	47	28,02	47	28,82	47	29,76	50	31,65		
Greece	33	7.99	25	5,96	27	6,40	28	7,70	28	7,63	31	14,33	29	14,09	30	15,50	35	19,18		
Hungary	32	9.77	32	9,60	37	7,80	36	8,63	38	9,01	39	17,61	40	20,84	40	18,90	45	22,94		
Iceland	9	3.79	9	3,87	10	3,92	11	4,14	15	4,22	17	11,73	19	15,38	21	17,30	21	17,84		
Ireland	38	9.69	38	10,77	40	9,88	39	10,26	40	12,34	43	18,03	43	17,83	44	18,52	48	24,42		
Israel	17	4.99	18	4,84	18	4,84	18	4,61	21	4,87	22	11,21	22	11,13	24	11,73	24	11,86		
Italy	35	13.18	36	13,04	39	14,13	42	14,32	41	14,07	45	22,26	47	22,73	47	22,80	49	26,90		
Japan	32	15.42	37	16,33	38	15,98	40	17,47	40	16,78	43	26,33	44	26,16	46	27,32	46	27,36		
Korea	35	16.21	35	16,26	34	15,72	36	15,43	40	16,64	42	23,61	43	23,28	43	23,20	45	26,95		
Latvia	17	5.09	17	5,02	18	5,29	22	6,82	23	6,59	23	6,94	26	14,45	26	15,13	28	19,39		
Lithuania	21	6.48	21	6,38	24	7,03	26	7,77	26	7,50	25	7,90	27	14,87	28	16,07	40	25,87		
Luxembourg	21	7.97	27	13,56	18	5,72	19	6,27	20	5,91	22	13,52	24	18,00	24	18,56	25	19,28		
Mexico	16	3.91	17	4,04	28	5,79	32	6,65	37	6,37	43	15,93	44	16,25	41	15,46	39	14,50		
Netherlands	33	12.87	35	13,55	39	13,83	39	13,82	42	15,01	42	14,79	46	24,84	46	24,98	47	25,98		
New Zealand	32	10.30	32	9,81	29	8,55	32	9,76	34	9,06	35	16,44	38	20,81	39	22,08	44	25,45		
Norway	39	16.98	42	16,76	43	17,18	44	18,15	47	22,62	49	31,35	49	31,87	49	32,87	49	32,34		
Poland	39	14.61	39	12,45	42	13,59	44	13,77	44	12,82	46	18,89	47	18,12	47	18,59	47	19,79		
Portugal	32	7.81	37	8,60	40	10,71	37	10,83	41	10,26	33	15,11	36	19,21	37	20,13	48	27,52		
Slovak Republic	32	12.14	32	12,18	35	12,68	36	12,24	38	9,41	40	19,15	40	17,24	40	18,07	44	22,00		
Slovenia	27	6.06	27	6,12	28	6,63	29	7,28	29	7,01	31	14,21	32	14,45	31	14,92	33	18,06		
Spain	38	13.05	40	12,22	36	9,55	41	11,75	42	12,79	40	11,65	42	17,65	47	23,79	48	24,82		
Sweden	40	14.19	41	14,57	42	15,29	43	15,96	43	14,60	46	22,16	43	27,14	50	29,14	51	29,37		
Switzerland	36	16.00	36	16,14	38	16,89	39	18,17	40	18,35	40	19,39	43	27,91	44	28,81	46	32,80		
Türkiye	21	5.29	21	5,44	23	6,04	32	8,94	36	9,39	36	10,37	37	10,33	36	10,10	36	10,40		
United Kingdom	41	16.14	43	15,72	44	16,51	45	17,04	48	17,23	51	28,40	51	29,44	51	31,25	51	32,06		
United States	0	0.00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00	0	0,00		
Annual Average	29	10.69	31	10,78	32	10,87	34	11,59	35	11,61	37	17,28	38	20,00	39	21,29	41	23,53		

Table A: Environmental Polices Adopted and Average Stringency Level in OECD Countries Between 2011 and 2019.

Source: (OECD, 2023)

Country	2011		2012		2013		2014		2015		2016		2017		2018		2019	
	Economic	Environmental	Ec	Env														
Australia	24	72	25	72	23	71	24	71	24	71	23	69	27	70	27	70	28	71
Austria	9	30	9	30	9	32	9	33	9	33	9	32	8	34	8	34	8	34
Belgium	13	41	13	38	12	39	13	34	12	37	11	38	11	37	12	33	11	31
Canada	19	70	20	71	20	72	20	72	18	72	18	72	18	72	19	72	19	72
Chile	47	48	47	48	46	49	48	47	44	47	44	48	46	47	45	48	48	51
Colombia	59	9	59	6	59	18	59	17	57	13	59	13	61	8	65	7	65	9
Czechia	22	42	22	40	22	41	22	39	21	41	22	37	21	38	20	38	20	36
Denmark	8	13	8	11	7	10	7	6	3	5	3	6	5	6	5	6	4	5
Estonia	23	55	23	51	26	56	28	54	25	50	28	53	28	57	25	54	25	45
Finland	2	58	4	57	3	57	5	55	10	54	10	55	10	54	11	56	13	55
France	17	25	18	23	18	26	17	25	20	25	20	23	20	21	21	17	21	14
Germany	6	22	6	25	6	28	3	27	8	26	7	26	7	26	7	19	7	20
Greece	41	26	40	27	40	24	40	23	40	22	40	20	42	20	42	23	42	19
Hungary	30	12	31	8	31	11	30	13	30	14	31	14	31	15	31	16	31	16
Iceland	10	69	11	69	11	70	11	70	11	69	12	71	14	71	14	71	12	70
Ireland	12	10	12	12	14	12	12	8	2	8	2	8	2	9	2	9	3	7
Israel	20	60	19	61	19	58	19	56	17	57	17	56	16	53	16	53	16	54
Italy	25	14	24	7	24	5	26	3	28	6	24	4	24	4	24	4	23	3
Japan	18	40	17	42	16	40	16	36	16	34	16	34	17	31	17	32	18	35
Latvia	38	5	38	5	37	7	38	9	38	9	41	9	38	10	38	12	39	10
Lithuania	32	17	32	18	32	21	32	21	33	24	32	25	32	28	32	27	32	27
Luxembourg	4	59	3	60	4	59	6	53	6	52	6	49	9	49	9	51	9	49
Mexico	54	24	53	24	54	27	54	28	51	27	52	27	52	25	52	26	53	26
Netherlands	14	32	15	34	13	29	14	29	14	29	14	29	13	24	13	20	14	21
New Zealand	26	66	27	66	27	66	25	66	23	68	25	65	25	66	26	64	27	64
Norway	11	52	10	52	10	52	10	51	13	53	15	51	15	51	15	50	15	44
Poland	37	36	36	33	36	33	36	32	36	31	34	33	36	36	34	36	33	33
Portugal	33	15	34	14	34	14	34	14	35	17	36	16	33	17	36	15	35	13
Slovakia	34	33	33	29	33	31	33	31	32	32	35	31	35	33	35	35	36	32
Slovenia	16	38	16	35	17	30	18	30	19	30	19	30	19	30	18	30	17	30
South Korea	7	63	5	64	5	64	4	63	4	63	4	63	3	63	3	63	2	63
Spain	27	23	29	21	29	20	29	19	31	19	30	18	30	18	30	21	29	18
Sweden	3	43	2	44	2	43	2	43	7	39	8	41	4	41	6	41	5	39
Switzerland	1	4	1	3	1	6	1	5	1	4	1	5	1	5	1	5	1	6
Turkey	44	45	44	46	44	38	42	40	42	42	42	43	40	43	40	43	40	43
United Kingdom	21	3	21	4	21	3	21	1	22	1	21	1	22	1	22	1	22	1
United States	15	68	14	68	15	68	15	68	15	66	13	66	12	64	10	66	10	66
Annual Average	22	36	22	36	22	36	22	35	22	35	22	35	22	35	22	34	23	33

Table B: Economic and Environmental Transition Indexes in OECD Countries Between 2011 and 2019.

Source: (European Commission, 2021)

	avg_year	unifcc	kyoto	copenhagen	non_oecd	mix_oecd	only_euam	only_asiaoc	long_term	rd_lag	rd_sq	environmental_rd	public	income	patents	governance	carbon_str	mkt_openn	n_controls		
avg_year	1.00																				
unifcc	0.85	1.00																			
kyoto	0.61	0.54	1.00																		
copenhagen	0.38	0.25	0.46	1.00																	
non_oecd	-0.14	-0.26	-0.18	-0.01	1.00																
mix_oecd	0.16	0.17	0.00	0.12	-0.26	1.00															
only_euam	-0.21	0.00	-0.23	-0.13	-0.35	0.07	1.00														
only_asiaoc	-0.17	-0.29	-0.22	-0.08	-0.33	1.00															
long_term	-0.22	-0.22	-0.01	-0.17	-0.09	0.09	1.00														
rd_lag	-0.14	-0.28	-0.26	-0.05	-0.19	-0.11	0.26	1.00													
rd_sq	-0.14	-0.02	0.00	-0.12	0.20	-0.08	0.22	1.00													
environmental_rd	0.10	0.02	0.19	-0.25	-0.36	-0.17	-0.32	0.14	1.00												
public	0.07	-0.03	0.11	-0.22	-0.32	-0.15	0.16	0.18	0.06	-0.10	0.80	1.00	-0.14	-0.14	0.06	-0.10	0.13	-0.07			
income	0.04	0.12	0.15	0.22	0.04	-0.05	0.01	0.06	-0.27	0.11	-0.08	-0.14	1.00	-0.08	0.07	0.14	0.14	0.51			
patents	0.18	0.16	0.21	0.16	0.08	-0.11	0.01	0.11	-0.18	-0.07	-0.16	-0.14	-0.08	1.00	0.08	0.19	-0.09	0.36			
governance	0.15	0.16	0.22	0.01	-0.25	0.00	-0.15	0.16	0.08	-0.08	0.30	0.06	0.07	0.08	1.00	0.32	0.01	0.48			
carbon_str	0.33	0.37	0.33	-0.03	-0.16	-0.05	-0.14	-0.20	-0.17	0.20	-0.05	-0.10	0.14	0.19	0.32	1.00	0.04	0.67			
mkt_openn	-0.09	-0.21	-0.02	-0.04	0.20	-0.03	-0.16	0.11	0.03	0.13	0.02	0.13	0.14	-0.09	0.01	0.04	1.00	0.49			
n_controls	0.23	0.22	0.31	0.09	0.03	-0.10	-0.23	0.19	-0.17	0.14	-0.02	-0.07	0.51	0.36	0.48	0.67	0.49	1.00			

Table C: Correlation Table of The Probit Model's Set of Variables of Interest

In bold correlations higher than 0,5 in absolute value.

	R13L		RIML 1-99th		RIML 5-95th		RIML 10-90th	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	PET-FAT	PEESE	PET-FAT	PEESE	PET-FAT	PEESE	PET-FAT	PEESE
$\hat{\beta}_0$	-0.0127 (0.0254)	-0.0747** (0.0261)	-0.0317 (0.0233)	-0.0488** (0.0231)	-0.0177 (0.0168)	-0.0484** (0.0184)	-0.0148 (0.0137)	-0.0494*** (0.0148)
$\hat{\beta}_1$	-1.979*** (0.274)		-0.434** (0.178)		-0.818*** (0.177)		-0.982*** (0.182)	
$\hat{\beta}_2$		-1.6441 (1.207)		-0.0279 (0.168)		-0.0581 (0.168)		-0.0447 (0.168)
N	76	76	166	166	152	152	135	135
p	0.0000	0.1733	0.2269	0.8519	0.0008	0.7364	0.0002	0.8104
I2	90.35	91.84	93.06	93.43	86.84	88.30	79.27	83.11
I2 _{ID}	98.93	99.16						
I2 _{Geographical Area}	0.00	0.00						
τ_{ID}	0.11	0.12	0.15	0.15	0.10	0.12	0.07	0.09
$\tau_{Geographical Area}$	0.00	0.00						

Standard errors in parentheses

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table D: Heterogeneity Inspection MRA

	avg_year	environmental_rd	public	long_term	dynamic	csd_control	htg_control	endog_control	rd_lag	rd_sq	income	patents	governance	carbon_str	mkt_openn	n_controls
avg_year	1,00	0,11	0,08	-0,22	-0,08	0,08	0,26	0,00	-0,12	-0,13	0,02	0,16	0,15	0,35	-0,07	0,23
environmental_rd	0,11	1,00	0,79	0,12	0,18	0,00	-0,02	0,13	-0,01	-0,12	-0,07	-0,13	0,32	-0,06	0,01	0,00
public	0,08	0,79	1,00	0,15	0,16	-0,14	-0,19	0,22	0,05	-0,10	-0,14	-0,11	0,07	-0,11	0,13	-0,06
long_term	-0,22	0,12	0,15	1,00	0,13	0,29	0,03	0,29	-0,14	-0,13	0,07	0,21	0,14	0,05	0,13	0,19
dynamic	-0,08	0,18	0,16	0,13	1,00	0,14	-0,18	-0,01	0,11	-0,09	0,01	0,20	0,28	0,32	-0,22	0,16
csd_control	0,08	0,00	-0,14	0,29	0,14	1,00	0,55	-0,09	-0,12	-0,15	0,24	0,00	0,39	0,23	0,01	0,30
htg_control	0,26	-0,02	-0,19	0,03	-0,18	0,55	1,00	-0,13	-0,16	0,10	-0,02	0,06	0,28	0,18	-0,08	0,12
endog_control	0,00	0,13	0,22	0,29	-0,01	-0,09	-0,13	1,00	-0,18	-0,17	-0,15	0,29	-0,16	-0,07	0,24	0,03
rd_lag	-0,12	-0,01	0,05	-0,14	0,11	-0,12	-0,16	-0,18	1,00	-0,13	-0,26	-0,14	0,09	-0,19	0,00	-0,17
rd_sq	-0,13	-0,12	-0,10	-0,13	-0,09	-0,15	0,10	-0,17	-0,13	1,00	0,12	-0,06	-0,08	0,19	0,12	0,16
income	0,02	-0,07	-0,14	0,07	0,01	0,24	-0,02	-0,15	-0,26	0,12	1,00	-0,18	0,07	0,16	0,18	0,53
patents	0,16	-0,13	-0,11	0,21	0,20	0,00	0,06	0,29	-0,14	-0,06	-0,18	1,00	0,08	0,32	-0,01	0,32
governance	0,15	0,32	0,07	0,14	0,28	0,39	0,28	-0,16	0,09	-0,08	0,07	0,08	1,00	0,30	-0,03	0,46
carbon_str	0,35	-0,06	-0,11	0,05	0,32	0,23	0,18	-0,07	-0,19	0,19	0,16	0,32	0,30	1,00	-0,01	0,70
mkt_openn	-0,07	0,01	0,13	0,13	-0,22	0,01	-0,08	0,24	0,00	0,12	0,18	-0,01	-0,03	-0,01	1,00	0,51
n_controls	0,23	0,00	-0,06	0,19	0,16	0,30	0,12	0,03	-0,17	0,16	0,53	0,32	0,46	0,70	0,51	1,00

Table E: Correlation Table of The Set of Variables Included In The FE Cluster Multivariate MRA's

In bold correlations higher than 0,5 in absolute value.

List of Figures

1	Environmental policies adoption and stringency trends between 2011 and 2019 Bars represent the OECD countries' average number of adopted policies per type. The green line represents the average aggregate number of climate policies adopted. The red line depicts the average stringency level of all the policies adopted. <i>Source:</i> OECD (2023)	9
2	Economic and Environmental Transition Indexes Trends The left-hand side scale represents the unit of measure of the bars. The right-hand side scale represents the unit of measures of the lines. <i>Source:</i> European Commission (2021)	12
3	Number of papers related to innovation for climate change in the top ten innovation journals (1990-2021). <i>Source:</i> Matos et al. (2022)	14
4	Meta-Analysis in economics over time. <i>Source:</i> Stanley and Doucouliagos (2012)	24
5	Random-Effects model distribution of effect sizes. <i>Source:</i> Harrer et al. (2021)	28
6	Publication bias. The slope of the relation between estimates and their SE equals the inverse Mills' ratio at the critical value a . In the image are depicted the two kinds of relation discussed. When there is no publication bias, $E(\text{effect} \text{No PB})$ is constant and, consequently, it is well represented by a linear function of SE: the estimates will randomly vary around the true effect (as it is shown for low values of SE in the graph). On the other hand, when reported estimates are influenced by publication bias, $E(\text{effect} \text{PB})$ is better represented by a quadratic function of SE: as the degree of precision of estimates decreases, estimates' magnitude must be many times higher than their standard error in order to achieve significance. Anyway, most precise estimates still randomly vary around the true effect, as they are less influenced by selection bias <i>Source:</i> Stanley and Doucouliagos (2012)	32
7	Mixed-Effects Model. Deviation effect of each of the two types of explanatory on the reported estimate. Above, it is depicted the effect that fixed-effects have on $\hat{\theta}$. Assuming one sub-group distinction between A and B, each of the two groups of studies will have its own distinct average effect: $\hat{\theta}_A$ and $\hat{\theta}_B$, with their respective distribution. Below is represented the (unique) random level effect: inside each the two sub-groups A and B, any aleatory value of the random study's characteristic, embodied in the random level, leads to a own specific distribution from which relative reported estimate are drawn. Of course, several random levels and sub-groups generally affects estimate simultaneously. <i>Source:</i> Harrer et al. (2021)	34
8	2-Levels Random-Effects model structure <i>Source:</i> Harrer et al. (2021)	37
9	3-Levels Random-Effects model structure <i>Source:</i> Harrer et al. (2021)	38
10	Meta-analytical instruments set and the estimation strategy map <i>Source:</i> Feld and Heckemeyer (2011)	40
11	Magnitude per Publication Year The y-axis represents the collected effect sizes, respectively as elasticities in figure 11a, and as partial correlations in figure 11b. The abscissa represents the year of publication of the primary study from which each estimate has been retrieved.	61

12	Sample Distribution of magnitude and pcc Bars represent the density of the respective interval of values. The blue continuous line is the average value. In figure 12a dashed lines represent Cohen (2013)'s general thresholds of economic practical significance: the yellow, the orange, and the red ranges respectively represent the small, the medium, and the large practical effects areas. In figure 12b dashed lines depicts the Doucouliagos (2011)'s pcc thresholds, instead: the yellow, the orange, and the red lines respectively represent the small, the moderate, and the large effects areas.	62
13	Funnel Plot and Random-Effect Estimated 95% Confidence Interval of The Effect Size The red line is placed at the value of the computed Random-Effects weighted average θ_{REML} . The grey lines represent the associated confidence interval at the 95% level.	64
14	Margins Plot of the Average Partial Effects From The Final Probit Model Estimation Plotted confidence intervals at the 10% level.	71
15	Influentials in The Funnel Plot of Elasticities Due to their relatively extreme precision, the two influentials would exert too much influence on the weighted average effect size.	73

List of Tables

1	Primary Studies Included	50
2	Dataset Variables *To avoid missings values, Journals not included in the Scopus CiteScore 2023 - i.e.: Iancu et al. (2022); Jiao et al. (2018); Zhang et al. (2017) - are assigned the minimum value of 2.6, which is the lowest score attained by the Journals included.	53
3	Cumulative Sample Observed Summary Statistics Summary statistics about the number of estimates per primary study, the period of publication and observed, and the sample dimension.	57
4	Correlation Between Geographical Variables In bold correlations higher than 0,5 in absolute value. Since only <i>_afrsammw</i> is 0 for each unit, its correlation is undefined.	58
5	Summary Statistics of Effect Sizes and Controls <i>magnitude</i> and <i>st_err</i> have fewer observation due to the inconvertibility of estimates in Zhang et al. (2017).	59
6	Average Partial Effects On The Probability Of Measuring A Negative Effect	69
7	Influentials Descriptives <i>dfbeta</i> index represents the deviation in the pooled fixed-effects weighted average due to their inclusion in the sample, in terms of standard deviations. If an estimate has a <i>dfbeta</i> higher than 1 it was recognized as an influential and, thus, removed from the following analysis.	73
8	PET-FAT Selection Bias Meta-Regression Analysis <i>POLS</i> refers to Pooled OLS; <i>WLS FE</i> and <i>WLS RE</i> respectively to Fixed-Effects and Random-Effects WLS; <i>RIML</i> and <i>RISML</i> respectively to the Random-Intercept and Random-Intercept-and-Slopes Multilevel Models; <i>FE Cluster</i> to the estimation of the Fixed-Effects Multilevel Model through Fixed-Effects Cluster econometric estimator.	74
9	Best PET-FAT Estimator Selection Tests	74
10	PEESE Selection Bias Meta-Regression Analysis	75
11	Best PEESE Estimator Selection Tests Since no variation of slopes is detected in the <i>RISML</i> specification of PEESE (see Table 10), it coincides with the <i>RIML</i> specification.	76
12	PET-FAT Selection Bias MRA on PCC	79
13	Best PET-FAT on PCC Estimator Selection Tests	79
14	Multivariate MRA General Specifications	81
15	Best Multivariate MRA Estimator Selection Tests	82
16	Standard Deviations of The Set of Variables Included In The FE Cluster Multivariate MRA's	83
17	Multivariate MRA Specific Model	85
A	Environmental Polices Adopted and Average Stringency Level in OECD Countries Between 2011 and 2019. Source: (OECD, 2023)	99
B	Economic and Environmental Transition Indexes in OECD Countries Between 2011 and 2019. Source: (European Commission, 2021)	100
C	Correlation Table of The Probit Model's Set of Variables of Interest In bold correlations higher than 0,5 in absolute value.	101
D	Heterogeneity Inspection MRA	102
E	Correlation Table of The Set of Variables Included In The FE Cluster Multivariate MRA's In bold correlations higher than 0,5 in absolute value.	103